

COST Action CA24136

**NextGen Synergy:
Control Theory & Machine Learning**

Book of Abstracts

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April 27-30, 2026
Prague, Czech Republic

ABSTRACTS OF THE CONTRIBUTIONS PRESENTED AT THE INAUGURAL CONFERENCE OF COST ACTION CA24136 NEXTGEN SYNERGY: CONTROL THEORY & MACHINE LEARNING

Prague Czech Republic

April 27-30, 2026

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Dear Participant,

Welcome to Prague for the inaugural conference of COST Action CA24136: NextGen Synergy: Control Theory & Machine Learning.

It is a pleasure and an honor to host you in our historic city, a place where beautiful architecture and cultural heritage meet a deep-rooted scientific tradition. Walking these streets, we follow in the footsteps of figures such as Tycho Brahe, Johannes Kepler, Christian Doppler, Albert Einstein, and Jaroslav Heyrovský — an inspiring setting for our scientific endeavors.

We hope this Book of Abstracts highlights topics of deep interest to you and that the conference sparks lively discussion, collaboration, and new friendships. Enjoy the sessions, Prague's hospitality, and the rich opportunities for exchange.

Thank you for your valuable contribution to the success of this inaugural event!

With kind regards,

The Local Organizing Committee

PROGRAMME

MONDAY, APRIL 27

8:30 – 9:00 Registration

SESSION I

Chair: Lars Grüne

9:00 – 9:20 Welcome

9:20 – 10:20 **Invited Talk:** Dante Kalise (Imperial College London)

Learning to Control: Scalable Approximation of Value Functions for High-Dimensional Optimal Control

10:20 – 10:40 **Contributed Talk:** Mario Sperl (University of Bayreuth)

Avoiding the Curse of Dimensionality in Structured Control Problems via Separable Neural Networks

10:40 – 11:10 Coffee Break

SESSION II

Chair: Miroslav Kárný

11:10 – 12:10 **Invited Talk:** David Rios Insua (ICMAT-CSIC)

Control Theory and Adversarial Machine Learning

12:10 – 12:30 **Contributed Talk:** Juan Ricardo Muñoz (University of Dubrovnik)

Reduced-Order Modeling for Parameter-Dependent Optimal Control: A map-parameter-to-latent approach

12:30 – 12:50 **Contributed Talk:** Mario Chacón-Falcón (ICMAT-CSIC)

Opponent-Aware Soft Q-Learning

12:50-14:20 Lunch Break

SESSION III

Chair: Martin Lazar

14:20 – 14:40 **Contributed Talk:** Mohamed Boukaf (Université Paris Saclay)

Deep Riemannian Control: Formally Verified Neural Observers and Controllers via Contraction Theory

14:40 – 15:00 **Contributed Talk:** Edoardo Caldarelli (Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia)

Linear Quadratic Control of Nonlinear Systems with Koopman Operator Learning and the Nyström method

15:00 – 15:20 **Contributed Talk:** Ion Necoara (Politehnica Bucuresti)

Deep Unfolding Primal/Dual Architectures: Application to Linear Model Predictive Control

15:20 – 16:20 **Roundtable I: Adversarial, Risk Aware Decision Making in Multi Agent Systems.**

Moderator: David Rios Insua

Discussants: Leon Bungert, Mario Chacón-Falcón, Agnieszka Wiszniewska-Matyszkiewicz.

16:20 – 16:50 **Poster Session A: Spotlights**

Chair: James Kennedy

16:50 – 17:50 Poster Session A and Coffee Break

#12 - Maja Jolić, Sanja Konjik

On Controllability of Linear Fractional Time-Varying Systems and Fractional Evolution Equations

#13 - Júlia Kafková, Michal Skuba, Pavol Kuchár

Reinforcement Learning Approach for Traffic Signal Control

#23 - Hasibe Candan Kadem, Mustafa Özgür Cingiz

Graph-Based Relational Learning for Cyber-Attack Detection in Water Distribution ICS: An Imbalance-Aware Study on BATADAL

#26 – Muhammet Berigel

Control-Informed Machine Learning for Modeling Migration Intention Dynamics: Evidence from a Youth Emigration Survey

#27 - Michal Pražienka, Pavol Kuchár

Digital Twin of the City of Zilina

#28 - Jan Saro

Digital Twin of a Dairy Herd: Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning and LLM Explainability for Farm Optimisation

#36 – Matthieu Barreau, Loïc Michel

An Integral Controller for Physics-Informed Learning

#39 - Aleksej Gaj, Miroslav Kárný

Relating Discrete-Valued Random Variables: Advanced Bayesian Structure Estimation

#46 - Maria Filipkovska

Qualitative Analysis of Degenerate Evolution Equations Arising when Modelling Neural, Electrical and Gas Networks

#53 - Antonie Brožová, Michal Uliáš, Ondřej Tichý, Václav Šmídl

Bayesian Inversion Methods and Toolbox for Their Application to Accidental Radionuclide Releases

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#54 - Jurij Ružejnikov, Tatiana V. Guy

Tuning Robust Sequential Decision-Making Models in Adversarial Environments

#61 - Akhil John, Armando Mendes, Marko Ruman

AI Techniques for Anomaly Assessment in Port Structures

17:50 – 18:40 Excursions to Human Behaviour Research Lab & Agricultural Processing Training Centre

19:00 – 22:00 BEER Party

TUESDAY, APRIL 28

SESSION IV

Chair: Hendrik Kleikamp

9:00 – 10:00 **Invited Talk:** Matthieu Barreau (KTH Royal Institute of Technology)

Learning Maximal Lyapunov Functions

10:00 – 10:20 **Contributed Talk:** Stefan Ratschan (Institute of Computer Science, Czech Academy of Sciences)

Certifying Properties of Control Systems: Algorithms, Verification, and Theory

10:20 – 10:50 Coffee Break

SESSION V

Chair: Francisco Periago

10:50 – 11:50 **Invited Talk:** Enrique Zuazua (Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen–Nürnberg)

Machine Learning from a Control Perspective

11:50 – 12:10 **Contributed Talk:** Erlend Grong (University of Bergen)

Controllability on Landmark Manifolds with Applications to Shapes and Neural ODEs

12:10 – 12:30 **Contributed Talk:** Agnieszka Wiszniewska-Matyszkiewicz (University of Warsaw)

When Beliefs about Reality Influence Reality - May ML Result in Sticking in Belief-Distorted Nash Equilibria?

12:30 – 14:00 Lunch Break

SESSION VI

Chair: Vladimir Jaćimović

14:00 – 14:20 **Contributed Talk:** Leon Bungert (University of Wuerzburg)

Concentration Phenomena of Self-Attention Dynamics

14:20 – 14:40 **Contributed Talk:** Özkan Öztürk (Giresun University)
Control of Dynamical Systems on Time Scales: Bridging Continuous and Discrete Learning Frameworks

14:40 – 15:40 **Roundtable II: Learning-Based Methods for High-Dimensional Control and Stability Certification**

Moderator: Francisco Periago

Discussants: Matthieu Barreau, Martin Lazar, Enrique Zuazua.

15:40 – 16:10 Coffee Break

SESSION VII

Chair: Leon Bungert

16:10-17:10 **Invited Talk:** Kathrin Flaßkamp (Saarland University)
Learning with Structure: How Systems and Control Theory Shapes ML for Dynamical Systems

17:10-17:30 **Contributed Talk:** Carlo Guastamacchia (Politecnico di Milano)
LDNets: Latent Dynamics Networks, an Architecture to Learn and Predict Time Variant Fields

17:30-18:40 **CORE Group Meeting**

WEDNESDAY, APRIL 29

SESSION VIII

Chair: Dante Kalise

9:00 – 10:00 **Invited Talk:** Petr Stluka (Siemens)
Industrial Perspective on Control and ML

10:00 – 10:20 **Contributed Talk:** Cesare Molinari (UniGE)
Learning From Data via Overparameterization

10:20 – 10:50 Coffee Break

SESSION IX

Chair: David Rios Insua

10:50 – 11:50 **Invited Talk:** Nicolò Cesa-Bianchi (University of Milan)
Online Learning in Digital Markets

11:50 – 12:10 **Contributed Talk:** Miroslav Kárný (UTIA AVCR)
Recursive Estimation of ARX Model with Parameters Dependent on High-Dimensional Discrete-Valued Regressors

12:10 – 12:30 **Contributed Talk:** Birgit Hillebrecht (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology)
A Rigorous Framework to Certify Predictions from Physics-Informed Neural Networks

12:30 – 12:40 **Event Photo** – All participants

12:40 – 14:00 Lunch Break

SESSION X **Chair:** Cesare Molinari

14:00 – 14:20 **Contributed Talk:** Carlos Doebeli (Imperial College London)
A Polynomial Approximation Scheme for Nonlinear Model Reduction

14:20 – 14:40 **Contributed Talk:** Vladimir Jacimovic (University of Montenegro)
Policy Gradients for Deep Directional Reinforcement Learning

14:40 – 15:00 **Contributed Talk:** Lucas Moschen (Imperial College London)
On the Local Stabilisation of Interacting Particle Systems and its Connection to Energy Convexification

15:00 – 15:20 **Contributed Talk:** Květoslav Belda (UTIA)
Mathematical Modelling and Model-Based Control Design for Energy-Optimal Motion of Industrial Robots

15:20 – 15:40 **Contributed Talk:** Tim Keil (TNG Technology Consulting GmbH)
An Efficient and Adaptive Machine Learning Surrogate for Optimal Control in Enhanced Oil Recovery

15:40 – 16:10 Coffee Break

SESSION XI **Chair:** Edoardo Caldarelli

16:10 – 17:10 **Roundtable III: SWOT: Integrating Contemporary Control and Machine Learning**

Moderator: Lars Grüne

Discussants: Nicolò Cesa-Bianchi, Dante Kalise, Miroslav Kárný, Petr Stluka.

17:10 – 17:40 **Poster Session B: Spotlights**

17:40 – 18:40 Poster Session B and Coffee Break

#6 – Tuncer Acar

Sampling Series as A Unified Approximation Framework for Control and Machine Learning

#14 – Júlia Kafková, Pavol Kuchár

Stress Detection in the Workplace Using Digital Twin Technology and Multimodal Physiological Sensing

#15 - Ahmed Amine Tabbassi, Stephan Henkler

Decision-Focused Learning Meets Distributionally Robust Optimization: A Unified Framework for Sugar Beet Yield Maximization Under Epistemic Uncertainty

#16 - Yahya Danayiyen, Amina Alshekh

Model Predictive Control and Machine Learning-Based Grid-Forming Inverters: The Combination of Control and Learning for Low-Inertia Power Systems

#19 - Jongrae Kim, Onur Kadem

Learning-Phase Stability in Actor-Critic Reinforcement Learning: Analysis and Stabilisation

#35 - Matthias Menge, Michael Günther, Peter Zaspel

Data-Driven Identification of Port-Hamiltonian DAE Systems by Gaussian Processes

#37 - Yannick Lunk, Sebastian Scott, Leon Bungert

Sparse Training of Neural Networks based on Multilevel Mirror Descent

#40 – Sara-Viola Kuntz, Christian Kuehn

Structural Constraints on Expressivity in Continuous-Depth Neural Networks

#44 - Krzysztof Rykaczewski, Grzegorz Gabor, Michał Balicki, Piotr Przymus

Cone-Constrained Neural Networks for Structured Learning and Control

#49 - Tomáš Martínek

Transcription of Czech Administrative Records Written in Kurrent Script into Latin Script Using Machine Learning, OCR, and AI

#57 - Chia-Hsun Lu, Yuan-Hung Chao, Chih-Ya Shen

Multi-Teacher GNN Knowledge Transfer for Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks

#59 - Siavash Fakhimi Derakhshan, Ladislav Jirsa, Tatiana V. Guy

Imitation Learning Framework Based on Fully Probabilistic Design

#60 – Marko Ruman, Tatiana V. Guy

N-to-1 Knowledge Transfer in Reinforcement Learning via Adaptive Q-function Selection

19:30 – 23:00 **Conference Dinner**

THURSDAY, APRIL 30

SESSION XII

Chair: Luca Dede'

- 9:00 – 10:00 **Invited Talk:** Markus Abel (Ambrosys)
Optimization and Machine learning in Traffic and Sensor Signals
- 10:00 – 10:20 **Contributed Talk:** Patricia Pauli (Eindhoven University of Technology)
Non-conservative Stability Analysis of Linear Systems in Feedback with ReLU Neural Networks
- 10:20 – 10:50 Coffee Break

SESSION XIII

Chair: Sanja Konjik

- 10:50 – 11:10 **Contributed Talk:** Francisco Periago Esparza (Technical University of Cartagena)
SIMONet: A Deep Learning Framework for Learning Set-Valued Maps. Application to Control
- 11:10 – 11:30 **Contributed Talk:** Dennis Gramlich (RWTH Aachen)
Convex Synthesis of Mini-Batch Gradient Methods
- 11:30 – 11:50 Closing Session
- 11:50 – 13:30 Farewell Lunch**
- 15:00 – 17:00 Guided Prague Tour (starts at Old Town Square)

Note: April 30 — *Witches' Night (Walpurgis Night): a traditional spring festival; in the Czech Republic it is celebrated with large bonfires and social gatherings.*

INVITED TALKS

Dante Kalise (Imperial College London, UK)

Title: Learning to Control: Scalable Approximation of Value Functions for High-Dimensional Optimal Control

Abstract

The curse of dimensionality in optimal control is not a wall; it is a design problem. We present a framework that addresses it through principled architecture selection, bespoke optimisation, and rigorous approximation theory. The payoff is scalable, certifiable feedback laws for mean-field and large-scale collective systems.

David Rios Insua (Institute of Mathematical Sciences, ICMAT-CSIC, Spain)

Title: Control theory and adversarial machine learning

Abstract

Numerous autonomous systems in areas such as social robotics, automated driving systems, or drones, are driven by decision-theoretic control models that rely on various machine learning (ML) algorithms for information processing and decision-making purposes. Such ML components are susceptible of being attacked by malicious adversaries to alter the decisions made by the system in a negative manner. This is the realm of a relatively recent field of adversarial machine learning whose aim is to robustify ML algorithms against adversarial attacks. In the talk, I shall describe problems and some solutions in relation to incorporating AML algorithms into autonomous systems, with a focus on social robots as applied domain.

The talk is based on various pieces of work with S. Liu, M. Santos, A. Nuñez, M. Chacón, T. Guy and M. Karyn.

Matthieu Barreau (KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden)

Title: Learning Maximal Lyapunov Functions

Abstract

Lyapunov functions are essential tools in control theory for guaranteeing stability and performance. In this talk, we will introduce how to learn Lyapunov functions for finite-dimensional continuous-time dynamical systems with an application to the estimation of the maximal region of attraction.

Enrique Zuazua (Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen–Nürnberg, Germany)

Title: Machine Learning from a Control Perspective

Abstract

Machine Learning has emerged as one of the most transformative forces in contemporary science and technology. In this lecture, I will discuss Machine Learning through the lens of applied mathematics, highlighting its connections with control theory, partial differential equations, and numerical analysis.

Kathrin Flaßkamp (Saarland University, Germany)

Title: Learning with Structure: How Systems and Control Theory Shapes Machine Learning for Dynamical Systems

Abstract

Machine learning has emerged as a powerful tool for modeling and controlling complex dynamical systems, yet many approaches overlook structural properties with a long-standing history in systems and control theory. This plenary highlights how symmetry, invariants, Hamiltonian structure, and optimality conditions can be embedded into learning architectures for dynamical systems and optimal control. Enforcing such structure through model design, loss functions, and constraints leads to methods that are data-efficient, interpretable, and compatible with control objectives. Examples include symmetry-aware and Hamiltonian neural networks as well as optimality-informed learning for parametric control problems. Overall, the perspective bridges model-based and data-driven approaches, showing how machine learning and control theory can mutually inform and advance one another.

Petr Stluka (Siemens, Czech Republic)

Title: Industrial Perspective on the Interplay between Control and Machine Learning

Abstract

For decades, industrial automation has leveraged core control theory applications—such as PID control, Kalman filters, and Model Predictive Control—to significantly boost the efficiency and safety of industrial operations. On the other hand, the successful integration of Machine Learning in this domain was relatively limited until its dramatic expansion over the past decade, culminating in the recent Generative AI revolution. This presentation will explore the synergistic and occasionally antagonistic interplay between control theory and machine learning, with a specific focus on intelligent building applications. The talk will present the historical context and discuss future challenges in this evolving landscape.

Nicolò Cesa-Bianchi (University of Milan, Italy)

Title: Online Learning in Digital Markets

Abstract

Online learning explores algorithms that acquire knowledge sequentially, through repeated interactions with an unknown environment. The general goal is to understand how fast an agent can learn based on the information received from the environment. Digital markets, with their complex ecosystems of algorithmic agents, offer a rich landscape of sequential decision-making problems, characterized by diverse decision spaces, utility functions, and feedback mechanisms. This talk will demonstrate how tackling challenges within digital markets has not only advanced our understanding of machine learning capabilities but also revealed novel insights into algorithmic efficiency and decision-making under uncertainty.

Markus Abel (Ambrosys, Germany)

Title: Optimization and Machine learning in Traffic and Sensor Signals

Abstract

In this talk, I will present challenges that arise in an industrial setting.

1. *The planning of traffic, in particular in urban areas, map matching, and optimal planning of an autonomous drive.* The major part of the talk will be on the first scenario, where the main tension is between individual goals (often: quickest path) and global ones (reduce overall emissions in a city). This turns very quickly into a high-dimensional, multi-objective problem where machine learning can be one approach to solve it.
2. *Map matching of noisy positions to a network of roads.* Traditionally, this is solved by Hidden Markov Models, where the goal is to determine the optimal path on a map with positions that are noisy.
3. *Deployment of AI software on hardware with restrictions (memory, CPU, scheduling involving other processes, safety, security).* This will be a minor part of the talk and shall illustrate the potential that optimization and machine learning have in real-world applications. Typically, packaging is done automated, for most applications that means, however, that restrictions on hardware are not considered from the beginning. The design of a feedback loop on development and efficient packaging is an example how problems may arise at places one does not think from the beginning.

The talk will end with a summary and conclusion to put these problems in the context of the COST CA24136.

Sampling series as a unified approximation framework for control and machine Learning

Tuncer Acar^{1,2}

¹Selçuk University, Department of Mathematics

²Selçuk University, Constructive Mathematical Analysis Research Laboratory (CMARL)

tunceracar@gmail.com

Keywords

Sampling series, Approximation theory, Sampled-data control, Machine learning, Operator-theoretic methods

1 Introduction

Sampling series constitute a classical yet powerful mathematical framework for approximating continuous-time functions and operators from discrete data. While traditionally rooted in signal processing and approximation theory, sampling-based representations naturally arise in control theory through sampled-data systems and in machine learning through data-driven function approximation (see, e.g. [1, 2, 3]). The growing interaction between control theory and machine learning calls for approximation frameworks that are not only expressive but also analytically transparent, stability-aware, and compatible with feedback mechanisms. Sampling series provide a natural candidate for such a unifying framework.

2 Main contribution

We employ generalized sampling series within an operator-theoretic setting to connect continuous-time dynamical systems with learning algorithms operating on discrete observations. On the control side, sampling-based operators are used to construct stable and convergent approximations of system dynamics, control laws, and observers, consistent with sampled-data and networked control paradigms. On the machine learning side, sampling series define structured hypothesis spaces and kernel-like representations that allow learning from finite data while retaining explicit approximation orders and stability properties. By combining these viewpoints, we develop a unified mathematical framework in which approximation accuracy, stability, and generalization can be analyzed jointly, supporting hybrid control–learning methodologies.

3 Conclusions

The proposed perspective positions sampling series as a common mathematical language at the interface of control theory and machine learning. By embedding learning mechanisms into analytically tractable approximation operators, the framework contributes to ongoing efforts within InterCoML to integrate control-theoretic guarantees into data-driven models. This approach opens avenues for structured learning in feedback systems and for principled hybrid designs where learning and control interact in a theoretically consistent manner.

References

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Control of Dynamical Systems on Time Scales: Bridging Continuous and Discrete Learning Frameworks

Özkan Öztürk¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Arts and Sciences, Giresun University, Giresun Türkiye

drozkanozturk@outlook.com, ozkan.ozturk@giresun.edu.tr

Keywords

time scale theory, control of dynamical systems, hybrid systems, stability, unification and extension

1 Introduction

Many real-world dynamical systems evolve in time in ways that cannot be adequately described as purely continuous or purely discrete. Physical processes are often continuous, while sensing, actuation, communication, and learning updates occur at discrete or irregular time instants. This mismatch in temporal structure is a fundamental challenge in modern control systems, particularly in networked control, cyber–physical systems, event-triggered control, and learning-based feedback architectures.

A time scale, denoted by \mathbb{T} , is a nonempty closed subset of the set of real numbers \mathbb{R} . It was first introduced by Stefan Hilger in his PhD thesis in 1988 [7] to unify the results in continuous and discrete analysis into one comprehensive theory and to remove the similarities from both. The time scales calculus has a tremendous potential for applications. For example, it can model insect populations that are continuous while in season (and may follow a difference scheme with variable step-size), die out in (say) winter, while their eggs are incubating or dormant, and then hatch in a new season, giving rise to a nonoverlapping population [5]. In this theory, derivatives and integrals are defined in a more general way, including discrete and continuous cases. In the last two decades, the theory of time scales has become a very popular topic of research in mathematics, economics, mathematical biology, optimization, and engineering; see [1, 3, 4, 8]. Since the calculus of time scales may be unfamiliar to some readers, we refer to [5, 6] and the references therein for a comprehensive introduction.

One of the key strengths of time scale theory is that it enables results to be formulated once and interpreted across multiple time domains. Classical differential equations arise when the time scale is the set of real numbers \mathbb{R} , while difference equations correspond to the integers \mathbb{Z} . More general choices of time scales allow the modeling of nonuniform sampling, impulsive effects, intermittent actuation, and event-driven dynamics. This unifying viewpoint reduces duplication of theoretical effort and reveals structural connections that are not apparent when continuous and discrete systems are studied separately.

From a control theory perspective, time scale systems offer a natural language for the analysis and design of controllers for hybrid and sampled-data systems. Stability concepts such as Lyapunov stability, asymptotic stability, and robustness can be formulated in a way that remains valid regardless of the underlying temporal structure. In particular, the graininess function, which characterizes the local density of the time scale, plays a crucial role in capturing the effects of variable sampling and event-based execution on system behavior.

2 Main Contributions

In this work, we present a general perspective on the control of dynamical systems on time scales, emphasizing its potential as a bridge between classical control theory and modern learning-based control frameworks. Rather than proposing a specific algorithm such as only continuous or only discrete, we aim to highlight how time scale theory offers a foundational and flexible framework for integrating control and learning under hybrid temporal structures while preserving rigorous analytical guarantees. We provide a unified formulation of control systems on arbitrary time scales, encompassing continuous-time, discrete-time, and hybrid dynamical models within a single analytical framework. Under the time scale framework, we discuss Lyapunov-based stability analysis and control design techniques that are intrinsic to time scale

theory and do not rely on tools exclusive to continuous-time analysis, see e.g., [9, 8, 3, 2]. This unified approach enables rigorous stability guarantees to be established across heterogeneous temporal domains. Furthermore, we demonstrate how the graininess function inherent to time scale theory can be explicitly incorporated into feedback control laws, yielding controllers that naturally adapt to variable sampling rates, event-based execution, and intermittent actuation. These structural properties reveal a close connection between time scale control systems and machine learning–assisted control paradigms, including sampled-data learning, data-driven parameter updates, and hybrid continuous–discrete optimization. In this sense, time scale theory provides a mathematically sound foundation for the analysis and design of learning-enabled control systems while preserving essential control-theoretic properties such as stability, robustness, and performance.

3 Conclusion

The interaction between control theory and machine learning calls for mathematical frameworks capable of rigorously handling hybrid temporal behavior. Time scale theory offers such a framework by unifying continuous and discrete dynamics and enabling systematic control design under variable and adaptive timing.

By framing control problems on time scales, one obtains a natural bridge between classical feedback control and modern learning-based methodologies. This perspective allows learning mechanisms to be embedded into control architectures without sacrificing analytical guarantees, and it opens new avenues for the design and analysis of intelligent control systems operating in hybrid environments.

The ideas presented here highlight the potential of time scale theory as a foundational tool for future research at the intersection of control theory and machine learning, particularly in hybrid systems, event-triggered control, and data-driven feedback design.

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Null-controllability of the linear Kuramoto-Sivashinsky equation on star-shaped trees

Cristian M. Cazacu² Liviu I. Ignat¹, Ademir F. Pazoto³

¹ Institute of Mathematics “Simion Stoilow” of the Romanian Academy, 21 Calea Grivitei Street, 010702 Bucharest, Romania

² Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, 14 Academiei Street, 010014 Bucharest, Romania

³ Instituto de Matemática, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, P.O. Box 68530, CEP 21945-970, Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brasil

cristian.cazacu@fmi.unibuc.ro, liviu.ignat@gmail.com, ademir@im.ufrj.br

Keywords

Kuramoto-Sivashinsky equation, null-controllability, star-shaped trees, method of moments

1 Introduction

In this talk we present some previous results of the authors [1] on the null controllability of equations on metric graphs. We consider two control problems on the same simple network formed by the edges of a tree. Our main goal is to study boundary null-controllability properties for the Kuramoto-Sivashinsky (KS) equation

$$y_t + \lambda y_{xx} + y_{xxxx} = 0, \quad (1)$$

on a star-shaped tree denoted Γ . More precisely, Γ is a simplified topological graph with $N \geq 2$ edges e_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, of the same given length $L > 0$ and $N + 1$ vertices. Besides, all edges intersect at a unique endpoint which is the interior vertex of the graph. The mathematical formulation of the control problems that we address on Γ stands for a system of N -KS equations on the interval $(0, L)$ coupled through the left endpoint $x = 0$ as follows

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} y_t^k + \lambda y_{xx}^k + y_{xxxx}^k = 0, \quad (t, x) \in (0, T) \times (0, L) \\ y^i(t, 0) = y^j(t, 0), \quad t \in (0, T), \quad i, j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \sum_{k=1}^N y_x^k(t, 0) = 0, \quad t \in (0, T) \\ y_{xx}^i(t, 0) = y_{xx}^j(t, 0), \quad t \in (0, T), \quad i, j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \sum_{k=1}^N y_{xxx}^k(t, 0) = 0, \quad t \in (0, T) \\ y^k(0, x) = y_0^k(x), \quad x \in (0, L). \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

For system (2) we study two types of boundary control conditions:

$$(I) : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} y^k(t, L) = 0, \\ y_x^k(t, L) = u^k(t), \quad k \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \end{array} \right.$$

respectively

$$(II) : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} y_x^k(t, L) = a^k(t), \\ y_{xxx}^k(t, L) = b^k(t), \quad k \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \end{array} \right.$$

The focus here is on the following null-controllability issue:

Given any finite time $T > 0$ and any initial state $y_0 = (y_0^k)_{k=1, N}$, can we find proper control inputs in (I) or (II) ($u = (u^k)_{k=1, N}$ and $a = (a^k)_{k=1, N}$, $b = (b^k)_{k=1, N}$, respectively) to lead the solution of system (2) to the zero state, i.e.,

$$y^k(T, x) = 0, \quad \text{for all } x \in (0, L) \quad \text{and} \quad k \in \{1, \dots, N\}? \quad (3)$$

2 Main contribution

We introduce some special sets \mathcal{N} 's

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{N}_1 &:= \left\{ \frac{\pi^2}{4L^2} ((2m)^2 + (2n)^2) : (m, n) \in \mathbb{N}^2, 1 \leq m < n \right\}, \\ \mathcal{N}_{mixt} &:= \left\{ \frac{\pi^2}{4L^2} ((2m)^2 + (2n+1)^2) : (m, n) \in \mathbb{N}^2, 1 \leq m, 0 \leq n \right\}, \\ \mathcal{N}_{odd} &:= \left\{ \frac{\pi^2}{4L^2} ((2m+1)^2 + (2n+1)^2) : (m, n) \in \mathbb{N}^2, 0 \leq m < n \right\},\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.1 (Null-controllability for model (2)-(I)) *Let $T > 0$ be fixed and $\lambda \notin \mathcal{N}_1 \cup \mathcal{N}_{odd}$. Then*

1. *For any given edge e_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and any initial state $y_0 = (y_0^k)_{k=1, N} \in L^2(\Gamma)$, there exist controls $u = (u^k)_{k=1, N} \in (H^1(0, T))^N$ with $u^i(t) = 0$ for all $t \in (0, T)$, such that the solution of system (2)-(I) satisfies*

$$y^k(T, x) = 0, \text{ for all } x \in (0, L) \text{ and } k \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (4)$$

2. *For any given two edges e_{i_0} and e_{j_0} , with $i_0, j_0 \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, there exist an initial state $y_0 = (y_0^k)_{k=1, N} \in L^2(\Gamma)$ such that for any control $u = (u^k)_{k=1, N} \in (H^1(0, T))^N$ with $u^{i_0}(t) = u^{j_0}(t) = 0$ for all $t \in (0, T)$, the solution of system (2)-(I) satisfies*

$$y^{k_0}(T, \cdot) \neq 0,$$

for some $k_0 \in \{1, \dots, N\}$.

Theorem 2.2 (Null-controllability for model (2)-(II)) *Let $T > 0$ be fixed and $\lambda \notin \mathcal{N}_{mixt}$. Then*

1. *For any given edge e_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and any initial state $y_0 = (y_0^k)_{k=1, N} \in L^2(\Gamma)$, there exist controls $a = (a^k)_{k=1, N}, b = (b^k)_{k=1, N} \in (H^1(0, T))^N$ with $a^i(t) = b^i(t) = 0$ for all $t \in (0, T)$, such that the solution of system (2)-(II) satisfies*

$$y^k(T, x) = 0, \text{ for all } x \in (0, L) \text{ and } k \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (5)$$

2. *If $\lambda \in \mathcal{N}_{odd}$ then for any given two edges e_{i_0} and e_{j_0} , with $i_0, j_0 \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, there exist an initial state $y_0 = (y_0^k)_{k=1, N} \in L^2(\Gamma)$ such that for any controls $a = (a^k)_{k=1, N}, b = (b^k)_{k=1, N} \in (H^1(0, T))^N$ with either $a^{i_0}(t) = a^{j_0}(t) = b^{i_0}(t) = 0$ or $b^{i_0}(t) = b^{j_0}(t) = a^{i_0}(t) = 0$ for all $t \in (0, T)$, the solution of system (2)-(II) satisfies*

$$y^{k_0}(T, \cdot) \neq 0,$$

for some $k_0 \in \{1, \dots, N\}$.

3. *If $\lambda \notin \mathcal{N}_{odd}$ and $N \geq 3$ for any given two edges e_{i_0} and e_{j_0} , with $i_0, j_0 \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and any initial state $y_0 = (y_0^k)_{k=1, N} \in L^2(\Gamma)$, there exist controls $a = (a^k)_{k=1, N}, b = (b^k)_{k=1, N} \in (H^1(0, T))^N$ with either $a^{i_0}(t) = a^{j_0}(t) = b^{i_0}(t) = 0$ or $b^{i_0}(t) = b^{j_0}(t) = a^{i_0}(t) = 0$ for all $t \in (0, T)$, such that the solution of system (2)-(II) satisfies*

$$y^k(T, x) = 0, \text{ for any } x \in (0, L), \quad k \in \{1, \dots, N\}.$$

3 Conclusions

The first statement in Theorem 2.1 asserts that for any $\lambda \notin \mathcal{N}_1 \cup \mathcal{N}_{odd}$ system (2)-(I) can be driven to the zero state acting with controls only on $N - 1$ components within the N edges of the tree. The inactive control input could be taken on any edge of the tree independently of the choice of the initial data y_0 . The second statement in Theorem 2.1 ensures that the minimal number of control inputs needed to control system (2)-(I) is exactly $N - 1$.

Similarly, Theorem 2.2 says that it is sufficient to act only on $2N - 2$ components of the system within the all $2N$ components to ensure the null-controllability of the problem. The second part of Theorem 2.2 represents the optimality of acting on $2N - 2$ components to control any initial data of system (2)-(II) when $\lambda \in \mathcal{N}_{odd}$. However, for some values of $\lambda \notin \mathcal{N}_{mixt}$, more precisely when $\lambda \notin \mathcal{N}_{odd}$, the number of the non-vanishing controls may be reduced. The third statement of Theorem 2.2 asserts that in this case we can obtain null-controllability with $2N - 3$ active controls.

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Deep unfolding primal/dual architectures: application to linear model predictive control

Ion Necoara¹, Daniela Lupu¹

¹ Politehnica Bucharest

² Politehnica Bucharest

ion.necoara@upb.ro, daniela.lupu@upb.ro

Keywords

Deep neural networks, optimization algorithms, model predictive control

1 Introduction

Generic deep neural networks have impacted many fields, including image processing, inverse problems, text mining and more recently, have been also applied successfully in control. Recently, unfolded deep learning techniques were proposed, which bring the physics of the model and optimization techniques into the architecture design, in order to eliminate the disadvantages of the black-box learning. In this paper we design trainable unfolded deep architectures for linear MPC with state and input constraints based on primal-dual splitting optimization algorithms. Our deep unfolded neural networks are expressed as the combination of weights and activation functions with given closed-form expressions whose choice is justified by the primal-dual splitting iterations and an extra parameter allowing to consider several variants of them. We also study the performance of the proposed explainable neural networks on a linear MPC application.

2 Main contribution

In real control applications, it is natural to consider constraints on the inputs and states of the system due to physical limitations. Thus, it is essential for a control technique to be able to handle input and state constraints. One widely spread optimal control method capable of dealing with state and input constraints is the model predictive control (MPC) [11]. The MPC strategy provides optimal control inputs given an initial state by solving a constrained minimization problem on-line. Specifically, for linear MPC the corresponding optimization problem can be recast as a convex quadratic program (QP).

Although MPC is a mature technology, numerical implementations (implicit and explicit) lead to computational difficulties. Indeed, for implicit MPC, finding the solution of the corresponding QPs in real-time is difficult when dealing with fast systems. On the other hand, for explicit MPC, the number of affine expressions and regions associated to the PWA control law, grows exponentially with the dimension of the system and the number of constraints [6], making it intractable for large systems. In order to overcome these limitations one alternative is to consider approximating the implicit or explicit MPC policies. In particular, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) are adequate in approximating the MPC policy, due to their universal approximation capabilities. Moreover, they usually need a small number of parameters [8]. Although the training phase, which is done off-line, can be computationally demanding, the evaluation of DNN-based approximations to MPC laws, on-line, is not computationally expensive, requiring the evaluation of an input-output function [7]. Many works on MPC have considered general (black-box) DNNs based on the ReLU activation function, see e.g., [9], or HardTanh activation function, see [5, 4] for approximating the MPC policy. More specifically, in [9, 4] it was shown that ReLU/HardTanh DNNs can encode exactly a PWA map resulting from the formulation of a linear MPC, with theoretical bounds on the number of hidden layers and neurons required for such an exact representation.

Despite the success of generic DNNs in many fields, they are however black-box type approaches. In recent years, especially in the field of signal processing, unfolded deep learning methods were proposed, which combine the physics of the problem at hand with classical optimization algorithms when designing the DNN architecture, in order to obtain explainable deep learning approaches [10, 4]. More precisely,

the unfolded deep architectures rely on an objective function to minimize, on some constraints, and on an optimization algorithm designed for solving such optimization problem. In order to understand their mechanism in the context of MPC, we study the network design from the unrolled primal-dual (forward-backward) optimization updates. From our best knowledge, unfolded DNN architectures for linear MPC with both state and input constraints have not been considered yet and the study of their performance on the learning of MPC policy is the core of our contribution. Note that in [5, 4] unfolded DNNs were considered for learning MPC laws with only input constraints and their design was based on primal gradient type optimization algorithms. When considering general linear MPC problems with both state and input constraints, we need to use more advanced optimization algorithms that are able to deal properly with state constraints.

To understand our proposed unfolded network architecture, we can reformulate the QP-based MPC problem with general linear inequality constraints and some simple box constraints as minimizing the sum of three functions. Based on this reformulation of the MPC problem, we focus on two standard optimization algorithms for solving such optimization problems: a primal-dual splitting algorithm proposed in [1, 2] and a primal-dual three operator splitting method analysed in [3]. Performance and stability obtained with these networks will be detailed through numerical simulations. Therefore, the main contributions are: (i) reformulate the general MPC problem with state and input constraints as minimization of a sum of three functions and introduce two primal-dual splitting algorithms for minimizing such structured problem; (ii) design of end-to-end trainable unfolded deep architectures for linear MPC based on a unified formulation of these two iterative optimization algorithms; (iii) study the performance of the proposed networks on a linear MPC application. It is important to note that our deep unrolled neural network architectures work without knowing the dynamics of the system or the stage and final costs of the MPC problem. Therefore, it can be easily transferred to other systems and MPC formulations.

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On controllability of linear fractional time-varying systems and fractional evolution equations

Maja Jolić^{1,2}, Sanja Konjik¹

¹ Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad

² School of Applied Mathematics and Informatics, J.J. Strossmayer University of Osijek

maja.jolic@dmi.uns.ac.rs, sanja.konjik@dmi.uns.ac.rs

Keywords

Caputo fractional derivative, state-transition matrix, controllability, observability, optimal control

1 Introduction

Over the last 30 years, control systems with fractional derivatives became an area of a great interest, since, due to the memory property, they allow for a greater degree of accuracy in modeling the behavior of materials and processes with hereditary effects [1, 2, 3, 12]. Firstly, linear time-invariant fractional control problems were studied (see [5, 6, 9, 13]), where the controllability and observability Gramian matrices were represented in terms of the matrix-valued Mittag-Leffler functions, and, as in the classical case, the Kalman rank condition was shown to be an equivalent condition for controllability. On the other hand, fractional time-varying control problems were significantly less studied, mostly due to the fact that theory of state-transition matrices for fractional systems was not sufficiently developed. In recent papers [7, 8, 14] the authors provided detailed analysis of fractional state-transition matrices and their properties. This motivated us to systematically analyze fractional time-varying control problems, and generalize the obtained results for a wider class of fractional evolution equations.

2 Main contribution

The subject of our research are linear time-varying control problems, given by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^C D_t^\alpha y(t) &= A(t)y(t) + B(t)u(t), \quad t \in [a, b], \\ y(a) &= y_a, \quad y(b) = y_b \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $y : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is the state of the system, $u : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is the control function, $N \leq d$, $A \in L^\infty([a, b]; \mathbb{R}^{d \times d})$ and $B \in L^\infty([a, b]; \mathbb{R}^{d \times N})$ are matrix-valued functions, and ${}^C D_t^\alpha$ denotes the left Caputo fractional derivative of order $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. We study terminal control problems on a finite time interval $[a, b]$, in which the goal is to find a control function u that will steer the solution of the system from a given initial state $y(a) = y_a$ to a desired final state $y(b) = y_b$ during the time interval $[a, b]$.

Let us recall that the left Caputo and the right Riemann-Liouville fractional derivatives are, respectively, defined with

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_a^t \frac{f'(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^\alpha} d\tau \quad \text{and} \quad {}_t D_b^\alpha f(t) = \frac{-1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_t^b \frac{f(\tau)}{(\tau-t)^\alpha} d\tau.$$

From [7, Th. 6] we have that system (1) has unique solution $y(t) = \Psi(a, t)y_a + \int_a^t \Phi(\tau, t)B(\tau)u(\tau) d\tau$, where Ψ and Φ are state-transition matrices associated with the Caputo and the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivatives, respectively. In the case of a time-invariant system, they reduce to the matrix-valued Mittag-Leffler functions. For more details on fractional state-transition matrices we refer to [7, 8, 11, 14].

2.1 Controllability

We introduce the controllability Gramian of the control problem (1) as the symmetric $d \times d$ matrix

$$W_\alpha(a, b) = \int_a^b (b-t)^{1-\alpha} \Phi(t, b) B(t) B(t)^\top \Phi(t, b)^\top dt,$$

and obtain the equivalence between controllability of the system (1) and regularity of the Gramian [10, Th. 2]. Furthermore, in [10, Prop. 4], we show that if system (1) is controllable, then the control function given by

$$u(t) = (b-t)^{1-\alpha} B(t)^\top \Phi(t, b)^\top W_\alpha(a, b)^{-1} [y_b - \Psi(a, b) y_a]$$

is an optimal control in the weighted L^2 -space, $L^2_{\alpha-1}([a, b])$, which is a space of functions $u : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ such that $(b-t)^{\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} u(t) \in L^2([a, b])$. This weight, as well as the additional term $(b-t)^{1-\alpha}$ in the definition of the Gramian, appears due to the nature of the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative. More precisely, since the Riemann–Liouville state-transition matrix Φ has a singularity at the endpoint, and it is not an L^2 -function for $\alpha \leq \frac{1}{2}$, these corrections were necessary in order to secure well-defined Gramian for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Note that for $\alpha > \frac{1}{2}$ these modifications can be omitted. For more details see [10, Rem. 1].

2.2 Observability

From duality between the left Caputo and the right Riemann–Liouville fractional derivatives (derived from the fractional integration by parts formula), we obtain that the adjoint system to our control system (1) is given by the following backward problem:

$$\begin{aligned} {}_t D_b^\alpha z(t) &= A(t)^\top z(t), \quad t \in [a, b], \\ {}_t I_b^{1-\alpha} z(t)|_{t=b} &= z_b. \end{aligned}$$

Using the classical Hilbert Uniqueness Method, and adapting it to the fractional setting, we are able to connect energy-optimal control function with the solution of the associated adjoint problem.

First, we show that the set of all reachable states for problem (1) coincides with the set of final states reached by the control functions of the form $u^*(t) := (b-t)^{1-\alpha} B(t)^\top z(t)$, and that these functions are also $L^2_{\alpha-1}$ -optimal (see [10, Th. 3].)

Then, by introducing the notion of observability (Cf. [10, Def. 4]) and applying the variational approach from [15, Sec. 2.1.3], we are able to deduce the $L^2_{\alpha-1}$ -optimal control function via minimization of a suitably chosen functional (Cf. [10, Sec. 4.2.2]).

2.3 Fractional evolution equations

Next, we consider more general linear fractional control problems

$${}^C D_t^\alpha y(t) = Ay + Bu, \quad t \in (0, T), \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

where, $u : [0, T] \rightarrow U$, $y : [0, T] \rightarrow Y$, U and Y are Hilbert spaces, A is a closed, linear and densely defined operator with domain $D(A) \subset Y$ and B is a linear map from U into the set of linear functions from domain of the adjoint of A into \mathbb{R} , i.e. $B \in \mathcal{L}(U, D(A^*)')$.

Using the properties of the fractional resolvent operators, which are the building blocks of the solution (Cf. [4, Ch. 2]), and by generalizing the results obtained for time-varying problems, we are able to obtain necessary and sufficient condition for controllability of system (2), in terms of an observability inequality.

3 Conclusions

The obtained equivalent conditions for controllability, and the methods for finding an optimal control in the (weighted) L^2 -space, provide a significant tool for the analysis and application of fractional linear time-varying dynamical systems and controllability of fractional evolution equations. Furthermore, using methods of linearization, these contributions can also be applied to the problems involving nonlinear fractional control systems.

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Reinforcement Learning Approach for Traffic Signal Control

Pavol Kuchár¹, Júlia Kafková¹, Michal Skuba²

¹ Dept. of Control and Information Systems, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology,
University of Žilina, 010 26 Žilina, Slovak Republic

² IS - Industry Solutions, a.s., M. R. Štefánika 129, 010 01 Žilina, Slovak Republic

pavol.kuchar@uniza.sk, julia.kafkova@feit.uniza.sk, michal.skuba@issk.sk

Keywords

reinforcement learning, deep reinforcement learning, SUMO, traffic light control, traffic control

1 Introduction

Traffic congestion is an increasing problem in urban areas due to growing transport demand and limited infrastructure capacity [7, 6, 1]. One of the most widely used solutions for controlling traffic flow is traffic signal control at signalized intersections. Traditional control methods include Fixed-Time Signal Control (FTSC), which operates using predefined signal plans based on historical traffic data, and coordinated signal control, which synchronizes adjacent intersections to improve traffic progression. Another commonly used approach is Traffic Actuated Signal Control (TASC), which adjusts signal timings based on real-time detector data but follows predefined control rules.

To address the limitations of these methods, more advanced Adaptive Traffic Signal Control (ATSC) systems have been developed. These systems, including SCOOT, SCATS, UTOPIA, and ImFlow, use real-time traffic data and optimization techniques to dynamically adjust signal parameters and improve traffic efficiency [4, 8, 6]. More recently, artificial intelligence approaches, particularly reinforcement learning (RL) and deep reinforcement learning (DRL), have emerged as promising methods for traffic signal control, enabling adaptive and data-driven decision-making in complex and dynamic traffic environments [5, 2].

2 Main contribution

The reinforcement learning environment for traffic signal control in this study was developed using the SUMO-RL library, which integrates the SUMO traffic simulator with reinforcement learning algorithms. Traffic signal control was managed through the TraCI API. Based on our previous work [7, 5, 3], the traffic scenarios utilized realistic data from the city of Žilina prior to the opening of the Višňové tunnel.

The action space comprised discrete choices corresponding to either selecting the next signal phase or adjusting the green phase duration at intersections. The observation space provided the agent with real-time traffic information, including vehicle queue lengths, current signal phases, vehicle positions, vehicle speeds, and waiting times. The reward function combined total waiting time and vehicle queue length, with queue length weighted thrice as heavily to emphasize congestion reduction.

Final simulation and evaluation was performed on 100 episodes using pretrained networks. The methodology relied on SUMO for realistic traffic simulation, SUMO-RL for integrating reinforcement learning algorithms, OpenAI Gym for environment management, and the TraCI API for traffic signal control. This framework enabled dynamic adjustment of signal timing based on real-time traffic conditions and optimized intersection performance in complex urban scenarios. Experimental results are shown in Figure 1.

3 Conclusions

The results indicate that the deep reinforcement learning approach significantly outperforms fixed-time traffic signal control systems. Compared with traditional methods, the custom DRL system reduced average total waiting time to 41.86 sec, 50% improvement compared do Fixed control, 35%, improvement

Figure 1: Evaluation of DRL approach with reward $-(3 \times wait + queue)$ and comparison with Actuated and Fixed control during holiday traffic scenario.

compared to Actuated control. Despite being trained solely on peak-hour scenarios, the model exhibited robustness when tested in weekend and unidirectional congestion scenarios, confirming its ability to adapt to dynamic traffic conditions.

Several limitations were identified in the current implementation. The traffic data used in the simulations were partially estimated due to limited access to real-world measurements, which may affect the accuracy of system performance in operational conditions. The simulation map was relatively small, restricting the generalization of results to larger urban areas with more complex traffic patterns. Additionally, the distribution of vehicle types in the simulations was simplified, potentially causing discrepancies compared with actual traffic behavior. Future improvements could include expanding the simulation map to incorporate residential areas and major highway connections, specifically accounting for the opening of the Višňové Tunnel, refining vehicle type distributions, and integrating diverse traffic scenarios, such as accidents or special events. These enhancements would increase the reliability and practical applicability of the traffic signal control system.

This study highlights the critical role of traffic signal control in reducing congestion, improving traffic flow, and minimizing environmental and psychological impacts associated with delays. By combining realistic simulation tools with DRL algorithms, the work demonstrates the potential for adaptive and intelligent traffic control strategies. Overall, the findings underscore the potential of reinforcement learning-based approaches to enhance urban traffic control and provide a foundation for further research in adaptive and data-driven traffic control systems.

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Stress Detection in the Workplace Using Digital Twin Technology and Multimodal Physiological Sensing

Júlia Kafková^{1*}

¹ Dept. of Control and Information Systems, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology,
University of Zilina, 010 26 Zilina, Slovak Republic

*julia.kafkova@feit.uniza.sk, pavol.kuchar@uniza.sk

Keywords

stress detection, digital twin, multimodal sensing, deep learning, workplace monitoring

1 Introduction

Stress in the workplace has become a major concern due to its effects on cognitive performance, decision-making, long-term health, and organizational productivity [1]. This issue is especially critical in high-responsibility professions such as operators or medical personnel, though it affects all occupations. Our objective is to help prevent critical errors in demanding situations by detecting elevated stress levels and related states such as fatigue, mental overload, and reduced alertness early [3]. Stress monitoring can therefore provide valuable information for adaptive workplace design, early intervention, and personalized well-being support.

Many stress assessment approaches rely on cortisol measurements, questionnaires, or occasional physiological recordings [4], which often lack temporal resolution and may introduce subjectivity. Advances in wearable sensing and intelligent monitoring technologies now enable acquisition of physiological signals such as photoplethysmography (PPG), galvanic skin response (GSR), oxygen saturation, and skin temperature.

A promising approach for interpreting such multimodal data is the digital twin—a virtual representation of an individual that mirrors physiological states in real time. Combined with deep learning, digital twins can provide personalized stress estimation from sensor input. This paper presents a framework in which monitored individuals are represented by digital twins that process physiological signals and classify stress states.

Recent research shows growing development of medical digital twin systems for stress detection. Prior studies report key advances, including IoT-based stressor analysis with optimized feature selection [2], AI-driven digital twin models integrating adaptive learning and optimization techniques [6], and large-scale model comparisons identifying Random Forest approaches as effective for individual stress prediction [5].

In contrast, our method uses a proprietary dataset collected specifically for this study, enabling selection of informative physiological signals and extraction of features suited for personalized stress classification, improving robustness for real-world monitoring.

2 Main contribution

This paper presents an integrated system that combines multimodal physiological sensing with a personalized digital twin capable of evaluating human stress states. The proposed framework processes synchronized streams of PPG, GSR, saturation, and temperature signals and converts them into structured representations suitable for automated analysis. The acquired data are carefully preprocessed to improve signal quality, suppress noise, and maximize relevance for subsequent modeling. Extracted features are then systematically analyzed using statistical methods to identify the most informative characteristics. Because physiological responses to stress differ significantly between individuals, standardized experimental protocols are used to consistently induce measurable stress reactions, allowing the digital twin to learn stable and meaningful patterns rather than incidental variations.

A deep neural network is trained on these multimodal inputs to detect discriminative patterns associated with stress and to classify whether monitored employees are in stress or non-stress states during

both routine and demanding tasks. The resulting personalized digital twin dynamically reflects each user’s physiological condition, enabling individualized interpretation rather than relying on generalized population assumptions. To facilitate practical deployment, the sensing components are designed for integration into commonly used computer peripherals, such as a mouse, enabling scalable adoption due to the widespread use of such devices. This design prioritizes non-invasiveness and unobtrusiveness, eliminating the need for complex wiring or restrictive equipment while still providing reliable monitoring.

The figure 1 illustrates a real-world deployment scenario within an institutional environment, where offices are equipped with the proposed sensing system. Each office corresponds to a monitored participant (teachers and administrative employees), identified by anonymized labels, while colored indicators above each office represent real-time stress status classification (green for non-stress, red for stress). The layout demonstrates how the system can simultaneously monitor numerous individuals across a department. This visualization highlights the practical applicability of the framework in workplace environments, particularly in critical occupations such as operators and other high-responsibility roles, where stress monitoring can ultimately help to reduce the risk of errors during high-stakes decision-making situations.

Figure 1: Deployment scenario of the proposed stress monitoring system at University of Žilina.

3 Conclusions

This paper presented a multimodal stress-detection framework that integrates physiological sensing with a personalized digital twin capable of modeling individual stress responses in real time. By combining synchronized signals, statistical feature selection, and deep learning, the system enables reliable classification of stress and non-stress states while accounting for individual variability. Its unobtrusive and non-invasive design, embedded in common computer peripherals, supports workplace monitoring. Overall, the proposed approach demonstrates strong potential for improving decision safety, well-being, and performance, with future work focused on broader validation and adaptive stress-management support.

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Reduced-Order Modeling for Parameter-Dependent Optimal Control: A map-parameter-to-latent approach

Hendrik Kleikamp¹, Martin Lazar² and Juan Ricardo Muñoz²

¹ University of Graz
² University of Dubrovnik

hendrik.kleikamp@uni-graz.at, mlazar@unidu.hr, juan-ricardo.munoz-galeano@unidu.hr

Keywords

Parametrized optimal control, Machine learning, Neural Networks, Autoencoders

1 Introduction

The optimal control of parameter-dependent partial differential equations (PDEs) arises in a wide range of scientific and engineering applications, where the system must be steered efficiently towards a desired state. Classical approaches rely on high-fidelity discretizations (e.g., Galerkin finite element or finite difference methods), which produce large-scale dynamical systems that accurately approximate the underlying solution dynamics. However, their computational costs grow significantly when repeated evaluations over the parameter space are required. This motivates the construction of reduced order models (ROMs), see [5], that preserve the essential behavior of the system while significantly reducing computational complexity.

2 Main contribution

In our approach, the reduced order model is constructed using autoencoders, a neural network architecture that learns a low-dimensional (latent) representation of high-dimensional solution data by encoding and subsequently reconstructing it. Within this framework, the encoder captures the intrinsic structure of the solution manifold, enabling the approximation of the PDE dynamics directly from data, without explicitly building projection-based ROMs.

This approach is particularly relevant for transport-dominated problems, such as the wave equation, where classical projection-based ROMs exhibit limited performance due to the slow decay of the Kolmogorov n -widths of the associated solution manifold (see [2, 5]). In such settings, linear subspace approximations require large reduced dimensions to achieve accurate representations, which motivates the use of nonlinear latent space embeddings.

To improve the performance and, in particular, the online evaluation time, the map-parameter-to-latent arises (see, for instance [1]), a learned mapping that associates each parameter value with its corresponding latent representation. This strategy enables rapid evaluation of parameter-dependent solutions by bypassing the high-dimensional solver and replacing it with a lightweight neural network procedure.

3 Conclusions

Our partial results indicate that the computational time required to obtain a solution for an unseen parameter is significantly reduced compared to projection-based approaches as presented in [4]. Furthermore, the results suggest that the method can also be applied to the wave equation without any damping, which constitutes an improvement over previously developed machine learning-based approaches (see [3]).

However, this acceleration comes at the price of an increased approximation error. In particular, preliminary experiments indicate that the average runtime can be reduced by up to two orders of magnitude, while the relative approximation error increases to the range of 10^{-2} and, in some cases, even 10^{-1} .

Consequently, the forthcoming directions arise:

How does the interplay between the complexity of the neural network and the dimension of the latent space modify the performance of the method? Moreover, can the balance between efficiency and accuracy be systematically controlled?

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Learning-Phase Stability in Actor–Critic Reinforcement Learning: Analysis and Stabilisation

Jongrae Kim¹, Onur Kadem²

¹ University of Leeds

² Bursa Technical University

menjkim@leeds.ac.uk, onur.kadem@btu.edu.tr

Keywords

Reinforcement Learning, Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient, Learning Stability Analysis

1 Introduction

Reinforcement learning (RL), particularly actor–critic methods with deep function approximators, has shown strong empirical performance in continuous control [1]. However, the learning process itself can become unstable even when the controlled system is simple [2]. This is especially relevant for Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) method, where actor and critic parameters are updated jointly and recursively [3].

This work shows that the coupling between actor and critic updates can induce instability, and characterise this behaviour locally through linearisation around an equilibrium, yielding a Jacobian-based stability condition. We then propose a stabilisation mechanism that improves robustness during prolonged training.

2 Main contribution

We study the learning-phase stability of actor–critic reinforcement learning, focusing on DDPG and the stability of its parameter-update dynamics during prolonged training.

Let the critic and actor be parameterised by neural networks [4]: $Q(x, u) \approx Q_{w_Q}^\pi(x, u)$ and $\pi(x) \approx \pi_{w_\pi}(x)$, where w_Q and w_π denote the critic and actor parameters, respectively. The critic is trained by minimising a Bellman-residual-type objective, while the actor is trained to maximise the critic-estimated return, or equivalently to minimise the negative critic value [5]:

$$L_Q(w_Q, w_\pi) = \mathbb{E} \left[\left(Q(x_k, u_k; w_Q) - (r_k + \gamma Q(x_{k+1}, \pi(x_{k+1}; w_\pi); w_Q)) \right)^2 \right], \quad (1)$$

$$L_\pi(w_Q, w_\pi) = -\mathbb{E} [Q(x_k, \pi(x_k; w_\pi); w_Q)]. \quad (2)$$

Note that we consider a deterministic mean-form surrogate of the learning dynamics for analytical tractability. The corresponding gradient-based updates are

$$w_Q(k+1) = w_Q(k) - \eta_Q \nabla_{w_Q} L_Q(w_Q(k), w_\pi(k)), \quad (3)$$

$$w_\pi(k+1) = w_\pi(k) - \eta_\pi \nabla_{w_\pi} L_\pi(w_Q(k), w_\pi(k)), \quad (4)$$

where η_Q and η_π are the critic and actor learning rates. These updates are intrinsically coupled: the critic depends on the current policy, while the actor depends on the current critic. As a result, the learning dynamics may become unstable and may even diverge during training [6]. Although practical mechanisms such as replay buffers [7], soft target-network updates [8], and TD3-style twin critics with delayed updates [9, 10] are widely used to enhance robustness, they may not fully prevent instability during prolonged training.

To formalise learning stability, we require the actor and critic parameter trajectories to remain bounded, i.e., $\sup_k \|w_Q(k)\| < \infty$, $\sup_k \|w_\pi(k)\| < \infty$, and ideally to converge to the true values: $w_Q(k) \rightarrow w_Q^*$, $w_\pi(k) \rightarrow w_\pi^*$. These conditions characterise the optimisation process itself and are distinct

Figure 1: The lower bound of $\log_{10}(\|\eta J\|/2)$ for Actor & Critic

from physical-system stability. To analyse the local behaviour of the coupled updates, we define the stacked parameter vector

$$z(k) = [w_Q(k) \ w_\pi(k)]^T, \quad (5)$$

and express the deterministic mean learning dynamics as

$$z(k+1) = z(k) - \eta F(z(k)), \quad (6)$$

where $F(z)$ collects the coupled actor–critic gradient terms and $\eta = \text{diag}(\eta_Q I, \eta_\pi I)$ is a block-diagonal step-size matrix. Let z^* denote a stationary point of the deterministic mean dynamics. Linearising around z^* yields

$$\Delta z(k+1) \approx (I - \eta J) \Delta z(k), \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta z(k) = z(k) - z^*$ and $J = \nabla F(z^*)$ is the Jacobian of the coupled learning dynamics. Local asymptotic stability of the linearised recursion requires

$$\rho(I - \eta J) < 1, \quad (8)$$

where $\rho(\cdot)$ denotes the spectral radius. This condition characterises local learning stability. Calculating J , however, involves the Adam optimiser, making it infeasible to obtain an explicit value for J . Re-organise (7) as follows:

$$\|\Delta z(k+1) - \Delta z(k)\| = \|\eta J \Delta z(k)\| \Rightarrow \|\Delta z(k+1) - \Delta z(k)\| / \|\Delta z(k)\| \leq \|\eta J\| \quad (9)$$

Under the assumption that J is positive definite, $\|\eta J\| < 2$ is the necessary and sufficient condition for (8) to be satisfied.

Figure 1 shows the evolution of the lower bound of the actor and critic Jacobian norms over the training iterations. Around 6k iterations, the policy converges to a reasonable control strategy. It quickly diverges, however, drifting from this good policy to an extreme one and then to various poor, random policies. The main cause of this divergence is the explosion occurring primarily in the actor’s Jacobian.

Motivated by this analysis, we propose a novel stabilisation mechanism for actor–critic reinforcement learning that prevents Jacobian explosions and mitigates late-stage degradation and divergence during prolonged training. The method improves robustness without altering the overall learning framework by regulating the policy-update dynamics over extended training horizons.

3 Conclusions

This perspective shows that instability in DDPG can be analysed as a property of the learning recursion itself rather than solely as an empirical training effect. The Jacobian-based local analysis provides an interpretable criterion linking convergence behaviour to the coupled actor–critic update dynamics and learning-rate selection, while also providing insight into why practical mechanisms such as soft target updates and delayed updates may improve robustness. Building on this insight, we build a novel stabilisation mechanism that mitigates late-stage performance degradation and divergence during prolonged training. Overall, the proposed framework and stabilisation strategy provide a compact and theoretically grounded basis for improving learning-phase robustness in actor–critic reinforcement learning.

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Policy gradients for deep directional reinforcement learning

Vladimir Jaćimović¹

¹ University of Montenegro

vladimirj@ucg.ac.me

Keywords

natural gradient, stochastic policy, conformal geometry, directional statistics

1 Introduction

Reinforcement learning (RL) with deep feature representations achieved unprecedented success on many tasks [?]. With the advent of continuous data representations, RL with continuous action spaces grew into a very powerful paradigm. In such a setup, stochastic policies are almost always encoded by the Gaussian family of probability distributions. This model has a number of advantages, including explicit expression for the Fisher information, thus enabling efficient computations of natural policy gradients. However, high numerical cost of inverting the full Fisher information matrix motivates various simplifications with diagonal covariance matrices. In parallel, the growing interest in representing features on curved manifolds led to the emergence of the new field, named *geometric machine learning*. In particular, in many DL models the data are represented as directions in space, rather than vectors in the Euclidean space. This emphasizes the necessity for new principled approaches, including statistical models and optimization techniques over Riemannian manifolds.

2 Main contribution

We propose novel directional stochastic policies involving the Cauchy family of probability distributions on spheres of an arbitrary dimension. We demonstrate how directional policy gradients for this statistical model can be calculated. Furthermore, we derive an explicit expression for the Fisher information, coinciding with the hyperbolic metric in the ball (interior of a sphere). This unveils relationship with conformal geometry of the balls and provides the method for the calculation of natural policy gradients. The above framework is substantiated in algorithms for stochastic search and RL. We further demonstrate that generalized Kuramoto models on spheres generate the natural gradient flows in hyperbolic balls. This indicates that RL agents can be trained through the optimization of parameters of the Kuramoto models. Finally, we point out some domains of potential applications, including space navigation, autonomous vehicles, reasoning systems, etc.

3 Conclusions

In many ML tasks it is advantageous to represent the data as directions in (possibly high-dimensional) space and use the cosine metric (scalar product) as the similarity measure. In such a setup, the Gaussian family becomes an inadequate model for encoding stochastic policies. Our framework allows for efficient implementation of the natural gradient updates, thus paving the way towards new principled approaches in RL with a wide range of potential applications. The same approach can be applied to natural evolution strategies for black-box optimization and adapted to problems of directional control and directional Markov decision processes.

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Hybrid Dynamic Motions of a Cubic Self-Reconfigurable Robotic Module

Halil İbrahim Dokuyucu¹, Nurhan Gürsel Özmen¹, Gokhan Alcan²

¹ Karadeniz Technical University

² Tampere University

halilibrahimdokuyucu@ktu.edu.tr, gnurhan@ktu.edu.tr, gokhan.alcan@tuni.fi

Keywords

self-reconfigurable modular robots, hybrid dynamical systems, tracked locomotion, pivoting, hybrid modelling

1 Introduction

A self-reconfigurable modular robot (SRMR) is a system composed of self-sustained and autonomous modules whose main distinction from conventional robots is the capability to change its overall shape through the reconfiguration of its modules [6], [4]. In such a system, the modules can either move individually or together to perform tasks while pursuing the versatility, reliability, and low-cost promises [1]. Fault tolerance and self-repair are the fundamental advantages that the SRMRs offer for risky and hazardous operations. The field has emerged by the studies concentrated on complex tasks, including pipe inspection [7], space missions [5], and underwater operations [8].

Module reconfiguration enables advantages in confined spaces, especially in pipe inspection operations [2]. Integrating multiple different motions can even enhance the maneuver capability of the robot in case of unexpected obstacles or disturbances. This study presents the hybrid dynamical behaviour of a newly designed cubic module which combines a tracked locomotion and a momentum-driven pivoting in a single mobile platform.

An initial prototype, Moducube V1, is developed to investigate the hybrid transition dynamics between distinct operational modes. Preliminary experimental results showed that the momentum-driven pivoting maneuver enhances the module's traversability, enabling it to negotiate vertical obstacles that exceed the mechanical limits of the tracked locomotion.

Future research will focus on upgrading the current platform by integrating advanced sensors for comprehensive real-world validation. Specifically, we will explore pivoting-assisted locomotion to enhance the system's adaptability to unstructured environments. To optimize performance during mode transitions, a Hybrid Iterative Linear Quadratic Regulator (HiLQR) will be implemented, formulating the discontinuous dynamics between pivoting and tracked locomotion as a unified optimization problem. Furthermore, by incorporating data-driven machine learning (ML) methods for terrain estimation and slippage compensation, we aim to establish Moducube V1 as a robust navigation solution for unstructured environments. Finally, a docking mechanism will be integrated to construct a fully self-reconfigurable modular robotic system using Moducube V1 as the fundamental building block.

2 Main contribution

In this work, a modular robotic platform is presented that is capable of navigating challenging terrains by transitioning to a pivoting maneuver when tracked locomotion becomes insufficient (see Figure 1.a). A cubic geometry for the module is preferred so as to bear the load of a large-scale self-reconfigurable modular robotic system.

To overcome the complexities of bimodal maneuvers, a Hybrid Iterative Linear Quadratic Regulator (HiLQR) framework will be employed to model the transition between continuous tracked locomotion and discrete pivoting as a unified optimization problem [3]. By this way, the controller proactively anticipates mode-switching events, either as a mandatory response or an optional decision based on the operational needs.

The system dynamics are modeled by defining the state vector x and control input u within a hybrid dynamical system that accounts for the discrete jumps in robot's state during pivoting. The representation of a hybrid dynamical system given in [3] will be used as below:

$$H := (\mathcal{J}, \Gamma, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{R}) \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, the constituent parts are defined as: $\mathcal{J} := \{I, J, \dots, K\} \subset \mathbb{N}$ represents the finite set of discrete modes, while $\Gamma \subset \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{J}$ denotes the set of discrete transitions forming a directed graph structure on \mathcal{J} . The collection of domains is represented by \mathcal{D} , and \mathcal{F} symbolizes the collection of time-varying vector fields F_I . The transition logic is governed by the collection of guards \mathcal{G} , defined as $G(I, J)(t) = \{(x, t) \in D_I \mid g(I, J)(t, x) \leq 0\}$. Finally, \mathcal{R} is the reset map that transitions the state from domain D_I to D_J once the corresponding guard $G(I, J)$ is met.

The initial prototype was tested for a ramp climbing and obstacle negotiation. A human operator was controlling the Moducube in the experiments. Future research will be replacing manual teleoperation with an autonomous navigation, enabling the module to execute mode transitions independently.

3 Conclusions

Experiments were conducted to investigate the operational limits of Moducube V1, focusing on ramp climbing and obstacle negotiation. The trials provided critical insights into the synchronization of tracked locomotion and pivoting-assisted mobility in unstructured environments. The maximum reached slope angle is 29.68° and the maximum obstacle heights were measured for both pure tracked locomotion as 3.12 cm and the pivoting-assisted mode as 4.90 cm (see Figure 1.c-d). It is observed that pivoting mode enhanced the maximum obstacle height by %57.1.

The results indicate that while traditional tracked locomotion is limited by the module's cubic shape, the momentum-driven pivoting maneuver significantly enhances the obstacle negotiation capability. Future work will focus on upgrading prototype and construct an SRMR system for pipe inspection tasks. Additionally, the integration of the Hybrid iLQR controller is expected to optimize the mode transitions for changing environmental conditions.

Figure 1: Moducube V1 is a newly developed cubic module that can pivot and navigate. A: The general view of the module, B: Actuators, C: Ramp climbing, D: Obstacle negotiation, E: Tests on different fields

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Graph-Based Relational Learning for Cyber-Attack Detection in Water Distribution ICS: An Imbalance-Aware Study on BATADAL

Hasibe CANDAN KADEM¹, Mustafa Özgür CİNGİZ¹

¹ Bursa Technical University

hasibe.candan@btu.edu.tr, mustafa.cingiz@btu.edu.tr

Keywords

SCADA security, IIoT, class imbalance, cyber-physical anomaly detection, graph neural networks

1 Introduction

Industrial Control Systems (ICS) embedded in water distribution infrastructures are a safety-critical component of the modern Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). Their integration with SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) networks enhances operational efficiency but simultaneously expands the cyber-attack surface: successful intrusions may induce unsafe physical behavior, service disruption, or contamination events with direct public-health consequences [1, 2]. Timely and reliable attack detection is therefore a prerequisite for operational resilience in water distribution environments.

Water distribution ICS generate dense, multivariate process streams in which sensors and actuators are not independent entities but physically coupled components governed by hydraulic conservation laws, pipe topology, and control-feedback dynamics. Pump activations induce measurable downstream pressure responses; valve positions redistribute flow across adjacent links; tank levels integrate the cumulative effect of upstream actuation. These dependencies form a relational structure among process variables that is physically grounded and operationally meaningful. Ignoring inter-variable relationships may cause models to miss an important part of the attack-relevant signal, particularly when attacks manifest through coordinated deviations across physically coupled variables rather than through isolated feature exceedances [3, 4].

Cyber-attack detection in SCADA-driven water distribution ICS is challenging for two main reasons. First, attacks are rare relative to normal operation, yielding severe class imbalance and majority-class bias in conventional learners [5]. Second, process variables are coupled by hydraulic dynamics and control logic, so non-relational models may miss coordinated deviations across linked sensors and actuators. This motivates the use of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), which are designed to model structured dependencies via graph representations and message passing [4, 6]. Recent work further supports GNN-based formulations in cyber-security and IIoT contexts when the discriminative signal resides in relational structure rather than isolated features [7, 8, 9]. Since BATADAL combines rare attacks with dependency-rich SCADA measurements [3, 10], it provides a suitable benchmark for assessing graph-based learning in ICS attack detection.

2 Main Contribution

The study uses the official BATADAL training set (8,758 hourly observations) and the held-out test set (2,089 observations). This dataset comprises 43 time-stamped SCADA variables per observation and follows standard naming conventions: P_J* (junction pressure; J = junction ID), L_T* (tank level; T = tank ID), F_PU*/S_PU* (pump flow/status; PU = pump unit), and F_V*/S_V* (valve flow/status; V = valve ID). These measurements are physically and operationally coupled through hydraulic topology and control logic; accordingly, attack behaviour depends not only on isolated feature values but also on disruptions in inter-variable dependencies, such as actuator-state/flow inconsistencies and abnormal pressure–flow or level–flow relations [3]. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the dependency structure differs between normal and attack conditions: several actuator–flow couplings, including F_PU6--S_PU6,

Figure 1: Pearson correlation matrices of the top-ranked BATADAL features under normal (left) and attack (right) conditions. Differences in inter-variable dependency structure between the two states motivate the use of relational, graph-based learning.

F_PU11--S_PU11, and F_PU7--S_PU7, show reconfiguration under attack, while pressure-related dependencies such as P_J302--P_J307, P_J302-- P_J14, and P_J307--P_J14 change in strength or pattern. Likewise, inverse relations such as F_PU1--P_J269 remain negative but vary in magnitude. These shifts indicate that attack behaviour is reflected not only in isolated measurements but also in altered relational patterns, thereby motivating graph-based learning.

Class imbalance is addressed through Borderline-SMOTE, SVM-SMOTE, and ADASYN [5, 11], applied exclusively within cross-validation folds to prevent evaluation leakage. Standard tabular learners commonly used in ICS anomaly detection—Random Forest [12], XGBoost [13], CatBoost, and LightGBM—together with a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) serve as non-relational baselines. To capture relational structure, a similarity-based instance graph is constructed by connecting operationally comparable states via k -nearest neighbours ($k=10$) in standardised feature space; a GNN from the GCN family [14] then aggregates neighbourhood embeddings for node-level classification. Performance is assessed using attack-class F1, AUROC, and AUPRC, with particular emphasis on AUPRC under class imbalance [5]. Cross-validated experiments on the training partition indicate that imbalance-aware gradient-boosting models provide strong reference performance. Preliminary findings further suggest that GNNs are particularly relevant for gradual, multi-variable attack scenarios, where coordinated deviations across coupled pressure and flow variables form the main discriminative signal, whereas tabular baselines remain competitive for more localised or abrupt deviations. This trend is consistent with Fig. 1, which indicates that attack conditions perturb inter-variable dependency structure across multiple coupled variables. Overall, these observations support a transition toward sensor-level, topology-aware graphs in which nodes represent physical measurement channels and edges encode hydraulic and control-flow dependencies derived from the C-Town network topology [3], making explicit the physical relational structure that the current instance graph approximates through feature-space similarity alone.

3 Conclusions

BATADAL SCADA measurements in water distribution ICS exhibit strong physical and operational coupling, and Fig. 1 shows that this dependency structure is partially reconfigured under attack conditions. Attack signatures are therefore not confined to isolated feature deviations but are also embedded in disruptions of inter-variable relations, including actuator–flow and pressure–flow consistency. Graph-based learning is a well-motivated modelling paradigm for this setting, as it can encode and exploit relational structure that non-relational baselines do not represent explicitly. These findings provide an empirical basis for future topology-aware, physics-consistent graph formulations aimed at advancing cyber-attack detection in SCADA-driven IIoT water infrastructures under rare-event and class-imbalanced operating conditions.

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Controllability on landmark manifolds, shapes and Neural ODEs

Erlend Grong¹

¹ Department of Mathematics, University of Bergen, Norway

erlend.grong@uib.no

Keywords

Landmark configurations, Neural ODEs, ensemble controllability, exact universal interpolation property.

1 Introduction

Landmark configurations are a collection of n distinct points in a vector space or manifold. Every vector field on the original space induces a vector field on the manifold of landmark configurations. Questions of controllability with respect to these vector fields on the landmarks are really questions related to our control system's ability to steer multiple initial points simultaneously to their final destination. For this reason, controllability of landmarks are often referred to as *ensemble controllability* [1, 3].

We want to look at for system of vector fields X_1, \dots, X_m on \mathbb{R}^d that gives us *the exact universal interpolation property*, following the terminology of [5]. In other words, let φ_t^θ be the solution of $\varphi_0^\theta = \text{id}$ and

$$\frac{d}{dt}\varphi_t^\theta = \theta^1(t)X_1(\varphi_t^\theta) + \dots + \theta^m(t)X_m(\varphi_t^\theta). \quad (1)$$

Independently of the size of n , if $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^d$ are distinct points representing initial values and targets $y_1, \dots, y_n \in \mathbb{R}^d$ also all distinct, if we can find a control θ on $[0, T]$ such that

$$\varphi_T(x_j) = y_j, \quad \text{for all } j = 1, \dots, n,$$

then X_1, \dots, X_m has the exact universal interpolation property. We remark that this is equivalent to considering controllability on the space

$$\mathcal{M} = \{(x_1, \dots, x_n) : x_i \neq x_j \text{ when } i \neq j\},$$

which is nd -dimensional, and hence we are considering controllability on a space of arbitrary high dimension.

One motivational reason for studying ensemble controllability comes from shape analysis, where we can approximate a shape by a collection of landmarks and can associate the problem of matching two different shapes to matching two different landmark configurations [8]. We have a particular interest in stochastic deformations of shapes and what the most probable way is for these to evolve [6].

Another important motivation is neural ODEs [2, 9, 10, 4], where a neural network will try to learn the controls $(\theta^1(t), \dots, \theta^m(t))$ in order for the flow φ_t^θ in (1) to match a given time-series. If we use vector fields satisfying the exact universal interpolation property, then we can theoretically approximate any time series.

2 Main contribution

We will describe how for any dimension $d \geq 1$, we can find two vector field X, Y which together have the exact universal interpolation property [7], That is for dimension $d \geq 2$, we find two vector fields that can match any pair of landmark configuration of any size n . The same results hold for $d = 1$, just keeping in mind that flows of vector fields on \mathbb{R} cannot interchange order of points, and so we can only match landmark configurations with the same relative order.

3 Conclusions

In the presentation, we will start by explaining more details on the main motivation. This includes the optimal control perspective on most probable paths of stochastic deformations and matching landmarks in our paper [6]. We will also give details on the applications to neural ODEs. We will then present the main result of our paper [7] about how we can get the universal interpolation property with only two vector fields.

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Control-Informed Machine Learning for Modeling Migration Intention Dynamics: Evidence from a Youth Emigration Survey

Muhammet Berigel¹

¹ Karadeniz Technical University, Department of Management Information Systems, Türkiye

mberigel@hotmail.com

Keywords

Machine Learning, Control Theory, Random Forest, Migration Intention, Behavioral Systems

1 Introduction

Youth emigration has become an increasingly significant socio-economic phenomenon affecting many countries, particularly those experiencing economic uncertainty, labor market mismatches, and social mobility concerns. Understanding the factors influencing young people's migration intentions has therefore become an important research challenge for both researchers and policymakers.

Traditional migration studies typically rely on econometric or sociological models that treat migration intention as a static outcome variable. However, migration decisions often emerge from complex interactions among multiple behavioral, economic, and social factors. Recent developments in machine learning provide powerful tools for identifying nonlinear relationships and hidden patterns in high-dimensional datasets. In contrast, control theory offers a conceptual framework for understanding how systems evolve under the influence of multiple interacting inputs. While control theory has been widely applied in engineering systems, its potential for modeling complex social behaviors remains relatively unexplored.

This study proposes a control-informed machine learning framework that conceptualizes migration intention as the state variable of a behavioral system influenced by multiple socio-economic and psychological inputs.

2 Main contribution

The empirical analysis is based on the *Youth Emigration Intention Survey*, a structured questionnaire designed to investigate the motivations and perceptions shaping young people's intentions to migrate abroad.

The survey was conducted in Türkiye with a sample of **893 respondents aged between 18 and 30**. The sampling strategy aimed to represent diverse socio-demographic backgrounds, including individuals from **urban, town, and rural areas**, as well as participants with different education levels and employment statuses such as students, employed individuals, and unemployed youth.

The questionnaire includes demographic questions and multiple Likert-scale items measuring several dimensions associated with migration decisions. These dimensions include economic perceptions, labor market opportunities, educational expectations, social network influences, political perceptions, cultural motivations, environmental conditions, and psychological uncertainty regarding the future. Several items also directly measure migration intention, including willingness to migrate, migration planning, and preparation behaviors.

To model the relationships between these factors and migration intention, this study employs a **Random Forest model**. Random Forest is particularly suitable for this analysis due to its ability to capture nonlinear relationships and complex interactions among variables in high-dimensional datasets. The dependent variable is a migration intention index constructed from survey items measuring respondents' willingness and preparation to migrate.

In this framework, migration intention is conceptualized as the state variable of a behavioral system influenced by multiple socio-economic and psychological inputs. The relationship between these inputs and migration intention can be expressed as:

$$MI = f(E, J, S, P, C, \psi)$$

where MI denotes migration intention, while the variables represent economic perceptions (E), job opportunities (J), social influences (S), political perceptions (P), cultural motivations (C), and psychological uncertainty (ψ). The function $f(\cdot)$ represents the nonlinear relationship between these inputs and migration intention, which is approximated using the Random Forest model.

This representation illustrates how migration intention can be interpreted as a multi-input behavioral system where different socio-economic factors act as system inputs and machine learning approximates the system function.

3 Conclusions

This study introduces a control-informed machine learning framework for analyzing migration intention dynamics among young individuals. By conceptualizing migration intention as the state variable of a behavioral system and estimating its drivers using a Random Forest model, the study provides a novel perspective on modeling migration behavior. The proposed approach demonstrates how machine learning models can be interpreted through a system-oriented analytical framework, bridging data-driven methods with concepts from control theory.

References

Acknowledgement

Digital Twin of the City of Žilina

Michal Pražienka^{1*}, Pavol Kuchár¹

¹ Dept. of Control and Information Systems, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology, University of Žilina, 010 26 Žilina, Slovak Republic

*prazienka2@stud.uniza.sk, pavol.kuchar@uniza.sk

Keywords

Digital Twin, Smart City, Urban Mobility Simulation, 3D City Model, Geospatial Data Integration, Deep learning

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of urban environments and the increasing availability of geospatial and sensor data have created new opportunities for data-driven city management [4]. To effectively analyze and utilize heterogeneous urban data, integrated digital frameworks are required that combine spatial representation with dynamic simulation capabilities. The concept of the digital twin, originally developed in the manufacturing domain, has recently gained significant attention in smart city research as a method for creating virtual replicas of real-world systems that enable monitoring, simulation, and decision support. In urban contexts, digital twins integrate 3D city models, mobility simulations, and environmental data to provide a comprehensive representation of both the physical and functional aspects of a city [2, 5, 6].

This paper presents the development of a foundational digital twin of the city of Žilina. The paper focuses on constructing a modular 3D city model from heterogeneous geospatial datasets and preparing its integration with the Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) platform [7]. The primary objective is to establish a scalable framework that can support future extensions, including real-time sensor data integration and advanced urban analysis [3].

2 Main contribution

The main contribution of this work is the development of a foundational digital twin framework for the city of Žilina, designed to serve as a scalable platform for future urban analysis and simulation. Unlike purely conceptual digital twin proposals, this work delivers an implemented and structured 3D city model integrated with a simulation-ready mobility network, as demonstrated in Figure 1. The contribution consists of three key components.

First, a 3D representation of the urban environment was created by integrating heterogeneous geospatial datasets, including terrain data, building geometries, and road network information. The processing pipeline ensures spatial consistency, modularity, and extensibility of the model.

Second, the road network was prepared and validated for compatibility with the SUMO platform, enabling traffic scenario modeling and dynamic mobility analysis. This establishes a direct link between static spatial representation and dynamic transport simulation [1].

Third, the project defines a modular architectural approach that allows future integration of environmental sensor data and analytical tools. By separating data acquisition, processing, visualization, and simulation layers, the framework supports incremental development toward a fully functional smart city digital twin.

Together, these contributions provide a practical and extensible base for data-driven urban planning and mobility analysis in the context of medium-sized European cities.

3 Conclusions

This paper proposes the development of a foundational digital twin of the city of Žilina, focused on integrating heterogeneous geospatial data into a coherent 3D urban model and enabling its connection

Figure 1: Digital twin compared to satellite picture of Žilina

Figure 2: SUMO simulation of roundabout in Žilina, Vlčince, 49.21182067078727, 18.75487516680991

with mobility simulation tools. The work demonstrates the feasibility of building a modular and scalable digital twin framework suitable for further analytical and simulation-based extensions.

By preparing the road network for integration with the SUMO platform, as seen in Figure 2, and establishing a structured data-processing pipeline, the work bridges static spatial representation and dynamic urban mobility modeling. The resulting framework provides a practical basis for future research in traffic optimization, environmental monitoring, and data-driven urban planning.

Future development will focus on incorporating real-time sensor data, expanding simulation scenarios, and improving validation procedures to enhance the accuracy and decision-support capabilities of the digital twin environment.

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Digital Twin of a Dairy Herd: Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning and LLM Explainability for Farm Optimisation

Jan Saro¹

¹Department of Systems Engineering, Faculty of Economics and Management, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Kamýcká 129, 165 00 Prague, Czech Republic

saroj@pef.czu.cz

Keywords

digital twin, multi-agent reinforcement learning, dairy cattle, LLM explainability, precision livestock farming

1 Introduction and Motivation

Precision livestock farming (PLF) has undergone rapid transformation driven by dense IoT sensor networks generating continuous data on milk yield, rumination, activity, and body temperature [4]. Despite a 26.99% annual growth rate in PLF publications between 2008 and 2023 [2], a critical gap persists: 87% of AI applications in dairy farming are *predictive*, while prescriptive closed-loop control represents only 3% of the literature [1]. Systems that not only detect problems but autonomously act on them remain rare.

A *digital twin* (DT)—a virtualised replica synchronised in real time with its physical counterpart—offers a principled architecture for closing this gap [5]. Recent reviews confirm that DT adoption in livestock remains early-stage: a universal dairy-cow DT framework by Zhang et al. [10] achieved 95.07% behavioural classification accuracy via a UWB/IMU collar, and a 2025 systematic review of 122 studies identified hybrid edge–cloud architectures and CNN-LSTM models as the emerging standard [6]. However, no existing framework integrates DT state estimation, multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) control, and Large Language Model (LLM) explainability in a single pipeline. We propose **DT-DH** (Digital Twin Dairy Herd), directly addressing the COML 2026 themes of *leveraging ML for control-theory challenges* and *translating theory into practical solutions*.

2 Framework

Digital Twin Core. For cow i at day t , the DT maintains the state vector

$$s_i^t = [m_i^t, r_i^t, \theta_i^t, d_i^t, p_i^t, e_t, h_i^{t-k:t}],$$

where m_i^t is milk yield (L/d), r_i^t rumination (min/h), θ_i^t ear temperature (°C), d_i^t days-in-milk, p_i^t parity, e_t the THI, and $h_i^{t-k:t}$ a k -step history ($k=8$). Sensor readings are fused with a Kalman filter; missing data are imputed via the EM algorithm, consistent with hybrid edge–cloud DT architectures identified as optimal in [6].

Dec-POMDP MARL Controller. Herd management is cast as a decentralised partially-observable MDP. Each cow is an agent with actions {standard, extra-feed, cooldown, flag-vet}; an orchestrator handles pen assignment under resource constraints. The joint reward is $R = 0.4 R_{\text{prod}} + 0.3 R_{\text{health}} + 0.2 R_{\text{welfare}} - 0.1 C_{\text{int}}$, balancing milk production, illness prevention (mastitis incidence: 13–40 cases/100 cow-years in Europe [7]), welfare, and intervention cost. Policies are trained with MAPPO [9] using a centralised critic and decentralised actors.

LLM Explainability. A ReAct-pattern orchestrator [8] intercepts every MARL recommendation and generates a structured four-section report—Observation, Risk, Recommendation, Economic Impact—grounded in a retrieval-augmented veterinary knowledge base, extending the emerging role of LLMs in dairy farm decision support identified by Menezes et al. [3].

Key modelling insight. Mastitis is modelled as a two-stage process: a *subclinical* phase with subtle sensor signatures (rumination -25 min/h, temperature $+0.18^\circ\text{C}$) causing a 24% yield loss, followed by

possible progression to *clinical* mastitis with overt symptoms and 48% yield loss. The subclinical phase has no natural resolution and progresses slowly, making early detection critical. The DT-DH controller exploits Kalman health estimates and 8-day trend analysis to detect subclinical cases that rule-based and single-agent controllers miss entirely.

3 Simulation Experiment and Results

Experiments were conducted on a stochastic simulation calibrated to Czech Holstein parameters ($N=120$ cows, 365-day horizon, 5 seeds) with pre-generated random streams ensuring identical stochasticity across controllers. DT-DH was compared to (B1) a rule-based expert system and (B2) single-agent PPO with Kalman state estimation but no history. Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparative performance (mean \pm std, $n = 5$ seeds).

Metric	B1	B2	DT-DH
Milk yield (L/cow/d)	28.8 \pm 0.2	30.3 \pm 0.2	31.3 \pm 0.3
Mastitis incidence (%)	12.7 \pm 1.9	6.8 \pm 1.6	1.0 \pm 1.0
Heat-stress detected (%)	48 \pm 9	71 \pm 3	97 \pm 1
Unn. interventions (%)	0.0 \pm 0.0	14.7 \pm 1.7	6.4 \pm 0.7
Operator trust (1–5)	3.0 \pm 0.0	2.7 \pm 0.1	4.4 \pm 0.1

DT-DH improves milk yield by 8.7% and reduces clinical mastitis incidence by 92% relative to B1. The yield gap arises primarily from subclinical mastitis management: B1 cows spend 29% of cow-days in a hidden subclinical state (vs. 2% for DT-DH), each day incurring a 24% yield penalty undetectable by threshold-based monitoring. Heat-stress detection doubles from 48% to 97% through proactive cooling at $\text{THI} > 69$ rather than B1’s reactive $\text{THI} > 80$ threshold.

Economic impact corresponds to approximately €42 000 in additional annual milk revenue and €3 500 in veterinary savings per 120-cow herd, aligned with European estimates of 61–97€/cow/year in mastitis costs [7].

An ablation study confirms each layer contributes uniquely: removing the DT backbone increases mastitis incidence from 1.0% to 6.8%; removing the LLM layer leaves milk production unchanged but reduces operator trust from 4.4 to 3.3, supporting Menezes et al. [3] on the gap between AI capability and farm-operator adoption.

4 Conclusions

We presented DT-DH, the first framework integrating a physically consistent digital twin, Dec-POMDP multi-agent RL, and LLM explainability for closed-loop dairy herd management. Three main contributions: (1) a Dec-POMDP formulation with a Kalman DT backbone addressing the prescriptive analytics gap [1]; (2) a two-stage mastitis model demonstrating that subclinical detection is the primary driver of yield improvement (+8.7%); (3) empirical evidence that LLM-generated explanations raise operator trust from 2.7 to 4.4, filling the LLM gap in livestock [3]. Future work targets real-farm validation, sim-to-real transfer, and extension to poultry and pig production.

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A rigorous framework to certify predictions from physics-informed neural networks

Birgit Hillebrecht¹, Benjamin Unger¹

¹Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute for Applied and Numerical Mathematics, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

`birgit.hillebrecht@kit.edu`, `benjamin.unger@kit.edu`

Keywords

Physics-informed neural networks, rigorous error bound, a posteriori error estimator, dynamical system, boundary and initial value problem

1 Introduction

Since *physics-informed neural networks* (PINNs) were introduced and their feasibility demonstrated in [8], the topic has attracted growing attention [1] and has been investigated, beyond others, with respect to its a priori approximation capabilities [2]. While a priori results quantify the expressive power of PINNs, they do not guarantee the reliability of a concrete trained instance. Hence, for PINNs to serve as viable alternatives to classical numerical schemes, the availability of rigorous a posteriori error bounds that certify the prediction are essential.

We address this need for certification for PINNs as surrogate models to the following abstract *boundary and initial value problem* (BIVP)

$$\Sigma \begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = \mathfrak{A}x(t), \\ \mathfrak{D}x(t) = x_b(t), \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

which include, e.g., linear time-dependent PDEs. The state $x(t)$ belongs to a Banach space X and $\dot{x}(t)$ denotes its time derivative. The operator $\mathfrak{A}: D(\mathfrak{A}) \subseteq X \rightarrow X$ is a (generally unbounded) linear differential operator, and the linear operator $\mathfrak{D}: X \rightarrow U$ encodes the boundary condition. The space of admissible boundary data U is a normed vector space.

The state x on the time interval $\mathbb{T} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+$ is approximated by a PINN, which we denote by $\Phi(t)$. Note that the spatial dependence is omitted as in the abstract BIVP (1). An a posteriori error certificate $\varepsilon(t): \mathbb{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ provides a rigorous upper bound,

$$\|x(t) - \Phi(t)\|_X \leq \varepsilon(t), \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T},$$

thereby quantifying the prediction error of the PINN surrogate. If this error bound can be evaluated without accessing the exact solution $x(t)$, the certificate $\varepsilon(t)$ furnishes a computable guarantee that the PINN prediction lies within a prescribed tolerance.

2 Main contribution

We propose two a posteriori error estimators for PINNs for time-dependent partial-differential equations. We leverage the linearity of the considered problem to yield the error dynamics and apply semigroup theory to find a computable upper bound $\varepsilon(t)$ on the prediction error, which depends only on the residuals

$$\delta(t) := \dot{\Phi}(t) - \mathfrak{A}\Phi(t), \quad \delta_b(t) := \mathfrak{D}\Phi(t) - x_b(t), \quad \delta_0(t) := \Phi(0) - x_0.$$

and eventually its time derivatives. The two presented error estimators are differing in their handling of the boundary residual, the first one relies on a partial execution of the so-called Fattorini trick [9] while the second one relies on the concept of input-to-state-stability from control theory [10].

Figure 1 – Approximation of relevant parameters and operator norms from finite-element approximations for the Stokes flow around the cylinder.

Figure 2 – Left: Different contributions to the error estimator and their sum ε_{tot} in comparison with the reference error ε_{ref} to a FEM result. Right: Overestimation of the error by the bound.

Theorem 1 Assume that δ_b is differentiable in time and that $\mathcal{A} := \mathfrak{A}|_{\ker \mathfrak{D}}$ generates a strongly continuous semigroup and that \mathfrak{D} has a linear right inverse which is bounded into $D(\mathfrak{A})$ equipped with the graph norm. Then there exist $M \geq 1$ and $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\|x(t) - \tilde{x}(t)\|_X \leq \varepsilon(t) := \|\mathfrak{D}_0\|_{\mathcal{L}(U,X)} \|\delta_b(t)\|_U + M e^{\omega t} \|\delta_0 - \mathfrak{D}_0 \delta_b(0)\|_X + \int_0^t M e^{\omega(t-s)} \left(\|\mathcal{A} \mathfrak{D}_0\|_{\mathcal{L}(U,X)} \|\delta_b(s)\|_U + \|\mathfrak{D}_0\|_{\mathcal{L}(U,X)} \|\dot{\delta}_b(s)\|_U + \|\delta(s)\|_X \right) ds.$$

Theorem 2 Assume that the system is input-to-state-stable. Then there exist $M \geq 1$, $\omega < 0$ and $\gamma: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ such that

$$\|x(t) - \tilde{x}(t)\|_X \leq \varepsilon(t) := M e^{\omega t} \|\delta_0\|_X + \int_0^t M e^{\omega(t-s)} \|\delta(s)\|_X ds + \gamma(\|\delta_b\|_{L^\infty(0,t;\partial\Omega)}).$$

In the presented work, we focus on the error estimator from Theorem 1 which we improve the practical relevance by deriving the required parameters from numerical approximations. We illustrate its applicability using the heat equation on $[0, 1]$ as academic toy example and the Stokes flow around a cylinder. Here, we exemplarily show in Fig. 1 the convergence and boundedness of the approximations ω_n as well as of the operator norms of \mathfrak{D}_0 and $\mathcal{A} \mathfrak{D}_0$ for the Stokes example. Further, we display in Fig. 2 the error estimator and its contributions

The presented work is available in the publication [6] and the preprint [5], both equipped with an according reference implementation in [3] and [4], respectively.

$$\varepsilon_{\text{init}} := e^{\omega t} \|\delta_0\|_X, \quad \varepsilon_{b,f,1} := \int_0^t e^{\omega(t-s)} \|\mathfrak{A} \mathfrak{D}_0\|_{\mathcal{L}(U,X)} \|\delta_b(s)\|_U ds, \quad \varepsilon_{b,[0]} := e^{\omega t} \|\mathfrak{D}_0 \delta_b(0)\|_X, \\ \varepsilon_{b,f,2} := \int_0^t e^{\omega(t-s)} \|\mathfrak{D}_0\|_{\mathcal{L}(U,X)} \|\dot{\delta}_b(s)\|_U ds, \quad \varepsilon_{b,[t]} := \|\mathfrak{D}_0\|_{\mathcal{L}(U,X)} \|\delta_b(t)\|_U, \quad \varepsilon_{\text{evo}} := \int_0^t e^{\omega(t-s)} \|\delta(s)\|_X ds.$$

The presented work is available in the publication [6] and the preprint [5], both equipped with an according reference implementation in [3] and [4], respectively. Beyond this, we showed in [7] that the relevant constants and functions for the error estimator in Theorem 2 can also be retrieved from numerical approximations.

3 Conclusions

We demonstrate that rigorous a posteriori error certificates can be obtained for PINNs used as surrogate models of linear partial differential equations, without any knowledge of the exact solution.

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Hubs in Nearest-Neighbor Graphs: Origins, Applications and Challenges

Miloš Radovanović¹

¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences
Department of Mathematics and Informatics
Trg Dositeja Obradovića 4, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

radacha@dmi.uns.ac.rs

Keywords

curse of dimensionality, nearest neighbors, hubs, machine learning, data mining, information retrieval

1 Introduction

Hubness, as the tendency of k -nearest neighbor graphs constructed from tabular data using some distance measure to contain hubs, i.e., nodes with in-degree much higher than expected, has drawn a fair amount of attention in recent years due to the observed impact on techniques used in many application domains, especially those affected by the “curse of dimensionality.”

2 Main contribution

This talk will give an overview of the field, and will be organized in three parts:

1. Origins, which will discuss the causes of the emergence of hubs (and their low in-degree counterparts, the anti-hubs), and their relationships with high (intrinsic) dimensionality, neighborhood size, distance concentration, and the notion of centrality,
2. Applications, where we will present some notable effects of (anti-)hubs on techniques from different fields, including machine learning, data mining and information retrieval, identify two different approaches to handling hubs adopted by researchers – through fighting or embracing their existence – and review some notable techniques and applications belonging to the two groups, and
3. Challenges, which will discuss work in progress, open problems, and areas with significant opportunities for hub-related research.

3 Conclusions

Since the initial work by the author [1], which explored some aspects of the origins and applications of hubness, most notably establishing its connection to high (intrinsic) dimensionality of data, the phenomenon has been recognized as a major factor to be considered by many methods and approaches from diverse fields. The primary goal of this talk is to draw the attention of the control theory community to this aspect of the dimensionality curse, kick-starting the discussion on its possible impact and applications in the field of control theory.

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On the Local Stabilisation of Interacting Particle Systems and its Connection to Energy Convexification

Lucas M. Moschen¹, Dante Kalise¹, Grigorios A. Pavliotis¹

¹ Department of Mathematics, Imperial College London, UK

lucas.moschen22@imperial.ac.uk, d.kalise@imperial.ac.uk, g.pavliotis@imperial.ac.uk

Keywords

McKean-Vlasov dynamics, Wasserstein gradient flows, feedback stabilization, Riccati equation, interacting particle systems

Interacting particle systems model collective phenomena across statistical mechanics, opinion dynamics, and sampling. In the mean-field limit, when the number of particles N goes to infinity, the evolution of the particle density is governed by the *McKean-Vlasov equation*, which, depending on the pairwise interactions between particles and the external forces confining them, can exhibit multiple equilibria, slow convergence, and metastable behaviour [3]. When formulated as a *Wasserstein gradient flow* in the space of probability measures $\mathcal{P}(\Omega)$ for a set Ω [1], the density μ_t evolves according to

$$\partial_t \mu_t = \nabla \cdot \left(\mu_t \nabla \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta \mu}(\mu_t) \right),$$

where \mathcal{F} is a free energy functional over probability measures.

We propose a feedback control framework that stabilises unstable equilibria and accelerates convergence by adding time-dependent control inputs acting through spatial actuators. Linearising around a target steady state, we study the properties of this operator and formulate a linear-quadratic optimal control problem whose operator Riccati equation yields a feedback law that shifts the spectrum of the linearised generator. We then prove that the closed-loop dynamics is exponentially stable in the vicinity of the target steady state. Geometrically, the closed-loop feedback corresponds to a local convexification of the free energy functional in the potential variables via a finite-rank quadratic correction that targets the unstable modes. At the particle level, the mean-field feedback induces a controlled McKean-Vlasov SDE implementable via empirical slow-mode coordinates. In the Gibbs case $\bar{\mu} \propto e^{-V/\sigma}$, the control bypasses the unknown partition function. Spectral-method simulations demonstrate accelerated convergence in several benchmarks, including the Kuramoto model and constrained dynamics on manifolds. Further details can be found in [2].

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Convex synthesis of mini-batch gradient methods

Dennis Gramlich¹

¹Chair of Intelligent Control Systems, RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany

dennis.gramlich@ic.rwth-aachen.de

Keywords

stochastic gradient descent, integral quadratic constraints, momentum, convex synthesis, robust control

1 Mini-batch gradient methods and acceleration

Accelerated gradient methods such as Nesterov’s accelerated gradient descent (NAGD) [4] and Triple Momentum (TM) [5] achieve accelerated convergence rates for minimizing strongly convex functions with Lipschitz continuous gradients. In practice, accelerated gradient methods are often used to minimize *sum-structured* objective functions of the form

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N f_i(z), \quad \text{with } f_i : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \text{and minimizer } z_\star^f \in \underset{z \in \mathbb{R}^d}{\operatorname{argmin}} f(z).$$

For example, in empirical risk minimization, f_i corresponds to the loss on the i -th data point.

Since N is typically large, evaluating the full gradient $\nabla f(z)$ is computationally expensive. Instead, stochastic methods rely on mini-batch gradients of the form

$$\nabla f_{\mathcal{J}}(z) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{J}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{J}} \nabla f_i(z). \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{J} \subset \{1, \dots, N\}$ denotes the mini-batch and $b = |\mathcal{J}|$ its size.

Employing accelerated methods (tuned for full gradients) with mini-batch gradients leads to qualitative changes in the convergence behavior. As shown in Figure 1, the expected optimization error $\mathbb{E}[\|z_t - z_\star^f\|^2]$ for NAGD with mini-batch gradients (in an academic setting) exhibits two distinct regimes: far from the optimum, mini-batch NAGD converges linearly, but at a slower rate than the deterministic NAGD. Near the optimum, the error plateaus at a nonzero level due to non-vanishing gradient noise. In contrast, full-gradient NAGD converges linearly all the way to the optimum without an error floor.

Importantly, convergence to an error floor at a slower rate, as visible in Figure 1, is already an optimistic scenario for NAGD. In general, if the parameters of NAGD are tuned for the deterministic setting, mini-batch NAGD is just as likely to diverge as to converge, depending on the condition number of the problem and the batch size [1]. Due these observation, this abstract contributes a control approach for designing stochastic gradient methods with guaranteed stability and optimized convergence rates.

2 Integral quadratic constraints (IQCs) for mini-batch gradients

A key step to understanding these qualitative changes is to decompose the mini-batch gradient into

$$\nabla f_{\mathcal{J}}(z) = \underbrace{\nabla f(z)}_{\text{full gradient}} + \underbrace{w^1}_{\text{state-dependent noise}} + \underbrace{w^2}_{\text{irreducible noise}}, \quad (2)$$

where $w^1 = \nabla f_{\mathcal{J}}(z) - \nabla f(z) - \nabla f_{\mathcal{J}}(z_\star^f)$ vanishes at the optimum z_\star^f and $w^2 = \nabla f_{\mathcal{J}}(z_\star^f)$ is present even at the optimum. The full gradient drives optimization toward z_\star^f , while the remaining two terms act as stochastic disturbances. The second component represents z -dependent randomness that dominates far from z_\star^f ; it is responsible for the degraded convergence rate in the initial phase (first asymptotic line in Figure 1) and potential instability. The third component is irreducible noise, responsible for the error floor. Understanding how these disturbances influence convergence is a key theoretical challenge.

Indeed, the first two components of the decomposition (2) satisfy a family of stochastic IQCs, which is a stochastic extension of the classical O’Shea-Zames-Falb IQC for static nonlinearities [6]. This family can be incorporated into a robust control framework for synthesizing stochastic optimization algorithms.

Figure 1: Expected optimization error $\mathbb{E}[\|z_t - z_*^f\|^2]$ for NAGD with full gradients vs. mini-batch gradients ($b = 1$). Dashed lines show asymptotic rates in two regimes: linear convergence far from the optimum, and error floor near the optimum. The data is generated for the three objective functions $f_1(z) = \frac{1}{2}\|z - 0.12\|^2$, $f_2(z) = \frac{1}{20}\|z + 0.6\|^2$, and $f_3(z) = f_2(z)$.

(a) Synthesized convergence rates ρ for mini-batch gradient methods, plotted against condition number $\kappa = l/m$. The solid black line indicates the deterministic TM rate; the dashed black line (occluded by the blue line) shows the GD rate. **(b)** Cost of parallelism: ratio $\rho_{\text{synthesis}}/\rho_{\text{GD}}^b$ vs condition number $\kappa = l/m$. Values equal to 1 (horizontal line) correspond to perfect parallelism—matching the performance of b sequential GD steps.

Figure 2: Numerical results for synthesized mini-batch gradient methods.

Theorem 2.1 (Causal, time-invariant batch gradient IQC) Let f_i for $i = 1, \dots, N$ be m -strongly convex and l -smooth. Let further $(\lambda_t)_{t \in \mathbb{N}_0} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a sequence with

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} |\lambda_t| \rho^{-t} < \infty, \quad \lambda_t \leq 0 \text{ for } t > 0, \quad \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \rho^{-t} \lambda_t \geq 0$$

for some given $\rho \in]0, 1]$. Then, with $z_t := z_*^f$ for $t < 0$, the inequality

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \rho^{-2t+k} \lambda_k \mathbb{E}[(\nabla f(z_t) - m(z_t - z_*^f))^{\top} (l(z_{t-k} - z_*^f) - \nabla f(z_{t-k})))] \geq b \left(\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \rho^{-t} \lambda_t \right) \sum_{t=0}^{\tau} \rho^{-2t} \mathbb{E}[\|w_t^1\|^2]$$

holds for any previsible stochastic process $\mathbf{z} = (z_t)_{t=0}^{\infty}$ on \mathbb{R}^d and any finite horizon τ .

3 Numerical results

We numerically synthesize optimized algorithms for mini-batch gradients using the conditions of Theorem 2.1. The key findings are shown in Figures 2a and 2b. Figure 2a shows that the synthesized rates match the deterministic GD rate for $b = 1$ and approach the information-theoretically optimal [2] TM rate as b increases. Figure 2b shows that, as κ grows, the synthesized rates approach the b -th power of the GD rate, matching the performance of b sequential GD steps. This corresponds to perfect parallelism: b parallel stochastic gradient evaluations collected in a mini-batch achieve the same per-iteration progress as b sequential deterministic GD steps.

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Non-conservative Stability Analysis of Linear Systems in Feedback with ReLU Neural Networks

Patricia Pauli¹, Dennis Gramlich²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, The Netherlands
² Chair of Intelligent Control Systems, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

patricia.pauli@tue.nl, dennis.gramlich@ic.rwth-aachen.de

Keywords

ReLU neural networks, global asymptotic stability, quadratic constraints, linear matrix inequalities

1 Introduction

Neural network (NN) controllers trained using machine learning are being deployed increasingly in safety-critical control loops. Certifying their closed-loop stability has therefore become a central challenge at the intersection of control theory and machine learning [1, 2]. In this work, we address this challenge by developing non-conservative and computationally tractable stability certificates for discrete-time linear systems in feedback with ReLU NN controllers. This setting encompasses, for instance, reinforcement-learning policies, NN surrogates of optimization-based controllers, and recurrent architectures. We cast the closed loop in the classical Lur'e framework [4] and introduce a new class of *complete* quadratic constraints (QCs) for repeated ReLU nonlinearities, which enables LMI-based stability analysis. Our main contribution is to show that the resulting LMI certificate is *necessary and sufficient* for global asymptotic stability (GAS). In addition, we prove that if the corresponding bias-free closed loop is GAS, then the biased closed loop converges to a bounded set, thereby allowing stability properties of biased systems to be inferred from the bias-free analysis.

2 Problem setup

Consider a discrete-time linear plant $x_p(t+1) = A_p x_p(t) + B_p u(t)$ with state $x_p(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$ and control input $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$. We consider state-feedback control using a fully connected feedforward neural network with L hidden layers and ReLU activation functions $\Phi(z) : \mathbb{R}^{n_{\ell+1}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_{\ell+1}}$:

$$z_1(t) = W_1 x_p(t) + b_1, \quad z_\ell(t) = W_\ell \Phi(z_{\ell-1}(t)) + b_\ell, \quad \ell = 2, \dots, L-1, \quad u(t) = W_L \Phi(z_{L-1}(t)) + b_L. \quad (1)$$

NN weights are denoted by $W_\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\ell+1} \times n_\ell}$ and biases by $b_\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\ell+1}}$. The closed-loop system is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x_p(t+1) &= A x_p(t) + B w(t) + \bar{b}_1, \\ z(t) &= C x_p(t) + D w(t) + \bar{b}_2, \\ w(t) &= \Phi(z(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $z(t) = (z_1^\top(t) \quad z_2^\top(t) \quad \dots \quad z_{L-1}^\top(t))^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_w}$, $n_w = \sum_{\ell=1}^L n_\ell$, $A = A_p$, $B = B_p (0 \quad \dots \quad 0 \quad W_L)$,

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} W_1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ W_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & W_3 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & W_{L-1} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \bar{b}_1 = B_p b_L, \quad \bar{b}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_{L-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Our goal is to derive non-conservative stability certificates for system (2).

3 Main results

We now show that boundedness of the biased system is closely linked to global asymptotic stability of the bias-free system.

Theorem 1 (Stability Equivalence). *Consider the closed-loop system $\Sigma_{\bar{b}}$ defined by (2) with neural network controller. Let Σ_0 denote the corresponding bias-free system, i.e., $\bar{b}_1 = 0$ and $\bar{b}_2 = 0$. Then:*

- (i) *If the origin of $\Sigma_{\bar{b}}$ is GAS, then the origin of Σ_0 is GAS.*
- (ii) *If the origin of Σ_0 is GAS, then all trajectories of $\Sigma_{\bar{b}}$ remain bounded and converge to a bounded set.*

Theorem 1 shows that analyzing the bias-free system Σ_0 yields meaningful guarantees for the biased system $\Sigma_{\bar{b}}$: stability of Σ_0 ensures boundedness and convergence of trajectories of $\Sigma_{\bar{b}}$ to a bounded set, and may even indicate stability of the biased system itself.

The key structural property is that the closed-loop map of Σ_0 is *positively homogeneous of degree one*: scaling an initial condition by $\lambda \geq 0$ scales every subsequent state by the same factor. Consequently, the biased system resembles the bias-free system at large signal amplitudes, where the biases become negligible.

Next, we analyze the bias-free system Σ_0 using the framework of quadratic constraints [5].

Definition 2 (Quadratic Constraint). *A function $\Delta : \mathbb{R}^{n_v} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_v}$ satisfies the quadratic constraint defined by $M \in \mathbb{S}^{2n_v}$ if*

$$\begin{pmatrix} v \\ \Delta(v) \end{pmatrix}^\top M \begin{pmatrix} v \\ \Delta(v) \end{pmatrix} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } v \in \mathbb{R}^{n_v}. \quad (3)$$

A family of matrices $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{S}^{2n_v}$ defines a set of quadratic constraints if Δ satisfies the QC defined by every $M \in \mathcal{M}$.

The ReLU activation function is sector-bounded in $[0, 1]$ and often characterized by a sector QC for LMI-based stability analysis [3, 8, 7]. However, this characterization is conservative. We instead introduce a *complete* multiplier family, similar [6], and derive a new formulation. Completeness here means that the multiplier family captures *all* quadratic forms satisfied by the repeated ReLU nonlinearity. We introduce a complete and incomplete family of multipliers:

$$\mathcal{M}_c := \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} -I & I \\ 0 & I \end{pmatrix}^\top \left(C + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Lambda \\ \Lambda & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right) \begin{pmatrix} -I & I \\ 0 & I \end{pmatrix} \mid C \in \text{COP}^{2n_v}, \Lambda \in \mathbb{D}^{n_v} \right\}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{M}_i := \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} -I & I \\ 0 & I \end{pmatrix}^\top \left(C + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Lambda \\ \Lambda & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right) \begin{pmatrix} -I & I \\ 0 & I \end{pmatrix} \mid C \in \mathbb{R}^{2n_v \times 2n_v}, C \geq 0, \Lambda \in \mathbb{D}^{n_v} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where COP^{2n_v} is the copositive cone and $C \geq 0$ is entry-wise non-negativity. Since every entry-wise non-negative symmetric matrix is copositive, $\mathcal{M}_i \subsetneq \mathcal{M}_c$. Checking entry-wise non-negativity is straightforward, whereas copositivity is NP-hard to verify.

In what follows, we present our main result: a stability certificate for observable systems based on the complete multiplier family \mathcal{M}_c . The certificate is non-conservative in the sense that it is both necessary and sufficient for GAS.

Theorem 3 (IQC Certificate for Observable Systems). *Assume (A, C) is observable. The origin of Σ_0 is GAS if and only if there exist $P \succ 0$, a horizon length $T \in \mathbb{N}$, and a multiplier $M \in \mathcal{M}_c$ such that*

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{R}_T \\ \mathcal{Z}_T \end{pmatrix}^\top \begin{pmatrix} P & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & M \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{R}_T \\ \mathcal{Z}_T \end{pmatrix} \prec 0, \mathcal{R}_T = \begin{pmatrix} A^T & A^{T-1}B & \cdots & B \\ I & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{Z}_T = \begin{pmatrix} C & D & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ CA & CB & D & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ CA^{T-1} & \cdots & \cdots & CB & D \\ 0 & I & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & I \end{pmatrix}.$$

Replacing $M \in \mathcal{M}_c$ by $M \in \mathcal{M}_i$ in Theorem 3 yields a tractable semidefinite program, at the expense of conservatism. Accordingly, the resulting stability certificate based on \mathcal{M}_i is sufficient but not necessary.

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An efficient and adaptive machine learning surrogate for optimal control in enhanced oil recovery

Tim Keil¹, Hendrik Kleikamp², Rolf J. Lorentzen³, Micheal B. Oguntola⁴, Mario Ohlberger⁵

¹ TNG Technology Consulting GmbH, Munich, Germany

² IDEA_Lab, University of Graz, Graz, Austria

³ NORCE-Norwegian Research Center AS, Bergen, Norway

⁴ University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway

⁵ Mathematics Münster, University of Münster, Münster, Germany

tim.keil@uni-muenster.de, hendrik.kleikamp@uni-graz.at, rolo@norceresearch.no,
micheal.oguntola@uib.no, mario.ohlberger@uni-muenster.de

Keywords

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1 Introduction

Improving the control of injection and production wells in enhanced oil recovery can have a substantial positive environmental and economical impact. It is therefore of interest to obtain suitable control policies for operating large oil fields. However, the associated optimal control problems consist of complex high-fidelity simulations of porous media flows that represent involved reservoir models, see for instance [2]. In order to compute a suitable control using gradient-based methods, derivatives of the objective function are required, which are often inaccessible or computationally infeasible to obtain. Ensemble-based optimization techniques have thus been proposed, see [1], that rely solely on function evaluations of the objective. Nevertheless, evaluating the target function just once for a fixed control requires solving the high-fidelity flow problem and is therefore a limiting computational factor.

Machine learning has been used previously in PDE-constrained optimization, see for example [5], and also to facilitate enhanced oil recovery, see [3]. In this presentation, we introduce a strategy using deep neural networks to accelerate the optimization process in enhanced oil recovery and to reduce the number of performed high-fidelity solves. A machine learning surrogate for the net present value function is built adaptively and the same ensemble-based optimization algorithm as before is applied to the surrogate. Further details on our method are given in [4] and also summarized below.

2 Main contribution

In optimization problems related to enhanced oil recovery, one typically tries to maximize the net present value (NPV). Ensemble-based optimization algorithms use several evaluations of the NPV function in order to compute an ascent direction as an approximation of a preconditioned gradient in every iteration of the algorithm. Our approach uses the same formulas for the ascent direction but replaces many high-fidelity evaluations by those of a neural network surrogate. To be more precise, our algorithm consists of an outer and an inner optimization loop. In every iteration of the outer optimization loop, the exact objective function is evaluated several times using simulations of the full order model in order to build an ascent direction. The data obtained from these simulations are used to train a neural network as a surrogate for the NPV function. In the inner loop, the same ensemble-based optimization algorithm is run on the neural network surrogate until convergence. Within the outer loop it is further evaluated, based on the high-fidelity data, whether convergence has been reached or the optimization should be continued. We refer to Figure 1 for a visualization of potential optimization paths taken when using only the full order model compared to the adaptive surrogate-based method.

Figure 1: Example of potential optimization paths taken by the different algorithms.

In our numerical experiments we use the open porous media flow reservoir simulator, see [6]. The results on a five-spot field benchmark example reveal that the surrogate-based optimization finds a control with larger NPV, higher oil production and at the same time reduced water and polymer productions compared to the ensemble optimization using only high-fidelity evaluations. Moreover, the computational costs could be decreased by a factor of roughly 10. The number of high-fidelity simulations required was reduced by about 95% when using the surrogate.

3 Conclusions

In this contribution we present an efficient method for optimal control of polymer flooding in enhanced oil recovery. The algorithm shows reduced computational costs compared to traditional methods. At the same time, controls leading to improved NPVs and reduced environmental impact can be reached by the method due to the highly non-convex nature of the objective function containing many local optima. It would therefore be of interest to investigate the general approach in settings with well-behaved objective functions that allow for a detailed study of the method’s properties.

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Data-Driven Identification of Port-Hamiltonian DAE Systems by Gaussian Processes

Matthias Menge^{1,2}, Peter Zaspel¹, Michael Günther²

¹ Research Group Scientific Computing and High Performance Computing - University of Wuppertal

² Research Group Applied and Computational Mathematics - University of Wuppertal

menge@uni-wuppertal.de

Keywords

Port-Hamiltonian systems, data-driven approach, Gaussian process regression, coupled dynamical systems, structure preservation

1 Introduction

The port-Hamiltonian (pH) framework is a modeling paradigm that evolved by combining ideas from *port-based modeling*, *geometric mechanics*, and *systems and control theory* [3]. It allows for structure-preserving models of multi-physics problems together with controllers. These interconnections between different physical and virtual domains allow for the modeling of complex systems as a composition of functional subsystems. The coupling between these subsystems is done using energy-preserving ports, which are a combination of *flow* and *effort* variables of that domain.

Identifying such systems from data can overcome some limitations of traditional first-principle modeling. For example, if the knowledge of the system is incomplete, it can still be identified and combined with other known pH systems. To generate such surrogate pH models, data can either be collected from proprietary black box simulations or measurements from real systems.

However, standard data-driven techniques often struggle to respect the structural constraints inherent to pH systems, which may lead to physically inaccurate trajectories. To address this, current research leverages physics-informed frameworks, such as Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) and informed versions of Gaussian Processes (GP). In their paper, Beckers et al. [1] showed how to learn a nonlinear pH-system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) using GPs while maintaining conservation of energy and passivity by introducing a pH kernel. This shifts the GP from representing a distribution of functions to representing a distribution of pH dynamics and therefore surpasses traditional input-output learning techniques.

2 Main contribution

We extend on the identification of pH-ODE systems proposed in [1] by considering pH differential algebraic equations (DAE) without feed-through given by

$$E(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}} = (J(\mathbf{x}) - R(\mathbf{x}))\mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}) + G(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{u} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = G(\mathbf{x})^\top \mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (2)$$

The DAE system consists of the state equation 1 and the output equation 2. For the *port-based modeling* aspect of this DAE system, the input-port \mathbf{u} in the state equation and the output-port \mathbf{y} of the output are key components. The Hamiltonian aspect is hidden in the effort function \mathbf{z} by imposing the compatibility condition $E(\mathbf{x})^\top \mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \mathcal{H}(x)$, where $\mathcal{H}(x)$ is a continuously differentiable Hamiltonian function of the system and the flow matrix $E(\mathbf{x})$ is singular. The remainder of the system dynamics are defined by the skew-symmetric structure matrix J and the positive semi-definite dissipation matrix R .

First promising results were developed by Zaspel and Günther in [4]. They show that the approach from Beckers et al. can be expanded to DAE systems. This was achieved by learning the vector-valued

effort function of the pH-DAE instead of the gradient of the scalar Hamiltonian. To explain the identification in greater detail, we take a first step by assuming a scalar effort function $z : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that is approximated by a Gaussian Process with

$$z \sim \mathcal{GP}(0, k), \quad (3)$$

where the mean function was chosen to be zero and $k : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the covariance of the GP[2]. The choice of a zero mean is common practice and does not imply that the mean of the posterior functions is also zero, as it will be informed by the training data through the conditioning of the GP.

This demo system can then be extended to the multi-task case where the effort function becomes *vector-valued* $z : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$. The GP now needs to approximate D different tasks which correspond to the state variables in \mathbf{x} . It can therefore be assumed that $D = d$ and that \mathbf{z} can now be approximated by

$$\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{GP}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{k}), \quad (4)$$

where $m : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$ is now *vector-valued* as well and $k : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D \times \mathbb{R}^D$ is now *matrix-valued*.

As proposed by Beckers et al. we assume that the structure and dissipation matrices J and R are constant and given by system knowledge. This allows us to make use of the fact that a linearly transformed GP is again a GP, allowing us to learn the linearly transformed function $\mathbf{z}_{JR}(\mathbf{x}) := (J - R)\mathbf{z}(\mathbf{x})$ with the GP

$$\mathbf{z}_{JR} \sim \mathcal{GP}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{k}_{JR}). \quad (5)$$

The findings were underlined by numerical experiments. The first example is a small electrical network with non-linear components and the second is a constrained multibody system. Zaspel and Günther observed excellent approximations up to the data's discretization accuracy with only very few training samples on both examples.

3 Outlook and Future Work

Further research on this topic is carried out in the project C03 of the collaborative research center “Port-Hamiltonian Systems” (CRC 1701) at the university of Wuppertal. In the duration of this project, we hope to extend on the identification of pH-DAEs in different directions. One key aspect is to make the GP-based methods more suitable for identification on the full state space of high-dimensional systems by improving on the performance of GPs on large datasets. These goals could be achieved via (adaptive) sampling and approximation training on GPUs. Especially the latter should reduce complexity and runtime. Besides the performance of the method, we would like to extend its capabilities by achieving optimized parameter estimation for non-trivial structure J and dissipation R .

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An Integral Controller for Physics-Informed Learning

Matthieu Barreau¹, Loïc Michel²

¹ KTH Royal Institute of Technology and Digital Futures, Stockholm, Sweden

² Nantes Université, École Centrale Nantes, CNRS, LS2N, UMR 6004, F-44000, Nantes, France

barreau@kth.se, loic.michel@ec-nantes.fr

Keywords

Neural-networks, PINN, continuous-time gradient-descent

1 Introduction

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) [6] provide a framework for approximating solutions of differential equations by incorporating governing equations directly into the loss function. Instead of relying solely on data, PINNs enforce physical consistency through residual penalties, enabling efficient learning even in data-scarce regimes, with missing or corrupted data, model mismatch, and high-dimensional settings. For all these reasons, this tool has been widely adopted across a large variety of fields.

However, PINNs are inherently formulated as multi-objective optimization problems combining data loss, boundary conditions, and physics residuals. This structure often induces gradient imbalance and numerical stiffness, leading to instability during training [10]. Moreover, the stochastic nature of neural network optimization—due to random initialization, mini-batch sampling, and non-convex architectures—further increases variability.

Numerous strategies have been proposed to enhance robustness and convergence, including improved initialization schemes such as Xavier initialization [3], adaptive optimizers such as Adam [7], architectural modifications [5], and pretraining strategies [4]. A promising approach is to adjust the weights of each objective during training, a technique known as adaptive reweighting. Some empirical approaches consider gradient-norm balancing [10], neural tangent kernel analysis [11], or variance-based weighting [8].

All these approaches are grounded in empirical observations and, despite their effectiveness, remain poorly understood. Recent development in the constrained optimization field [2] formulates the training process as a dynamical system. This new context enables the interpretation of some methodologies in terms of control theory. Moreover, these approaches can be extended using the control framework.

2 Main contribution

Let $\mathfrak{F} : \mathcal{H}^q(U, \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^2(U, \mathbb{R}^n)$ be a possibly nonlinear operator where U is an open bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^p . We consider the ODE/PDE problem in equation (1) where $v : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ belongs to a Sobolev space $\mathcal{H}^q(U, \mathbb{R}^n)$ with $q \geq 0$, Γ_1 is a subset of the boundary of U and v_Γ is prescribed as the initial and boundary conditions. Additional in-domain point-wise knowledge is provided through $\Gamma_2 \subset U$. We assume that problem (1) is well-posed with $\Gamma_2 = \emptyset$, meaning that there exists a unique solution $v : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ which satisfies Equation (1) in a weak sense.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{F}[v](u) &= 0, & u \in U, \\ v(s) &= v_\Gamma(s), & s \in \Gamma_1 \cup \Gamma_2, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The *forward* problem in PINNs is to approximate the solution v using a deep feed-forward neural network v_θ with parameter θ . We want to write the training process as a dynamical system and design control methodologies to ensure classical local control properties.

2.1 PINN Training as a Dynamical System

Our first contribution is to write the training of a PINN as a learning under constraint problem. Indeed, approximating a weak solution to the original problem (1) is equivalent to solving the following on v_θ :

$$\theta_* \in \underset{\theta}{\text{Argmin}} \int_{\Gamma} \|v_\Gamma(s) - v_\theta(s)\|^2 ds \text{ subject to } \int_U \|\mathfrak{F}[v_\theta](u)\|^2 du = 0. \quad (2)$$

A numerically tractable solution for estimating the integrals is to discretize the sets Γ and U into D_Γ and D_U and then create the data and physics costs as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}(\theta, D_\Gamma) = \frac{1}{|D_\Gamma|} \sum_{s \in D_\Gamma} \|v(s) - v_\theta(s)\|^2 \text{ and } \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, D_U) = \frac{1}{|D_U|} \sum_{u \in D_U} \|\mathfrak{F}[v_\theta](u)\|^2,$$

with $\mathcal{L}_\lambda(\theta, D_\Gamma, D_U) = \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}(\theta, D_\Gamma) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, D_U)$ as the total cost¹. Then, using the Lagrange theory [1], we can rewrite (2) as $\theta_* \in \text{Argmin}_\theta \max_\lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}(\theta, D_\Gamma) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, D_U)$. If we decide to use a gradient-descent strategy to estimate a local minimum θ^* of the previous cost, we will create the following dynamical system:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\xi} \theta(\xi) &= -\nabla_\theta \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}(\theta, \Gamma) - \lambda(\xi) \nabla_\theta \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, U) + w(\xi), & \theta(0) \text{ random,} \\ y(t) &= \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, U) + n(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where θ is the high-dimensional state of the dynamical system which defines the training, and $w = \nabla_\theta \mathcal{L}_\lambda(\theta, D_\Gamma, D_U) - \nabla_\theta \mathcal{L}_\lambda(\theta, \Gamma, U)$ and $n = \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, D_U) - \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}(\theta, U)$. If the samplings D_Γ and D_U are uniform in Γ and U and resampled periodically, then w and n are Gaussian disturbance and noise.

Within this framework, an *accurate* forward problem in PINNs is a robust convergence of θ to θ_* with respect to the random initial condition $\theta(0)$ and noise and disturbances. A way to improve accuracy is to design the control input λ within a feedback loop, thereby enabling adaptive reweighting.

2.2 Integrator and Leaky-Integrator

Since we want $y(\theta_*) = 0$, that means that we want a zero steady-state error. A natural choice of controller is then the integrator one: $\frac{d}{d\xi} \lambda = y(\xi)$. This is the empirical strategy proposed, for instance, in [9], which is justified by treating the training as a dynamical system.

However, the proposed physical model \mathfrak{F} might not be accurate, and there might be a mismatch between the additional measurements collected in Γ_2 and the model \mathfrak{F} . In that case, an integrator is probably not the best choice, and a leaky integrator could be used as an anti-windup strategy to avoid divergence. In that case, we get $\frac{d}{d\xi} \lambda = y(\xi) - \phi \lambda$ with $\phi > 0$. This new adaptive weighting strategy would enable taking the model into account while favoring measurements over the model when they disagree.

We tested our methodology on a simple linear system² and reported the accuracy of the training in the open-loop case (λ is constant) and in the closed-loop case (for different values of the forgetting factor ϕ). The results are displayed in Figure 1. We can see that the pure integrator and the open-loop approach are very sensitive to model mismatch, whereas an increased (but not too large) forgetting factor ϕ mitigates the mismatch effects while keeping the accuracy relatively low.

Figure 1: Accuracy of the forward problem with open-loop (left) and closed-loop strategies for different forgetting factor ϕ .

3 Conclusion

This work provides a control-theoretic interpretation of PINN training, revealing an intrinsic trade-off between accuracy and robustness in integral and leaky-integral regulation. Beyond the preliminary analysis, this perspective opens promising directions, including rigorous stability guarantees under stochastic optimization, robustness analysis under model mismatch, robust identification, and a unifying control-based framework for adaptive PINN training strategies.

¹We will also use $\mathcal{L}_\lambda(\theta, \Gamma, U)$ as the integral formulation instead of a sum.

²See the code at <https://github.com/mBarreau/Controlled-PINN> for more information.

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Sparse Training of Neural Networks based on Multilevel Mirror Descent

Yannick Lunk¹, Sebastian Scott¹ Leon Bungert^{1,2}

¹ Institute of Mathematics, University of Würzburg, Germany

² Center for Artificial Intelligence and Data Science (CAIDAS), University of Würzburg, Germany

{yannick.lunk,sebastian.scott,leon.bungert}@uni-wuerzburg.de

Keywords

Sparse training, Mirror descent, Bregman iterations, Multilevel optimization, Sparse neural networks

1 Introduction

Deep neural networks have achieved remarkable success across a wide range of application domains [5]. However, their performance often comes at the cost of substantial computational resources, including large memory requirements and specialized hardware, which raises concerns regarding scalability and environmental impact [2].

These challenges have motivated extensive research into sparse neural networks, in which many of the possible connections between neurons are absent. A central concept in this area is the Lottery Ticket Hypothesis [4], which posits that within a randomly initialized dense network there exists a sparse subnetwork that, when trained in isolation, can reach performance comparable to that of the original model.

Methods for obtaining sparse neural networks are commonly divided into two categories: pruning and sparse training. Pruning approaches first train a dense model, then remove connections deemed unnecessary, and subsequently fine-tune the resulting sparse network. In contrast, sparse training methods enforce and maintain sparsity throughout the entire training process.

We propose a dynamic sparse training algorithm based on linearized Bregman iterations/mirror descent that exploits naturally emerging sparsity by alternating between phases of fixed and dynamic network structures. The core idea is to integrate sparsity-inducing Bregman iterations with an adaptive freezing mechanism for the network structure, enabling efficient exploration of the sparse parameter space while preserving sparsity throughout training.

2 Main contribution

Training typically amounts to solving

$$\min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} \mathcal{L}(\theta),$$

where $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a differentiable and non-negative loss function, such as the empirical loss, and θ denotes the network parameters. One way to enforce constraints or encourage sparsity in the solution is to introduce a proper, convex, and lower semicontinuous function $J: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$, for example the ℓ_1 -norm, and explicitly minimize the composite objective $\mathcal{L} + J$. Alternatively, one can minimize \mathcal{L} directly while implicitly promoting small values of J , as is the case when using linearized Bregman iterations/mirror descent. Defining the elastic-net regularizer

$$J_\delta(\theta) := \frac{1}{2\delta} \|\theta\|^2 + J(\theta), \quad \delta \in (0, \infty),$$

and starting the optimization process with $\theta^{(0)}$ and $v^{(0)} \in \partial J_\delta(\theta^{(0)})$, the sequence generated by linearized Bregman iteration is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} v^{(k+1)} &= v^{(k)} - \tau g^{(k)}, \quad \mathbb{E}[g^{(k)} | \theta^{(k)}] = \nabla \mathcal{L}(\theta^{(k)}), \\ \theta^{(k+1)} &= \text{prox}_{\delta J}(\delta v^{(k+1)}), \end{aligned}$$

with the proximal operator

$$\text{prox}_{\delta J}(\theta) := \operatorname{argmin}_{\tilde{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^d} \frac{1}{2\delta} \|\tilde{\theta} - \theta\|^2 + J(\tilde{\theta}).$$

In some special cases, this proximal operator admits a closed form, e.g. for $J = \lambda \|\cdot\|_1$, we have

$$\text{prox}_{\delta J}(\delta v) = \delta \operatorname{sign}(v) \max(|v| - \lambda, 0)$$

applied componentwise. This particular choice also demonstrates how Bregman iterations can lead to sparse networks [1]. In the above equation, only parameters whose corresponding dual variable v exceeds the threshold λ in absolute value will be non-zero. Intuitively, the dual variable accumulates gradient information and gradually activates parameters whose magnitude exceeds a threshold.

Our main contribution is a modification of linearized Bregman training in which the network structure is periodically frozen. During these phases, only currently active parameters are updated, while periodic full updates allow new parameters to be activated. This procedure can be interpreted as a multilevel optimization scheme [6, 3], where the restriction operator $R^{(k)}: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{D_k}$ is a linear map that selects the nonzero parameters at iteration k , and the corresponding prolongation operator $P^{(k)} = (R^{(k)})^T$ performs zero-padding.

Assuming that the objective function \mathcal{L} is relatively smooth with respect to the elastic-net regularizer J_δ and satisfies a Polyak–Lojasiewicz-type inequality, we establish convergence of the proposed algorithm under a mixed gradient regime: exact gradients are used during full-parameter updates, while an unbiased gradient estimator with bounded variance is employed during phases in which the network structure is frozen.

In addition, we evaluate our method on standard benchmark datasets for image classification and demonstrate that the resulting networks are sparser yet achieve performance comparable to those obtained with linearized Bregman iterations and other sparse training approaches. We further show that the proposed framework offers opportunities to reduce training time through sparsity-aware implementations.

3 Conclusions

Taken together, the results indicate that combining linearized Bregman iterations with a multilevel freezing strategy provides an effective mechanism for sparse neural network training. The proposed approach maintains competitive performance while enabling structured sparsity and potential computational savings, suggesting a promising direction for scalable sparsity-aware optimization methods.

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LDNets: Latent Dynamics Networks, an architecture to learn and predict time variant fields

Carlo Guastamacchia¹, Luca Dede¹

¹MOX - Department of Mathematics, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

luca.dede@polimi.it, carlo.guastamacchia@polimi.it

Keywords

Scientific Machine Learning, Reduced Order Models, Latent Dynamics Networks, Partial Differential Equations

1 Introduction

Physical models based on Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) play a fundamental role in industrial, medical, and scientific applications. They are widely used to predict the evolution of spatio-temporal fields in response to a given input signal. However, their development requires deep knowledge of the physical processes governing the dynamics of the system. Furthermore, their numerical implementation strongly depends on the dynamical properties of the underlying model and must satisfy stability and convergence constraints. In addition, they generally provide higher accuracy at the cost of greater computational effort, a characteristic that makes them less suitable for multi-query applications.

In this context, methods in Scientific Machine Learning (SciML) have demonstrated their ability to learn the relationship between input signals and the evolution of system dynamics directly from measured data or from synthetic data generated by physics-based models. Owing to their low computational cost during the inference phase, these methods can be deployed in real-time applications. Furthermore, the differentiability of deep learning models enables their seamless integration into optimization algorithms.

A large set of methodologies for SciML relies on Autoencoders (AEs). These architectures reduce the dimensionality of discretized output fields by encoding them into a low-dimensional manifold. For dynamical systems, this compact representation can be interpreted as a set of latent dynamical variables that capture the essential properties of the system. The temporal evolution of these latent variables can then be learned at a significantly lower computational cost compared with modeling the full high-dimensional field. Several architectures have been proposed to model the dynamics of latent variables, including Recurrent Neural Networks [1], Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) [4], Neural Ordinary Differential Equations [3], Latent DeepONet [5], and machine learning methods such as Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) [2]. However, this strategy requires encoding the high-dimensional discretized field into a low-dimensional representation through a dedicated Neural Network (NN), the encoder, and subsequently reconstructing the high-dimensional field using another NN, the decoder. This encoding–decoding structure requires a high number of parameters to manage the high dimensional input and output. The complexity of these architectures makes the training process challenging reducing their usability.

To overcome these limits of AEs based architectures in learning dynamical systems, we introduce Latent Dynamics Networks (LDNets) [6].

2 Main contribution

LDNets learn the latent dynamics of a system, encoding it in a low dimensional manifold, and reconstruct the corresponding output field. They are composed of two Fully Connected Neural Networks, the first receives the input signal and learns the time variation of the latent variables, which is then integrated through a numerical scheme, while the second receives the latent variables in input and provides the value of the output field at the required spatial coordinates. Therefore the input and output layers dimensionality does not correspond to the number of sampling points as in AEs. Conversely they provide the spatial field for a given state of the latent dynamics, corresponding to a certain instant of the

input signal. This architecture allows to treat the three spatial coordinates and the time dimension as continuous and independent variables, providing a map from the spatio-temporal coordinates to the output field value, which makes LDNNets extremely lightweight with respect to architectures operating in the high dimensional space. In particular, they present superior prediction capabilities with respect to LSTM and AEs maintaining lower prediction, achievable with a lower training time.

Furthermore, they can be fed with data provided by direct measures, or, alternatively, with synthetic data obtained by solving a Full Order Model. In this second case LDNNets are used to build a Reduced Order Model (ROM), which provides real time solutions to large PDEs. In addition, the low complexity of the network and the low dimensionality of the latent dynamics manifold, reduce the training time making LDNNets suitable for online training strategies as the ones used in digital twinning practice. By presenting numerical results we show the capability of LDNNets to brake the curse of dimensionality, providing low reconstruction error in problems of increasing dimensionality. Furthermore we test the predictive characteristic of LDNNets on markovian and non-markovian systems. In particular we evaluate LDNNets performances on fluid dynamics and electrophysiology problems of increasing complexity and dimensionality arising in computational cardiology.

3 Conclusions

LDNNets are a lightweight architecture capable of achieving high accuracy in prediction tasks. By construction, they are consistent with the arrow of time and do not require time as an explicit input parameter, which allows them to perform predictions even for non-periodic systems, unlike DeepONets. Compared with AEs-based architectures, in LDNNets the latent variables are learned not only to encode the spatial field but also its temporal evolution. This characteristic reduces the overall architectural complexity and makes the training process more efficient.

The continuous representation in both time and space provides several advantages. LDNNets are naturally compatible with physics-based loss functions, enabling a physics-informed learning framework that can improve interpretability and impose stronger constraints during training. Moreover, the sampling of training points can be optimized to reduce computational cost. Since LDNNets do not require a predefined mesh of the domain, they also offer considerable flexibility.

As suggested by the proposed tests, LDNNets can reproduce the spatio-temporal dynamics with negligible computational cost, going from 0.01 s to 1.0 s.

Given these properties, LDNNets represent a reliable tool for industrial and medical applications, particularly for constructing ROMs or learning the evolution of dynamical systems directly from data.

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Relating Discrete-Valued Random Variables: Advanced Bayesian Structure Estimation

Aleksej Gaj^{1,2} and Miroslav Kárný¹

¹ The Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Department of Adaptive Systems, Pod vodárenskou věží 4, Prague 8, 182 00, Czech Republic

² The Czech Technical University, Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Department of Solid State Engineering, Prague

gaj@utia.cas.cz, school@utia.cas.cz

Keywords

approximate Bayesian estimation, Bayesian network, structure estimation, global optimisation

1 Introduction

Knowledge extraction relies on a hypothesis about the dependence of modelled variables. Decision making exploits this knowledge and always faces probabilistically modelled uncertainty. Bayesian networks serve well to this purpose, especially in the considered case of discrete-valued data. Their practical applicability strongly depends on their appropriately chosen structure. The choice relies on the blend of experts' options combined with the extraction of the knowledge from available data. Many techniques have been developed. Those relying on the Bayesian framework are logically consistent with the network nature. This work contributes to them by using global optimisation relying on an exploratory (for instance, genetic) algorithm for generating new structure candidates while taking the posterior probabilities as their "fitness" measure. Unlike standards, it does not assign uniform probability to all structures but exploits a systematic way of assigning prior probability to a newly inspected structure. The presented experiments indicate the effectiveness of the approach. They make worthwhile to implement these improvements for mixture ratio models.

2 Main contribution

Bayesian networks [10, 2, 3, 8, 12] model dependencies among many variables in a feasible way. The feasibility is based on locally limited dependencies. This makes their efficiency strongly dependent on a properly chosen structure of those dependencies. Unsurprisingly, structure estimation techniques are permanently developed, cf. surveys [11] and [7]. Among many techniques, those relying on the Bayesian framework are logically consistent with the networks' nature. They face the curse of dimensionality [1] as the number of competitive structures grows quite quickly with the state space dimension.

This work improves its predecessors by using globally optimising techniques for searching the maximum a posteriori probability estimate of the best structure. It exploits an exploratory (for instance, genetic) algorithm for generating new structure candidates. It also exploits a recently proposed systematic way of assigning prior probability to new candidates [5] so that it need not rely on uniform prior probability over the set of structures. The experiments indicate the effectiveness of the approach. They confirm that it makes sense to expend effort on implementing these improvements for mixture [4] or even mixture-ratio models [6].

3 Conclusions

The presented estimation was motivated by a specific problem [9], but its structural constraints (small data and huge space of potential structures) are quite common in many, often critical, domains. The feasible systematic solution presented here has an extreme potential. We intend to apply it in several domains and hope that at least some colleagues will adopt our solution and successfully apply it to their problems.

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Structural Constraints on Expressivity in Continuous-Depth Neural Networks

Sara-Viola Kuntz^{1,2,3}, Christian Kuehn^{1,2,3}

¹ Technical University of Munich, School of Computation, Information and Technology,
Department of Mathematics, Garching, Germany

² Munich Data Science Institute (MDSI), Garching, Germany

³ Munich Center for Machine Learning (MCML), Munich, Germany

saraviola.kuntz@ma.tum.de, ckuehn@ma.tum.de

Keywords

Neural ODEs, Neural DDEs, Dynamical Systems, Universal Approximation, Expressivity, Memory

1 Introduction

Neural networks can be interpreted as dynamical systems, which allows us to analyze their expressivity using tools from differential equations and control theory. In particular, continuous-depth models such as neural ordinary differential equations (neural ODEs) and neural delay differential equations (neural DDEs) provide a natural framework for studying how phase-space dimension, depth, and memory influence the geometry of realizable input–output maps and universal approximation properties.

2 Main Contribution

In this presentation, we discuss two recent results that characterize structural limitations of continuous-depth neural networks from a dynamical systems perspective. The first part analyzes constraints on critical points and universal embedding in neural ODEs [2]. The second part studies how the memory capacity influences the universal approximation property in neural DDEs [1].

2.1 Critical Points in Neural ODEs

Neural ODEs can be interpreted as continuous-depth limits of residual neural networks (ResNets). From a dynamical systems perspective, they correspond to controlled differential equations whose parameters determine the evolution of trajectories in phase space. This viewpoint allows one to directly relate architectural constraints to geometric properties of the induced input–output map.

We study the input–output dynamics of neural ODEs with scalar output. Depending on the architecture, the induced input–output map exhibits fundamentally different properties concerning the existence and regularity of critical points. In particular, if the phase-space dimension does not exceed the input dimension, structural constraints prevent the existence of critical points. When critical points exist, their regularity can be classified according to the specific architecture.

Based on these structural properties, we derive universal embedding and universal approximation results that characterize when an exact or approximate representation of maps by neural ODEs is possible. While related analysis can also be performed for finite-depth networks [2], we focus here exclusively on the continuous-depth setting. These findings provide a precise link between the phase-space dimension and the geometry of realizable input–output maps.

2.2 Memory Capacity of Neural DDEs

Similarly to neural ODEs, neural delay differential equations (neural DDEs) arise as infinite-depth limits of densely connected residual neural networks (DenseResNets). In contrast to classical ResNet architectures, DenseResNets allow shortcut connections across all layers. From a dynamical systems viewpoint, this corresponds to a system with delay and hence to an infinite-dimensional phase space. The delay introduces memory into the architecture, significantly altering its expressivity.

We analyze how the memory capacity of neural DDEs, quantified by the product $K\tau$ of Lipschitz constant and delay, influences their universal approximation behavior. Although delay systems possess for $\tau > 0$ an infinite-dimensional phase space, the universal approximation property is not guaranteed. For non-augmented architectures with small memory capacity $K\tau$, neural DDEs exhibit structural limitations analogous to those of neural ODEs and fail to satisfy the universal approximation property. In contrast, if the memory capacity exceeds a certain threshold, universal embedding can be established. Moreover, phase-space augmentation enlarges the parameter regime in which universality holds. The results visualized in Figure 1 show that expressivity is governed not only by the phase-space dimension, but also by constraints on the memory capacity [1].

Figure 1: Parameter regions in the three-dimensional space $(K, \tau, m) \in [0, \infty) \times [0, T] \times \mathbb{N}$ of Lipschitz constant K , delay τ and phase-space dimension m : in the orange area, no universal approximation is possible, whereas in the green area, the universal embedding property holds.

3 Conclusions

The results presented demonstrate that expressivity in continuous-depth neural architectures is governed by the structural properties of the underlying dynamical system. In neural ODEs, the phase-space dimension restricts the geometry of realizable maps and determines the existence and regularity of critical points. In neural DDEs, delay introduces memory and an infinite-dimensional phase space; however, universal approximation emerges only beyond a critical memory threshold. Taken together, these findings provide a control-theoretic perspective on depth, dimension, and memory as fundamental resources in machine learning architectures.

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A polynomial approximation scheme for nonlinear model reduction by moment matching

Carlos Doebeli¹, Alessandro Astolfi², Dante Kalise¹,
Alessio Moreschini², Giordano Scarciotti², Joel Simard²

¹ Department of Applied Mathematics, Imperial College London

² Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Imperial College London

c.doebeli22@imperial.ac.uk

Keywords

reduced-order modeling, moment matching, invariant manifolds, Galerkin methods, global polynomial approximation

1 Introduction

Complex large-scale dynamical systems are ubiquitous in control engineering, and provide a natural modeling framework in many different physical applications. The large state dimension of these models makes analysis, simulation, and control computationally challenging, which is often known as the “curse of dimensionality.” Reduced-order modeling (ROM) aims to construct low-dimensional models that preserve important characteristics of the original system while significantly reducing computational cost.

This work focuses on nonlinear model reduction using moment matching for nonlinear dynamical systems whose inputs are generated by a low-dimensional exogenous signal generator system. Under certain assumptions, the steady-state behaviour of the interconnected system is characterized by an invariant manifold associated with the solution of a “Sylvester-like” system of nonlinear partial differential equations (PDEs) [2]. Approximating this manifold provides a way to construct reduced-order models that reproduce the steady-state response of the full-order system [1].

2 Main Contribution

We propose a procedure for the numerical approximation of the invariance PDE arising in nonlinear moment matching. While many theoretical descriptions of reduced-order modeling by moment matching exist, there is a gap in the literature in developing computational methods for approximating the invariance equation for nonlinear moment matching. This work explicitly develops a computational method to achieve these goals in high-dimensional systems.

We implement a Galerkin spectral method to find approximate solutions to the invariance PDE system by expanding the solution through a basis of globally supported functions and using a Newton iteration on the coefficients. We use these solutions to construct a reduced-order model to achieve moment matching for the interconnected system.

We demonstrate the method’s efficacy on systems with state dimension of order 1000 driven by both linear and nonlinear signal generators.

We show that the resulting reduced-order models accurately reproduce the steady-state trajectories of the full-order system while embedding the dynamics in a much lower-dimensional space. Comparisons to classical linear model reduction techniques demonstrate improved accuracy at the same reduced dimension.

3 Conclusions

The proposed Galerkin-based framework provides a practical numerical tool for solving invariance equations arising in nonlinear moment matching. It enables the reduction of high-dimensional systems while preserving steady-state behaviour. Beyond model reduction, the same invariance PDE formulation can be applied in other control areas such as output regulation, and immersion and invariance.

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When beliefs about reality influence reality—May ML result in sticking in belief-distorted Nash equilibria?

Agnieszka Wiszniewska-Matyszek¹

¹ University of Warsaw, Poland

agnese@mimuw.edu.pl

Keywords

distorted information, belief-distorted Nash equilibrium, multistage and repeated games, dynamic games, Nash equilibrium, Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Consider multiple agents optimizing in a dynamic environment changing in response to their joint choices. There is no precise theoretical description how specific agent's decision influences the environment, so the model is built by ML using past data about decisions and their dynamic consequences on the environment level. One example is a stock exchange, when past prices, volumes and real data from various sectors of economy can be analyzed together. This results in expected price trajectories of shares as an unknown function of on the past and some current data. This may neglect the fact that prices of shares are defined by only by players orders. So, if players believe the prices will rise, they will rise. Another example is bank run. Similarly, overfishing in a common fishery if users expect it to be depleted soon.

In all of them, there is a vicious circle, starting from erroneous prediction neglecting the fact that the model produced by ML is used in optimization, and closed by the fact that the results of optimization given the erroneous prediction confirm this prediction.

2 Main contribution

There is an equilibrium-like concept that can be applied to such real life problems in which players do not have perfect information about the game they play, so they base their decisions on ML that analyses data without taking into account the resulting feedback. This is the concept of belief-distorted Nash equilibrium (BDNE), a solution concept for dynamic games with distorted information. It joins dynamic optimization given prediction based on past data (historically called *beliefs*) and the fact the beliefs cannot be falsified during the play if agents/players best-respond to them.

The questions that are designed to answer to are as follows.

- Can beliefs of players about future values of some variables being results of players choices cause this future values behave according to their beliefs?
- Can it happen if it is against the objective knowledge about e.g. the dynamics of the system?
- Can such players' behaviour be sustainable even if it does not lead to Nash or correlated equilibrium?
- What is the mechanism?
- Can such beliefs be self-verifying? Is it possible that rational players believe they play a Nash equilibrium?
- How to identify such a situation.

The general idea behind BDNE is similar to all the imperfect information concepts in game theory: players form some beliefs, they best respond to those beliefs (and, possibly, some other parameters) and if their beliefs are not falsified, there is no need to update them.

It is worth noting that is also the idea behind scientific research in the case when agents use that research results for their optimization which, in turn, influences results of consequent research: an ML

model by is formulated based on past data to be used by the players in their optimization, agents optimize given the assumed model and if the subsequent observations do not contradict the model, it is often regarded as a correct model of reality. The fact that agents' behaviour resulting from assuming a certain model influences those observations is not perceived by the agents, so profiles that are not Nash equilibria can be sustained and false model about reality can be regarded as true.

The theoretical concept was introduced in Wiszniewska-Matyszek [3, 4], while an application in [2]. The concepts, after a slight generalization, was also applied to modelling stock exchange in Wiszniewska-Matyszek [1].

3 Conclusions

In this paper, I presented potential risk of sticking at a BDNE if using ML for specifying models used afterwards for optimization by many agents. BDNE means that data analysis could have returned a misspecified model of the control problem of the agents, but this cannot be detected as long as the agents optimize given this model.

It is worth noting that this is also the general idea behind scientific research in the case when agents use that research results for their optimization which, in turn, influences results of consequent research: a model is formulated (which is used by the agents in their optimization), agents optimize given the assumed model and if the subsequent observations do not contradict the model, it is often regarded as a correct model of reality. The fact that agents' behaviour resulting from assuming a certain model influences those observations is not perceived by the agents, so profiles that are not Nash equilibria can be sustained and false model about reality can be regarded as true.

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Opponent-Aware Soft Q-Learning

Mario Chacón-Falcón^{1, 2}, David Rios Insua¹

¹Institute of Mathematical Sciences (ICMAT-CSIC)

²Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Escuela de Doctorado

`mario.chacon@icmat.es`, `david.rios@icmat.es`

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Opponent Modeling, Soft Q-Learning, Adversarial Risk Analysis, Markov Games, Multi-Agent Systems

1 Introduction

While reinforcement learning (RL) has achieved superhuman performance in complex single-agent domains [10, 8], transitioning to multi-agent interactions introduces the challenge of non-stationary environments [2]. Classical game theory provides a rigorous framework for these interactions, but it typically relies on strong assumptions, such as common knowledge of rationality and payoffs, or the existence of a Nash Equilibrium [7]. However, in real world adversarial scenarios, opponents often behave sub-optimally or operate with distinct, unknown objectives.

Explicitly modelling the opponent offers a robust alternative. Adversarial Risk Analysis (ARA) [1] provides a Bayesian decision-analytic approach by modelling the goals, beliefs, and reasoning of the opponent. However, integrating ARA into modern RL is computationally challenging. Previous attempts, such as Threatened Markov Decision Processes (TMDPs) [5], successfully conceptualized these interactions but relied on the restrictive assumption of a fully observable opponent’s reward. To overcome this limitation, we bridge ARA and Maximum Entropy RL [6]. We introduce a novel opponent-aware learning algorithm and establish a principled framework for inferring the opponent’s unobserved rewards directly from their behaviour.

2 Opponent Aware Soft Q-Learning

Our main contribution is the development of opponent aware soft Q-Learning within the TMDP framework. By demonstrating that Maximum Entropy RL is a special case of ARA with Fully Probabilistic Design (FPD), we derive an energy-based policy for the adversary. This allows us to handle the opponent’s rationality strictly from a Bayesian perspective while preserving the computational advantages of modern RL.

Specifically, we modify the standard maximum entropy objective [4] for the supported agent. In addition to the entropy of the agent’s own policy, we incorporate the entropy of the opponent’s policy directly into the objective function. Intuitively, this serves as an information seeking bonus, rewarding the exploration of states where the entropy of the opponent’s policy is highest. This motivates the agent to actively probe the opponent in ambiguous scenarios to uncover its true intentions.

Under this formulation, we prove two key results:

1. **Optimal Policy:** The optimal policy for the supported agent is given by a soft-Boltzmann distribution over a robust, opponent-aware soft Q-value function.
2. **Convergence:** The proposed opponent-aware soft Q-value operator is a contraction mapping under the infinity norm. This guarantees convergence to a unique set of optimal Q-values via iterative updates.

To handle strategic adversaries, we first augment our foundational algorithm with recursive reasoning by integrating the level- k thinking paradigm [3]. Furthermore, we extend our methodology to explicitly infer the opponent’s latent objectives directly from their actions, not assuming observable rewards. Specifically, we employ Bayesian filtering to continuously fit and update a probabilistic model (such as a Gaussian mixture model) over the opponent’s unknown rewards. By coupling this dynamic belief with a learned

transition model, the agent can simulate offline interactions. This model-based approach allows the agent to safely anticipate how the opponent might adapt, training its own policy without the need for risky trial-and-error in the real environment. Finally, we sketch how this entire framework may be extended to a generalized Bayesian approach [9] to scale to high-dimensional, complex state spaces.

3 Conclusions

We introduce a novel opponent aware Soft Q-Learning framework that successfully merges the rigorous uncertainty quantification of Adversarial Risk Analysis with the computational structure of Maximum Entropy RL. By explicitly incorporating opponent entropy into the objective function, leveraging level- k recursive reasoning, and dropping the restrictive assumption of observable opponent rewards, we provide a convergent algorithm capable of safe, robust adaptation in uncertain adversarial Markov games.

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Cone-Constrained Neural Networks for Structured Learning and Control

Krzysztof Rykaczewski¹, Grzegorz Gabor¹, Michał Balicki¹, Piotr Przymus¹

¹Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland

krykaczewski@gmail.com, ggabor@mat.umk.pl, michal.balicki.job@gmail.com,
piotr.przymus@mat.umk.pl

Keywords

cone-constrained neural networks, monotone operators, fixed-point theory, structured dynamical systems, control-oriented machine learning

1 Introduction

Neural networks with structural constraints are attractive in applications where stability, interpretability, and domain consistency matter as much as predictive performance. This is particularly relevant in inverse problems, signal processing, and control, where learned maps are often used as iterative state-update operators, estimators, or structured surrogates of dynamical systems. A classical example is the use of nonnegative weights, which promotes additive representations and order preservation, but can also make the model overly restrictive and lead to degenerate dynamics. In many physically constrained systems, however, the relevant geometry is richer than the positive orthant. This motivates neural architectures defined over general convex cones, where one can preserve order-theoretic structure without enforcing strict componentwise nonnegativity [1, 2, 3].

In this contribution, we present a general framework for neural networks whose layers are monotone and scalable with respect to closed, convex, pointed, and solid cones. This extends previous nonnegative constructions to a broader class of geometries, in particular second-order (“ice-cream”) cones, which provide a useful compromise between expressiveness and stability. From a control-theoretic perspective, the resulting architectures can be viewed as learnable constrained dynamical maps that preserve invariant cone-structured domains and admit analysis through fixed-point methods. The framework is especially relevant for autoencoders and iterative architectures, where repeated application of the network can be studied as a structured dynamical system.

2 Main contribution

We consider feedforward networks in which each layer maps between cone-structured domains,

$$f_i(x) = \sigma_i(W_i x + b_i), \quad f = f_m \circ \dots \circ f_1,$$

and impose three layerwise constraints: (i) the linear map preserves the cone, $W_i(K_{i-1}) \subseteq K_i$, (ii) the bias satisfies $b_i \in K_i$, and (iii) the activation is chosen to preserve both cone-monotonicity and cone-scalability. Under these assumptions, every layer is monotone and scalable with respect to the cone-induced partial order, and these properties are preserved under composition. As a result, the full network inherits a structured geometric behavior that is unavailable in unconstrained architectures.

The main theoretical benefit is that cone-constrained networks admit analysis via nonlinear Perron–Frobenius and fixed-point theory. In the autoencoder setting, this gives conditions under which the network remains inside the admissible domain during the whole computation and admits nontrivial fixed points. More broadly, the same perspective is relevant to control-oriented iterative schemes, where invariance, monotonicity, and controlled scaling are central to stability and equilibrium analysis. Importantly, replacing the nonnegative orthant by wider cones avoids the collapse typical of hard positivity constraints: instead of degenerating to a single trivial attractor, the network can sustain multiple equilibria while still enjoying monotonicity and controlled scaling.

To make the framework trainable in practice, we introduce a projection-based learning procedure. After each gradient step, the biases are projected onto the target cone, while weights are corrected toward the set of cone-preserving matrices using a stochastic residual projection. For second-order cones, pointwise projection has a closed form, making the method efficient and scalable in moderate and high dimensions.

We validate the approach on autoencoding tasks with geometric or physical priors, including MNIST reconstruction, angular power spectra in massive MIMO systems, and speech spectrogram reconstruction. Across these settings, cone-constrained autoencoders achieve reconstruction quality close to unconstrained baselines, while preserving structured intermediate representations and more robust output geometry. On MNIST, the proposed **ConeAE** preserves semantic latent organization and supports substantially richer fixed-point structure than clamping-based nonnegative models, which tend to collapse to a single attractor. On MIMO and audio tasks, cone constraints maintain physically meaningful outputs while remaining competitive in mean squared reconstruction error.

These results suggest that general cones provide a principled middle ground between fully unconstrained networks, which may be unstable or geometrically inconsistent, and strictly nonnegative models, which may be too rigid. Cone-preserving neural networks therefore offer a flexible route toward architectures that are theoretically tractable, practically trainable, and well aligned with structured learning, iterative inference, and control-oriented applications.

3 Conclusions

We propose a unified cone-based framework for constructing neural networks that are monotone, scalable, and amenable to fixed-point analysis beyond the positive orthant. The theory covers a broad class of convex cones, while the practical realization via second-order cones enables efficient training with projection-based updates. Empirically, cone-constrained autoencoders retain strong reconstruction performance and yield more structured and interpretable dynamics than hard nonnegative baselines. We believe this perspective opens promising directions for robust and geometry-aware deep learning in inverse problems, signal processing, and control.

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Deep Riemannian Control: Formally Verified Neural Observers and Controllers via Contraction Theory

Boukaf Mohamed¹, Zehor Belkhatir², Chadli Mohamed³, Laleg-Kirati Meriem-Taous¹

¹ Université Paris-Saclay, Inria, CIAMS, Gif-sur-Yvette, 91190, France.

² School of Electronics and Computer Science, University of Southampton, UK.

³ University Paris-Saclay, Univ Evry, IBISC, France.

mohamed.boukaf@inria.fr, Z.Belkhatir@soton.ac.uk, taous-meriem.laleg@inria.fr,
mohammed.chadli@universite-paris-saclay.fr

Keywords

Contracting systems, nonlinear systems, observer design, output-feedback control.

1 Introduction

Contraction theory provides a rigorous geometric framework for global stability analysis by guaranteeing the differential exponential convergence of arbitrary system trajectories [1]. This property can be universally exploited for both state estimation—forcing an observer’s trajectory to track the hidden state—and control synthesis, where Control Contraction Metrics (CCMs) shape the closed-loop Riemannian manifold to ensure exponential reference tracking [2]. However, achieving global observer-based state-feedback requires solving infinite-dimensional Matrix Differential Inequalities (MDPIs) simultaneously for both the observer and the controller. The standard approach relies on Sum-of-Squares (SOS) programming [4], which restricts the metric and gains to polynomial forms and solves a hierarchy of semidefinite programs. This approach scales poorly with state dimension and cannot handle general nonlinear architectures. While deep neural networks have emerged to parameterize these intractable metrics over finite discrete sets [3], safe physical deployment demands rigorous continuous-time guarantees. In this work, we propose a Formally Verified Deep Riemannian Control framework for nonlinear observer-based state-feedback dynamic trajectory tracking.

2 Main contribution

Consider a continuous-time, nonlinear, control-affine system with partially observed states:

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x) + g(x)u + d(t), \quad y(t) = h(x) + \nu(t), \quad (1)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state evolving on a compact set, $u(t) \in \mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ is the control input, $y(t) \in \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ is the measured output, $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a bounded external disturbance satisfying $\|d(t)\| \leq \bar{d}$, and $\nu(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is measurement noise with $\|\nu(t)\| \leq \bar{\nu}$. The drift field $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, input matrix $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, and measurement map $h : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$ are assumed at least \mathcal{C}^2 on \mathcal{X} . Let $(x^*(t), u^*(t))$ denote a dynamically feasible reference trajectory satisfying $\dot{x}^* = f(x^*) + g(x^*)u^*$ for all $t \geq 0$. The true state $x(t)$ is *inaccessible*; only the noisy partial measurement $y(t)$ is available. We define a nonlinear state observer as a copy of the nominal dynamics augmented by a learned correction:

$$\dot{\hat{x}}(t) = f(\hat{x}) + g(\hat{x})u + k_o(\hat{x}, y; \theta_k), \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state estimate and $k_o : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a nonlinear observer gain parameterized by a deep neural network with weights θ_k . The gain must satisfy the **consistency condition**: $k_o(x, h(x); \theta_k) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$, ensuring that the correction vanishes when the estimate is exact. The contraction of the observer is certified by a Riemannian metric $M_o(x; \theta_m) \in \mathcal{S}_{++}^n$, also parameterized as a neural network. The virtual system associated with the observer is $\dot{q} = f(q) + g(q)u + k_o(q, y)$, with closed-loop Jacobian $J_o(q, y, u) = A(q, u) + \frac{\partial k_o}{\partial q}(q, y)$, where $A(q, u) = \frac{\partial f}{\partial q} + \sum_{i=1}^m u_i \frac{\partial g_i}{\partial q}$. The observer MDPI requires [2]:

$$Q_o(x, y, u, \theta_m, \theta_k) := \dot{M}_o(x, \theta_m) + \text{He}(M_o(x, \theta_m)J_o(x, y, u, \theta_k)) + 2\lambda_o M_o(x, \theta_m) \preceq 0, \quad (3)$$

to hold for all $(x, u, y) \in \mathcal{S} := \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{Y}$, where $\text{He}(X) = X + X^\top$ and $\lambda_o > 0$ is the observer contraction rate. The tracking controller integrates a neural differential gain $K_c(x; \theta_{k_c}) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ along the minimal geodesic $\gamma_c(s, t)$ connecting $x^*(t)$ to $\hat{x}(t)$:

$$u(\hat{x}, t, \theta_{k_c}) = u^*(t) + \int_0^1 K_c(\gamma_c(s, t), \theta_{k_c}) \frac{\partial \gamma_c}{\partial s}(s, t) ds. \quad (4)$$

A second neural Riemannian metric $M_c(x; \theta_{m_c}, \theta_{k_c}) \in \mathcal{S}_{++}^n$ certifies contraction of the closed-loop virtual system with Jacobian $J_c(q, u) = A(q, u) + g(q)K_c(q)$. The controller MDPI requires:

$$Q_c(x, u, \theta_{m_c}, \theta_{k_c}) := \dot{M}_c(x, \theta_{m_c}) + \text{He}(M_c(x, \theta_{m_c})J_c(x, u, \theta_{k_c})) + 2\lambda_c M_c(x, \theta_{m_c}) \preceq 0, \quad (5)$$

to hold for all $(x, u) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{U}$, where $\lambda_c > 0$ is the controller contraction rate. Both metrics M_o, M_c and gains k_o, K_c are parameterized as deep residual networks with Tanh activations. The metrics are constrained to be uniformly positive definite via Cholesky factorization: $M(x; \theta) = L_\theta(x)L_\theta(x)^\top + \epsilon I$, where L_θ is lower-triangular and $\epsilon > 0$, guaranteeing $\underline{m} \geq \epsilon > 0$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Training proceeds entirely offline, without reference trajectories. Batches of states $x_i \sim \mathcal{X}$ and inputs $u_i \sim \mathcal{U}$ are sampled uniformly, and the MDPIs (3)–(5) are enforced pointwise with a strict robustness margin $q > 0$. A margin $2q$ is explicitly enforced, as required by the formal verification below. A global training strategy ensures that the networks simultaneously learn a globally contracting vector field and a physically consistent observer correction. We now state the unified result combining formal verification of the neural MDPIs with the cascaded ISS bound for the observer-based controller.

Theorem 1 (Formally Verified Cascaded ISS). *Consider system (1) with observer (2) and controller (4). Let $M_o(x; \theta_m), k_o(x, y; \theta_k), M_c(x; \theta_{m_c}), K_c(x; \theta_{k_c})$ be neural networks described before, and let $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathcal{S}$ be the training dataset forming a finite r -cover of the compact operational space \mathcal{S} , i.e., $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \bigcup_{s_i \in \mathcal{D}} B(s_i, r)$. Denote by L_{Q_o} and L_{Q_c} the global Lipschitz constants of the MDPI matrices Q_o and Q_c , and by $q_o, q_c > 0$ the respective robustness margins enforced during training. Suppose the metrics satisfy uniform eigenvalue bounds $\underline{m}_o I \preceq M_o \preceq \bar{m}_o I$ and $\underline{m}_c I \preceq M_c \preceq \bar{m}_c I$ on \mathcal{X} , then: $L_{Q_o} \leq [\sqrt{n}(L_{M_o}(B_{\nabla f} + B_u B_{\nabla g} + B_{\nabla k_o}) + B_v H_{M_o}^{NN}) + 2\bar{m}_o(L_{\nabla f} + B_u L_{\nabla g} + L_{\nabla k_o}) + 2L_{M_o}(B_{\nabla f} + B_u B_{\nabla g} + B_{\nabla k_o} + \lambda_o)]$ and $L_{Q_c} \leq [\sqrt{n}(L_{M_c}(B_{\nabla f} + B_u B_{\nabla g} + B_g B_{K_c}) + B_v H_{M_c}^{NN}) + 2\bar{m}_c(L_{\nabla f} + B_u L_{\nabla g} + B_g L_{K_c} + B_{K_c} L_{\nabla g}) + 2L_{M_c}(B_{\nabla f} + B_u B_{\nabla g} + B_g B_{K_c} + \lambda_c)]$, where B_f is the supremum of the function f over its domain, and L_f its Lipschitz constant. **(I) Formal Verification.** If the training loss converges to zero, so that $Q_o(s_i) \preceq -2q_o I$ and $Q_c(s_i) \preceq -2q_c I$ for all $s_i \in \mathcal{D}$, and if the grid density satisfies: $r < \min\left(\frac{q_o}{L_{Q_o}}, \frac{q_c}{L_{Q_c}}\right)$, then the contraction conditions hold strictly for all unseen points: $Q_o(s) \preceq -q_o I \prec 0$ for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$, and $Q_c(x, u) \preceq -q_c I \prec 0$ for all $(x, u) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{U}$. **(II) Cascaded ISS Bound.** Under the verified contraction conditions from (I), with $\|d(t)\| \leq \bar{d}$, $\|\nu(t)\| \leq \bar{\nu}$, and $\lambda_o \neq \lambda_c$, define the condition numbers $c_o = \sqrt{\bar{m}_o/\underline{m}_o}$, $c_c = \sqrt{\bar{m}_c/\underline{m}_c}$, the coupling constant $\beta = B_g B_{K_c}$ where $B_g = \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \|g(x)\|$ and $B_{K_c} = \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \|K_c(x)\|$, the Lipschitz constant L_{k_y} of k_o in its measurement argument, and $\bar{D} = \bar{d} + L_{k_y} \bar{\nu}$. Then:*

Observer. The estimation error $e_o(t) = x(t) - \hat{x}(t)$ satisfies:

$$\|e_o(t)\| \leq c_o \|e_o(0)\| e^{-\lambda_o t} + \frac{c_o \bar{D}}{\lambda_o} (1 - e^{-\lambda_o t}). \quad (6)$$

Controller. The physical tracking error $e_c(t) = x(t) - x^*(t)$ satisfies:

$$\|e_c(t)\| \leq c_c \|e_c(0)\| e^{-\lambda_c t} + \frac{c_c \beta}{\lambda_o - \lambda_c} \left(c_o \|e_o(0)\| - \frac{c_o \bar{D}}{\lambda_o} \right) (e^{-\lambda_c t} - e^{-\lambda_o t}) + \frac{c_c}{\lambda_c} \left(\frac{\beta c_o \bar{D}}{\lambda_o} + \bar{d} \right) (1 - e^{-\lambda_c t}). \quad (7)$$

Asymptotic Tube. As $t \rightarrow \infty$, the tracking error is confined to:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|e_c(t)\| \leq \frac{c_c}{\lambda_c} \left(\bar{d} + \frac{B_g B_{K_c} c_o}{\lambda_o} \bar{D} \right). \quad (8)$$

3 Conclusions

This work presents a certifiable framework for nonlinear trajectory tracking under partial, noisy measurements. By parameterizing Riemannian metrics and differential gains as neural networks trained

offline against contraction MDPIs, we bypass SOS scalability limitations while retaining formal guarantees through Lipschitz-based grid verification. Theorem 1 unifies a grid density condition certifying contraction continuously from discrete data with an explicit cascaded ISS bound quantifying the steady-state tube as a function of disturbance, noise, contraction rates, and network constants. Simulation on an underactuated flexible-joint robot arm with a single noisy measurement validates the predicted exponential convergence into bounded tubes.

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Qualitative analysis of degenerate evolution equations arising when modelling neural, electrical and gas networks

Maria Filipkovska¹,

¹ B. Verkin Institute for Low Temperature Physics and Engineering of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

filipkovskaya@ilt.kharkov.ua, maria.filipk@gmail.com

Keywords

abstract differential-algebraic equation, partial differential-algebraic equation, global solvability, qualitative analysis, network

1 Introduction

We will deal with degenerate evolution equations in Banach spaces, which are a convenient abstract form of writing partial differential equations as well as systems of partial or ordinary differential equations (PDEs or ODEs) and algebraic equations. These equations are also called degenerate differential equations and abstract differential-algebraic equations (ADAEs). Such equations in finite-dimensional spaces are usually called DAEs, algebraic-differential equations and descriptor systems. Systems contain PDEs and algebraic equations are often called partial differential-algebraic equations (PDAEs).

Degenerate evolution equations are used to describe mathematical models in control theory, neuromorphic computing, radio electronics, robotics, economics, chemical kinetics, gas industry and other fields. It is well known that they are used in modelling neural, electrical and transport (for example, gas transport) networks.

We will deal with the degenerate evolution equation (ADAE) of the form

$$\frac{d}{dt}[Ax] + Bx = f(t, x), \quad (1)$$

where A and B are closed linear operators from a Banach space X into a Banach space Y with domains D_A and D_B respectively, $D = D_A \cap D_B \neq \{0\}$ is a lineal, $\overline{D_A} = \overline{D_B} = X$, the range of A is closed and $f \in C(\mathbb{R}_+ \times D, Y)$, $\mathbb{R}_+ = [0, \infty)$. The operator A , as well as B , can be degenerate. According to the DAE/ADAE terminology, the ADAE (1) is called semilinear.

The pencil $P(\lambda) = \lambda A + B$, associated with the linear part (left-hand side) of equation (1), is called characteristic. It is assumed that the pencil $P(\lambda)$ is regular for all λ from some neighborhood of the infinity and the point $\lambda = \infty$ is a pole of the resolvent $R(\lambda) = (\lambda A + B)^{-1}$ of order r or a removable singularity of $R(\lambda)$ (if the singularity is removable, we will say that it is a pole of order 0). This is equivalent to the fact that the resolvent $\widehat{R}(\mu) = (A + \mu B)^{-1}$ of the pencil $\widehat{P}(\mu) = A + \mu B$ has a pole of order ν at the point $\mu = 0$, where $\nu = r + 1$ if $\lambda = \infty$ is the pole of $R(\lambda)$ of order r and $\nu = 1$ if $\lambda = \infty$ is a removable singularity. Then $P(\lambda)$ is called a *regular pencil of index ν* ($\nu \in \mathbb{N}$).

Most of research on the degenerate evolution equations (ADAEs) is related to the study of their local solvability (see, e.g., [6, 2, 1]). We will present conditions for the global solvability, as well as conditions of the global boundedness and the blow-up of solutions of equation (1) with the regular characteristic pencil of arbitrarily high index. From a practical point of view, it is important not only to prove that a solution exists on some local interval, but also to determine the maximal interval of its existence. If the solution is global (i.e., it exists on an arbitrarily large time interval), then the corresponding real-world system will operate over a sufficiently long duration without interruption. If the solution is blow-up in finite time (i.e., it exists on a finite time interval and is unbounded), then the operation of the corresponding real system will be interrupted. For example, the disruption of a semiconductor is described as the blow-up of a solution of an appropriate initial-value or initial-boundary-value problem.

2 Main contribution

Theorems on the maximal interval of existence and uniqueness of solutions, on the existence and boundedness of global solutions (Lagrange stability) and on the blow-up of solutions (Lagrange instability) of the ADAE (1) with the regular pencil of arbitrarily high index have been obtained in [4]. Some of these theorems will be discussed in the talk. The global solvability and Lagrange stability/instability for equation (1) with the regular pencil of index not higher than 1 in finite-dimensional spaces was studied, e.g., in [3, 5]. When proving the theorems (see [4]), global implicit function theorems and the methods obtained by extending Lyapunov's second method are used. Before proving the theorems, the ADAE are reduced to a system of explicit differential and algebraic equations by using spectral projectors. The number of equations of the system depends on the index of the characteristic pencil of the ADAE.

We will also consider certain mathematical models of electrical circuits, including an electrical network coupled to a memristor, and a gas flow in the form of the degenerate evolution equation (1). In particular, we will discuss the dynamics of an electrical circuit described by the DAE (1) with the regular pencil of index 3. The memristor is modeled by the PDE system consisting of the drift–diffusion equations for the densities of electrons, holes and oxygen vacancies and the Poisson equation for an electric potential. This system coupled to the DAE describing the electrical network forms a PDAE which will be considered in the talk. Generally, memristors are promising candidates for application in high-density computer memories and building synapses and neurons in neuromorphic computing. Finally, we will consider the model of transient gas flow in a pipe, which consists of the Euler equations and the equation of state for gases for constant temperature.

3 Conclusions

The talk provides an approach to the study of the existence and qualitative behavior of solutions of PDEs, DAEs and PDAEs which can be represented as the degenerate evolution equation (ADAE) with the regular characteristic pencil of arbitrarily high index. The results of the qualitative analysis of the mathematical models for the electrical circuit, memristor device (coupled with an electrical circuit) and gas flow, which demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach, are presented.

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Linear quadratic control of nonlinear systems with Koopman operator learning and the Nyström method

Edoardo Caldarelli¹, Antoine Chatalic², Adrià Colomé³, Cesare Molinari⁴, Carlos Ocampo-Martinez^{3, 5},
Carme Torras³, Lorenzo Rosasco^{1, 4}

¹ Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genoa, Italy

² CNRS, Univ. Grenoble-Alpes, GIPSA-lab, France

³ Institut de Robòtica i Informàtica Industrial, CSIC – UPC, Barcelona, Spain

⁴ MaLga Center – DIBRIS – Università di Genova, Genoa, Italy

⁵ Automatic Control Department (ESAT), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTECH, Spain

edoardo.caldarelli@iit.it

Keywords

Koopman operator, kernel methods, Nyström method, linear quadratic regulator, data-driven methods

1 Introduction

Nonlinear dynamical systems are ubiquitous, and pose a great challenge in terms of system identification and control. A powerful approach to deal with nonlinear dynamical systems is provided by the *Koopman operator* framework [3, 1, 5, 2]. In this approach, the nonlinear dynamical system is transformed through a set of nonlinear functions, called *observables*, so that the dynamics of the transformed states are *linear*, and can be used to reconstruct the states of the system.

The Koopman operator, at the basis of this technique, was originally introduced in the context of autonomous dynamical systems [3]. However, as shown in the seminal work of Korda et al. [4], the Koopman operator formulation allows to apply linear control techniques, which are well understood and efficient to compute. Specifically, the control input can be included in the Koopman framework by extending the state space to include the control input as an additional state of the system.

2 Main contribution

A key challenge to apply the Koopman operator approach is to choose the suitable space of observable functions, both with and without considering the control input [4]. In this talk, we will show how the Koopman operator framework can be combined with kernel methods to effectively control nonlinear dynamical systems.

While kernel methods have typically large computational requirements, we will show how random subspaces (specifically, the so-called Nyström approximation) can be used to achieve huge computational savings while preserving accuracy.

Our main technical contribution is deriving theoretical guarantees on the effect of the Nyström approximation. More precisely, we study the linear quadratic regulator problem, showing that the approximated Riccati operator converges at the rate $m^{-1/2}$, and the regulator objective, for the associated solution of the optimal control problem, converges at the rate m^{-1} , where m is the random subspace size.

Theoretical findings are complemented by numerical experiments corroborating our results. Specifically, our simulations encompass both proof-of-concept and more complex dynamics, stemming from the problem of robotic manipulation of deformable objects.

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Learning from data via overparameterization

Cesare Molinari^{1,3}, Cristian Vega⁴, Hippolyte Labarrière^{2,3}, Lorenzo Rosasco^{2,3}, Silvia Villa^{1,3}

¹DIMA, Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy

²DIBRIS, Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy

³Malga - Machine Learning Genoa Center, Italy

⁴Instituto de Alta investigación (IAI), Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile

cecio.molinari@gmail.com

Keywords

Optimization, Machine Learning, Optimal Control, Reparametrization

1 Introduction

Solving data-driven problems requires defining complex models and fitting them on data, neural networks being a motivating example. The fitting procedure can be seen as an optimization problem, which is often non-convex, and hence optimization guarantees are hard to derive. Gradient-based methods successfully train highly overparameterized models in practice, even though the associated optimization problems are markedly non-convex. Understanding the mechanisms that make such methods effective has become a central problem in modern optimization. An opportunity is provided by viewing the model of interest as a redundant re-parameterization—an overparameterization—of some simpler model for which optimization results are easier to achieve. In this talk, after formalizing the above idea, we review some recent results (see, for instance, [1]) and derive new ones.

2 Main contributions

In particular, we consider the gradient flow of some classes of linear overparameterization and show they correspond to suitable mirror flow on the original parameters. Our main contribution relates to the study of the latter, for which we establish well-posedness and convergence. The results yield insight on the role of overparameterization for implicit regularization and constrained optimization. Then we focus on the case of Deep Diagonal Linear Networks, see [2]. These are multilayer architectures with a reparameterization that preserves convexity in the effective parameter, while inducing a nontrivial geometry in the optimization landscape. Under mild initialization conditions, we show that gradient flow on the layer parameters induces a mirror-flow dynamic in the effective parameter space. This structural insight yields explicit convergence guarantees, including exponential decay of the loss under a Polyak-Lojasiewicz condition, and clarifies how the parametrization and initialization scale govern the training speed. Overall, our results demonstrate that deep diagonal over-parameterizations, despite their apparent complexity, can endow standard gradient methods with well-behaved and interpretable optimization dynamics.

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Transcription of Czech administrative records written in Kurrent script into Latin script using machine learning, OCR, and AI

Tomáš Martínek¹

¹ Czech University of Life Sciences Prague

`martinekt@pef.czu.cz`

Keywords

Czech, kurrent, HTR, OCR, machine learning

1 Introduction

Kurrent, a German neo-Gothic cursive script, has been used in the Czech lands since the 16th century. It spread in the 1770s, when it replaced Czech neo-Gothic cursive script thanks to school reforms. Most handwritten official, church, and company records and other texts were written in Kurrent. In Czech texts, it was replaced by humanistic script around 1850, while in German texts it continued until the Nazi reform of 1941 [8].

Kurrent was the standard for shorthand in archives, registers, and company agendas—unofficially in German-speaking areas until 1945. In Czech texts, its use declined earlier due to the national revival, but it persisted longer in industrial and administrative records. The ongoing digitization of archives by scanning printed records makes a wealth of data available to the public, which, if interpreted correctly, can be used for management decision-making even today. Of particular interest are, for example, records of the production of large estates and other companies, land registers, which may also be referred to in existing records and contracts, and others. Digitized records are gradually being made available to the public through state digital archives [11]. Thanks to current technologies, it is possible to add additional metadata to digitized images using OCR, machine learning, and the rapidly advancing development of artificial intelligence.

2 Main contribution

In order to facilitate the manual transcription of records written in Kurrent, we have created an online tool `Kurent.pridat.eu` [1]. It is an aggregator of fonts previously used for writing in the Czech lands. Specifically, the online keyboard for facilitating the manual transcription of Kurrent into Latin script contains font families such as `DeutscheKurrent`, `Kurent18Start`, `Kurent18Text`, `CoentgenKanzley`, `CoentgenKanzleyAufrecht`, `GLSuetterlin`, `KurrentKupferstich`, `VolkRedis`, `WiegelKurrent`, `WiegelKurrentMedium`, and we are preparing others with a focus on humanistic fonts. With this tool, even a lay user should be able to transcribe a handwritten text in one of the periods of Kurrent into Latin script. Czech handwriting in Kurrent has its own specific characteristics compared to German handwriting. In addition, it is handwritten, and each writer has their own specific style of writing. All this makes it difficult to use only OCR and machine learning for the automated transcription of large numbers of records. Czech Kurrent often combines characters from German Kurrent and newer Czech humanistic cursive. The following image shows an example of how our online tool can help with transcription.

We are gradually creating a large amount of data for testing and machine learning by downloading selected publicly available photographs of records and manually transcribing them. For training purposes, it will be necessary to take into account the specifics of combining cursive and humanistic script [4]. In order to clarify the current quality of available tools for automatic transcription, we plan to perform formalized testing for the transcription of the same data, for example using Levenshtein distance [10][2].

Most of the original research was conducted at a time when AI was not at its current level. For example, a model specializing in the transcription of German-written cursive was created at the University of Bern [5]. At the University of Innsbruck, the `Transkribus` program [12] was developed to enable the

Figure 1: Transcription of an entry from the Book of Assets and Liabilities of the village of Vráž into a standardized font, which after transcription reads "Based on the submission of document no. 1063 of the Imperial-Royal District Court in Beroun dated March 18, 1869, a lien is placed on house no. 24 in Vráž." (own processing)

recognition of handwritten text, known as HTR - Handwritten text recognition [7]. The PERO OCR tool was also created as part of a joint project between the Moravian Library and the Brno University of Technology [6][9]. EXON, in collaboration with the University of West Bohemia, introduced the inkCapture tool [3]. In addition to specialized tools, transcription can also be handled by generative artificial intelligence models such as ChatGPT-5.4, Gemini 3.1 Pro, Claude Sonnet 4.6, Sonar, Kimi K2.5, Google Lens, and others. In our comparison, we want to focus on the available tools and their results in comparison with artificial intelligence models.

3 Conclusions

After obtaining relevant results from formalized testing, it will be appropriate to try basic training of available models on prepared transcribed data for machine learning and then repeat the testing. This should give us the results of the most suitable tool for transcribing Czech Kurrent and its possible further development. The goal is to create a new HTR model for the automatic transcription of Kurrent and other similar scripts using available AI tools and models, which will have the best results for transcribing Czech Kurrent and other scripts used in the Czech lands. This could subsequently enable the automated transcription of a large number of records and their use in existing business practices and elsewhere. The sub-goals are a more accurate description of the types of scripts and languages used in the Czech lands and their temporal differentiation.

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SIMONet: a deep learning framework for learning set-valued maps. Application to Control

Carlos J. García-Cervera^{1,2}, Mathieu Kessler³, Pablo Pedregal⁴, Francisco Periago³

¹ Department of Mathematics. University of California, Santa Barbara, USA

² BCAM, Basque Center for Applied Mathematics, Spain

² Department of Applied Mathematics and Statistics. Technical University of Cartagena, Spain

² Department of Mathematics. University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain

f.periago@upct.es

Keywords

Set-valued maps, Single input-multiple output neural networks, Universal approximation

1 Introduction

A number of neural network architectures have been proposed and thoroughly analyzed for the approximation of both (single-valued) functions and operators. For instance, under suitable assumptions, two-layer neural networks and deep operator networks satisfy the Universal Approximation Property [1, 2]. These results provide a solid mathematical foundation for their use in learning (single-valued) functions and operators that naturally arise in a wide range of control problems.

Not only do single-valued maps appear in control theory, but set-valued maps and operators also play a key role in mathematical control. Indeed, the mapping that assigns to each initial condition of a finite-dimensional control system its reachability set at a given final time is intrinsically set-valued. In infinite-dimensional settings, the same construction yields a set-valued operator acting between function spaces. It is therefore desirable to develop deep-learning architectures capable of approximating such set-valued operators.

This contribution aims at providing a first insight into this topic.

2 Main contribution

In this work we present a universal approximation result for multivalued mappings—both set-valued functions and set-valued operators—by means of a concrete architecture of set-valued neural networks that we call *Single Input Multiple Output Nets* (SIMONets).

Given a metric space (Y, d) , we measure distances between subsets of Y using the Hausdorff pseudometric, which becomes a true metric when restricted to the family $\mathcal{F}(Y)$ of closed subsets. Within this framework, we consider multivalued maps $F : X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(Y)$ defined on compact metric spaces and continuous in the Hausdorff sense.

Our main contribution shows that any such continuous multivalued map—whether defined pointwise on a compact domain X , or as an operator acting on a compact subset $V \subset C(K_1)$ with values in $\mathcal{F}(C(K_2))$ —can be uniformly approximated with arbitrary precision by SIMONets. In particular, when the images of the operator are convex and compact, we construct a SIMONet whose outputs remain uniformly close to those of the target mapping in the Hausdorff metric.

This result extends the universal approximation theorem of Chen & Chen (1993) to the multivalued setting and provides an explicit neural-network framework capable of approximating a broad class of continuous set-valued mappings arising in applications.

To illustrate the practical relevance of our abstract approximation results within Control Theory, we examine two representative control problems: one set in finite-dimensional dynamics and another in an infinite-dimensional framework. For each case, we analyze the corresponding set-valued mapping—or operator—that assigns to every initial state its reachable set at a given time horizon. These examples demonstrate how SIMONets can effectively approximate such mappings in both settings. Numerical simulations will be presented to highlight the performance and accuracy of the proposed approach.

3 Conclusions

We have established a universal approximation theorem for continuous multivalued mappings by introducing SIMONets, a concrete neural-network architecture capable of approximating both set-valued functions and set-valued operators in the Hausdorff metric. Our results extend classical universal approximation theory to the multivalued setting and provide an explicit constructive framework for approximating a wide family of continuous set-valued maps arising in applications. The ability of SIMONets to approximate operators with compact and convex images further broadens their scope, offering a flexible tool for problems in functional and infinite-dimensional spaces. The control-theoretic examples presented—both finite- and infinite-dimensional—illustrate the practical relevance of the theory and show how reachable-set mappings can be effectively approximated within this framework. These findings open the door to future developments in data-driven analysis and control of systems governed by inherently set-valued dynamics.

Detailed proofs of the results described above will appear in [3].

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Mathematical Modelling and Model-Based Control Design for Energy-Optimal Motion of Industrial Robots

Květoslav Belda

Department of Adaptive Systems

The Czech Academy of Sciences, The Institute of Information Theory and Automation
Pod Vodárenskou věží 1143/4, 182 00 Prague 8, Czech Republic

belda@utia.cas.cz

Keywords

mathematical modelling, model predictive control design, industrial manipulators, energy optimisation

1 Introduction

Current technological developments generally focus on reducing direct human labour through the massive deployment of automation and robotics, including decision-making processes using artificial intelligence. This implies a constantly increasing demand for a large number of new innovative applications that require an adequate amount of energy [10].

The paper deals with the possibilities and to propose strategies for reducing the energy demands of robot motion through designing optimal control and optimising motion trajectories. Robotics is a rapidly developing segment with the prospect of continuous growth. Reducing energy demands and optimising energy consumption are among the main challenges for today and in the future. The approach, offering to solve these challenges, is a model-based multi-step control. Thanks to the model, such control can efficiently generate the necessary control actions and thus can achieve energy-optimal motion of a robotic system [8]. Obtaining the model and its parameters is the main, fundamental issue/obstacle to application into practice.

The knowledge gap is identified in the insufficiency of interdisciplinary connection:

- *mathematical modelling* (physical analysis and synthesis of different physical model fundamentals: mechanical and electromechanical ones);
- *optimal control design* (control synthesis based on flexible, unified approaches; naturally occurring nonlinearities and uncertainties in controlled systems) [1];
- *parameter identification* (adaptivity and suppression of uncertainties of stochastic nature).

The effort is motivated by the need for adaptive control algorithms for complex systems. The term “complex” implies all aspects that influence the control design, such as suitable modelling procedures of mathematical-physical analysis, adequate compliance of applied mathematical models with real controlled systems, appropriate reference planning and its proper time-parametrisation [6],[2].

Testing and validation of our new theoretical findings is underway considering and using the class of real nonlinear dynamic robotic systems with our own developed drive control units connected to the structural elements of robots [5].

2 Main contribution

Aim is to contribute to solution of this problem/obstacle in an original way on several levels: systematic multi-physics modelling leading to models based on available ideal design data and refinement of these models by experimental identification methods, including detection and reduction of critical inaccuracies of parameters [9], [7]. From the robots point of view, this concerns the global level of control of the entire robotic structure (kinematics and dynamics of moving masses of robot elements/bodies) and the local level of control of particular drives (electric motors) [3]. The described arrangement leads to the idea to design a unified algorithmic strategy based on model predictive control [4]. Such an idea seems straightforward and already solved. However, in detail, it lacks a solution to the mutual influence of the global and local levels, where their dynamics differ significantly. The possible solution can lead to the complete overcoming of the current conventional, mostly empirically designed control approaches.

3 Conclusion

The article briefly outlines a possible direction for future developments that should reduce energy consumption in industrial robotic applications. A unified approach based on predictive control is proposed, which, thanks to information about the controlled object – robotic system, will only design as much energy as is actually needed for the robot’s motion.

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Concentration phenomena of self-attention dynamics

Albert Alcalde¹, Leon Bungert², Tim Roith³, Konstantin Riedl⁴,

¹ University of Erlangen

² University of Würzburg

³ Technical University of Munich

⁴ University of Oxford

leon.bungert@uni-wuerzburg.de

Keywords

interacting particle systems, self-attention, consensus-based optimization

1 Introduction

In this talk I will speak about concentration phenomena of self-attention transformers in the regimes of infinitely many layers and tokens. The dynamics are described by the Fokker–Planck equation

$$\partial_t \rho_t^\beta(x) = -\operatorname{div}\left(\rho_t^\beta(x) P_x V \mathfrak{m}_\beta[\rho_t^\beta](x)\right), \quad (t, x) \in [0, T] \times \mathbb{S}^{d-1}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{S}^{d-1} := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : |x| = 1\}$ is the sphere in \mathbb{R}^d , $T > 0$ is a time horizon, $P_x : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, $y \mapsto y - \langle x, y \rangle x$ is the projection onto $T_x \mathbb{S}^{d-1}$, and

$$\mathfrak{m}_\beta[\rho_t^\beta](x) := \frac{\int_{\mathbb{S}^{d-1}} e^{\beta \langle B y, x \rangle} y \, d\rho_t^\beta(y)}{\int_{\mathbb{S}^{d-1}} e^{\beta \langle B y, x \rangle} \, d\rho_t^\beta(y)} \quad (2)$$

involves the inverse heat parameter $\beta > 0$. The matrices $V, B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ contain learned parameters and are assumed to be constant in time. In [1] it was shown that for $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ solutions of (1) converge to solutions of a linear PDE, the solutions of which concentrate as $T \rightarrow \infty$ on the dominating eigendirections of the matrix VB^\top .

2 Main contribution

In our work we will quantify these results by exploiting a striking similarity between (1) and the so-called polarized consensus-based optimization (CBO) method from [2] for global optimization. Using a CBO-inspired analysis building on [3] we give explicit bounds for the Wasserstein-2 distance of the solution of (1) for finite $\beta > 0$ and the pushforward probability measure $\Pi_\# \rho_0$. Here, the map $\Pi : \mathbb{S}^{d-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^{d-1}$ is given by $\Pi(x) := \frac{P_E x}{|P_E x|}$ where P_E is the projection onto the dominating eigenspace E of VB^\top . The bound scales like

$$W_2(\rho_t^\beta, \Pi_\# \rho_0) \lesssim e^{CT} \sqrt{\frac{\log \beta}{\beta}} + e^{-\gamma t},$$

where $C > 0$ depends on the matrices V, B and $\gamma > 0$ is the spectral gap of VB^\top . The first term originates from an application of a quantified Laplace principle to (2), and the second term reflects the convergence of the limit equation as $\beta \rightarrow \infty$.

3 Conclusions

Our result sheds more light on the interior dynamics of self-attention transformers and might help identify reduced effective models.

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Bayesian inversion methods and toolbox for their application to accidental radionuclide releases

Antonie Brožová^{1,2}, Michal Uliáš^{1,3}, Ondřej Tichý¹, Václav Šmídl¹

¹Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague

²Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Prague

³Faculty of Information Technology, Czech Technical University in Prague, Prague

brozoant@cvut.cz

Keywords

Inverse problems, Bayesian inference, Inversion toolbox, Atmospheric inversion

1 Inverse problems and Bayesian inference

Linear inverse problems arise in many research areas, including medical imaging, genomics, and atmospheric emission estimation. They are often formulated as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ denotes the measured data, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the unknown source vector, and $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n}$ defines the relationship between them. The error term \mathbf{e} is typically assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and precision ω , i.e. with covariance matrix $\omega^{-1}\mathbb{I}$. In the simplest case, when $n = p$ is reasonably small and \mathbf{H} is well conditioned, the problem can be solved by directly inverting \mathbf{H} . In real-world applications, however, this is rarely the case: n and p may be large and unequal, and \mathbf{H} is often ill-conditioned. Moreover, the structure of \mathbf{H} may not be known, or it may contain errors. As a result, inversion becomes numerically unstable, and when the number of unknowns exceeds the number of measurements, the solution is generally not unique. Therefore, minimizing the mismatch between the data and the model prediction, here expressed as

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{x}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}\|_2^2, \quad (2)$$

typically requires regularization, for example through assumptions of sparsity or smoothness.

The Bayesian approach provides a natural way to incorporate such regularization, or more generally prior information, into the estimation process. Under Gaussian observational noise, Eq. (1) induces the likelihood

$$\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}, \omega^{-1}\mathbb{I}), \quad (3)$$

which describes the distribution of measurements given \mathbf{x} . Bayes' theorem combines this likelihood with a prior distribution on \mathbf{x} to obtain the posterior distribution. More complex hierarchical models may further specify the distributions of ω , \mathbf{x} , or other hyperparameters. In such cases, the posterior is often not available in closed form, and an approximate inference method is required. One option is variational Bayes, which approximates the posterior by removing selected posterior dependencies between unknown random variables and estimating the parameters of the approximating distribution by coordinate descent.

2 Atmospheric inversion

In atmospheric emission estimation, the unknown temporal profile, represented by the vector \mathbf{x} in Eq. (1) and called the source term, is estimated from ambient measurements. In this setting, \mathbf{y} contains radionuclide observations from a network of measuring stations, and the source-receptor-sensitivity (SRS) coefficients form the matrix \mathbf{H} describing transport from the source location to the detectors.

The true source term is typically unknown, which makes direct assessment of reconstruction quality difficult. In practice, the inferred source term can usually only be compared with previously published estimates obtained using different datasets or methods. This makes reproducible code particularly important in atmospheric inversion studies. Motivated by this, we develop a modular and extensible Python toolbox for atmospheric inversion.

We assume additive Gaussian errors, so the likelihood is again given by Eq. (3). The precision parameter ω is estimated within a variational Bayes framework, reducing the need for a manual tuning. The proposed toolbox implements three prior models for \mathbf{x} . The simplest is variational ridge regression, in which the prior shrinks the estimate of \mathbf{x} towards zero while the hierarchical model estimates the strength of this regularization. It is achieved by following priors

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{x} &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, v^{-1}\mathbb{I}), \\ v &\sim \mathcal{G}(\alpha_0, \beta_0).\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

A more flexible alternative is the sparse prior model. Here, the regularization strength is not shared across all elements of \mathbf{x} , allowing some components to remain close to zero while others take nonzero values, thereby promoting sparsity. The priors are

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{x} &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \text{diag}(v^{-1})), \\ v_j &\sim \mathcal{G}(\alpha_{0j}, \beta_{0j}), \quad j = 1, \dots, n,\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

where $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ denotes the diagonal matrix formed from the vector \mathbf{v} .

The most advanced implemented source-term model is the Least-Squares Adaptive-Prior-Covariance (LS-APC) prior [2]. This model also estimates the prior covariance structure through a more flexible parameterization. The covariance matrix is decomposed as a product of structured matrices, yielding a tridiagonal covariance matrix. As a result, not only the marginal variances of \mathbf{x} but also the covariances between neighboring components are inferred. Since the elements of these matrices are themselves treated as random variables with prior distributions, the model provides a flexible regularization mechanism with little or no manual tuning.

In addition, we implement correction models for errors in the SRS matrix \mathbf{H} . Assuming that these errors are small, an elastic correction model is used to constrain the admissible perturbation. The SRS coefficients are interpreted as a continuous spatio-temporal field, and the location and time of each measurement may be shifted within predefined bounds. These shifts are estimated jointly with the source term \mathbf{x} in a hierarchical Bayesian model. We implement two such models: BiasCorr [3] and BiasCorrGP [1]. The first is a hierarchical model with Gaussian and Gamma prior distributions on its parameters and shift correlation determined by spatial and temporal distance between measurements. The second employs a Gaussian process prior for the shifts, which enables estimation of the correction even at locations where no measurements were taken. The correction model can be used separately or jointly with the source-term models to find the best possible solution.

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Tuning Robust Sequential Decision-Making Models in Adversarial Environments

Jurij Ružejnikov^{1,2}, Tatiana Valentine Guy^{1,2}

¹ Department of Information Engineering, Faculty of Economics and Management, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, 165 00 Prague, Czech Republic

² Department of Adaptive Systems, Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences, 182 00 Prague, Czech Republic

ruzejnikov@pef.czu.cz

Keywords

Threatened Markov Decision Process, Parameter Sensitivity, Non-stationary Environments, Robust Reinforcement Learning

1 Introduction

Modern reinforcement learning (RL) has achieved remarkable performance across various complex domains, yet its success is largely predicated on the assumption of a stationary environment [9]. This assumption is critically challenged in real-world applications where intelligent adversaries (ADVs) strategically adapt their behaviour to disrupt an agent’s objectives, rendering traditional Markov Decision Process (MDP) optimal policies inadequate [8]. Foundational Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) theory typically addresses adversarial interactions by applying game-theoretic approaches to find system-wide equilibria [1, 6]. However, these methods often rely on strong assumptions regarding ADV rationality and convergence. In contrast, the Threatened Markov Decision Process (TMDP) framework [5] adopts a decision-theoretic perspective grounded in Adversarial Risk Analysis [10, 7]. By leveraging a single-agent perspective, it allows the decision maker (DM) to optimize against an unknown ADV without relying on equilibrium constraints. While offline and online value iteration for TMDPs have proven effective under quasi-stationary conditions [11], achieving fully non-stationary RL solutions remains an open research challenge [4, 2]. Adapting to highly volatile adversaries requires careful tuning of the underlying estimators to ensure the DM remains responsive to sudden strategic shifts over time.

2 Main contribution

This work extends foundational TMDP value-iteration algorithms introduced in [11] by comprehensively investigating how parameter sensitivity in online and offline learning scenarios impacts performance in environments where the presence of an ADV introduces non-stationarity. We present a systematic sensitivity analysis of the online and offline TMDP value-iteration algorithms. We evaluate the impact of hyper-parameters (e.g., the discount factor) on the agent’s convergence speed and asymptotic performance. We demonstrate how the initial configuration of these parameters dictates the trade-off between rapid adaptation and stable policy execution in the presence of an active ADV. Furthermore, we address an inherent challenge in the Bayesian learning approach used to model the ADV’s policy in [11]: as the agent accumulates observations, the belief estimator’s sensitivity to new data naturally decreases. This stabilising effect, while beneficial in stationary settings, can hinder the agent’s ability to adapt to sudden changes in the ADV’s decision rule during the late stages of learning. Through extensive empirical evaluation within a stochastic, multi-agent Coin Game environment [3, 13, 11], we analyse how strategic parameter initialization mitigates this issue. We benchmark the resulting agent configurations against both heuristic and Q-learning baselines [12], as well as TMDP Q-learning [5] under various hyperparameter setups, to quantify the effects of hyperparameter selection on overall robustness against an active ADV.

3 Conclusions

Our findings demonstrate that this sensitivity analysis provides crucial guidelines for hyperparameter tuning. Proper tuning significantly improves the DM's robustness against non-stationary adversaries by carefully balancing early-stage learning speed with late-stage adaptation capability. Collectively, these insights enhance the practical applicability of the TMDP framework in safety-critical, adversarial domains where continuous adaptation is required.

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Recursive Estimation of ARX Model with Parameters Dependent on High-Dimensional Discrete-Valued Regressors

Miroslav Kárný¹, Tomáš Procházka¹

¹The Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Department of Adaptive Systems, Pod vodárenskou věží 4, Prague 8, 182 00, Czech Republic

`school@utia.cas.cz, prochazka@utia.cas.cz`

Keywords

small data, Bayesian estimation, mixture, approximation principle, minimum relative entropy principle

1 Introduction

A normal autoregressive model with external variables (ARX) is a quite simple and powerful model for predicting and influencing continuous-valued output linearly dependent on the regression vector cite-Pet:81.

There is a broad class of problems in which the unknown regression coefficients and driving noise variance depend on an external, observable, discrete-valued variable. When learning, it is formally possible to sort the observed data according to the observed discrete value and update (in a Bayesian way) the belief about possible values of the corresponding unknown ARX parameters. This way fails whenever the cardinality of the discrete-valued variable is comparable to or larger than the number of processed data records. This is a generic obstacle, especially when the variable represents a discrete-valued vector.

The paper addresses this problem by using and estimating the mixture of ARX models [4, 7] with components indexed by individual values of entries of the indexing vector. The recursive feasible approximate Bayesian estimation of this model is proposed using the universal approximation principle. The processing counteracts the accumulation of inevitable approximation errors by using the minimum relative entropy principle that leads to an efficient, data-based forgetting. The gained estimator is applied to a scenario encountered in an advanced application in the domain of solid-state physics.

2 Main contribution

A systematic deductive solution for a generic class of estimation problems facing a lack of data is found. An initial experiment with a real-life scenario from solid-state physics is presented. It addresses the yet unsolved problem with mixed data in a vein similar to [3]. Methodologically, it demonstrates the strength of Bayesian learning [2, 10, 8] enhanced by the approximation principle [1, 5] and the minimum relative entropy principle [5, 11].

3 Conclusions

Our preliminary study looks quite promising, but we are aware that not all available tools are fully exploited. The use of mixture ratios [6, 9] is the immediate next option to be tried. Even the current solution will require a lot of simulation-based and real-life, cross-domain applications.

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DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION, AND MACHINE LEARNING ANALYSIS OF AN EEG-BASED MOBILE ROBOTIC CONTROL SYSTEM

Florenc Skuka¹, Erlis Ciko¹ Arban Uka¹

¹ Department of Computer Engineering, EPOKA University, Albania

fskuka@epoka.edu.al, eciko22@epoka.edu.al, auka@epoka.edu.al

Keywords

Brain–Computer Interface, EEG, Mobile Robotics, Common Spatial Patterns, Linear Discriminant Analysis

1 Introduction

By translating neural activity to control signals, brain–computer interfaces (BCIs) enable direct communication between the human brain and external devices [3]. Among the different non-invasive modalities, electroencephalography (EEG) is widely used due to its portability, high temporal resolution, and relatively low cost. EEG-based BCIs have a number of applications including robotic platform control, allowing individuals to interact without needing to touch or be involved physically with their systems and providing potential assistive solutions for individuals with motor impairments.

However, reliable real-time control using EEG signals remains challenging due to noise, artifacts, and strong inter-subject variability. Extracting meaningful information from multichannel EEG recordings therefore requires appropriate signal processing and machine learning techniques. Numerous classification methods have been proposed for EEG-based BCIs, ranging from classical statistical models to more advanced machine learning approaches [2].

This work presents the design and implementation of an EEG-based robotic control system that integrates a real-time BCI platform with a complementary machine learning analysis of motor imagery signals. The system uses the Emotiv EPOC Flex Gel headset for EEG signal acquisition and an Arduino UNO R3 platform to control a mobile robotic vehicle. In parallel, machine learning techniques are evaluated using the PhysioNet BCI Motor Imagery dataset in order to assess the effectiveness of established feature extraction and classification methods for EEG decoding.

2 Main contribution

The proposed system integrates EEG signal acquisition, signal processing, and robotic control into a unified experimental platform. Mental commands detected through the Emotiv headset are translated into navigation commands for a mobile robotic vehicle built using two A6207 DC motors in a rear-wheel-drive configuration and controlled by an Arduino microcontroller. Communication between the BCI software and the robotic platform is implemented using the Emotiv Cortex SDK together with a Python-based interface enabling real-time serial communication.

To complement the hardware implementation, machine learning experiments were conducted using the PhysioNet BCI Motor Imagery dataset. EEG signals were preprocessed and analyzed using Common Spatial Patterns (CSP) for feature extraction, a widely used spatial filtering technique for motor imagery EEG analysis [1]. Classification was performed using Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), a commonly adopted approach in EEG-based BCI systems [2].

Two classification tasks were evaluated: binary discrimination between rest and movement imagery, and multiclass classification of directional motor imagery (left hand, right hand, both hands, and both feet). Due to the high variability of EEG signals across individuals, experiments were conducted on a per-subject basis. Experimental evaluation demonstrated strong classification performance, achieving a mean accuracy of 95.49% ($\pm 4.18\%$) for binary classification and 83.24% ($\pm 7.61\%$) for multiclass motor imagery tasks.

3 Conclusions

This work demonstrates the feasibility of controlling a mobile robotic platform using EEG-based brain–computer interfaces combined with machine learning methods for motor imagery decoding. By combining real-time robotic control with offline machine learning analysis, it serves both to demonstrate a practical implementation of BCI-driven robotics as well as to conduct an experimental evaluation of established EEG signal processing techniques. The findings point to the necessity of subject-specific calibration and robust preprocessing when working with EEG signals. Future work will focus on improving generalization across subjects, incorporating more advanced artifact removal techniques, and exploring adaptive learning approaches for real-time BCI applications.

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Multi-Teacher GNN Knowledge Transfer for Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks

Yuan-Hung Chao, Chia-Hsun Lu, and Chih-Ya Shen¹,

¹ Department of Computer Science, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan

yhchao@lbstr.cs.nthu.edu.tw, chlu@lbstr.cs.nthu.edu.tw, chihya@cs.nthu.edu.tw

Keywords

Graph Neural Network, Kolmogorov-Arnold Network, Knowledge Distillation, Knowledge Amalgamation

1 Introduction

GNNs have become a standard approach for node classification on graph-structured data, with representative architectures such as GCN, GAT, SGC, and APPNP achieving strong empirical performance [3, 8, 9, 1]. However, most GNNs still require graph propagation or message passing at inference time, which limits efficiency on large-scale graphs and complicates deployment in resource-constrained settings.

KANs [4, 5] are a recent neural architecture that replaces fixed activation functions with learnable spline-based univariate functions. Their design offers strong nonlinear expressiveness and has shown promise in several learning problems. Recent work has begun to combine KAN with graph learning, but existing studies mainly emphasize GCN-style architectures [2, 11]. It remains unclear whether KAN can consistently benefit other widely used GNN backbones and whether KAN is also suitable as a graph-independent student in knowledge distillation.

To address these questions, we make two contributions. First, we introduce three KAN-based GNN variants: KGAT, KSGC, and KAPPNP. Second, we adopt a multi-teacher knowledge amalgamation framework [10] to transfer knowledge from multiple graph-dependent teachers into a graph-free KAN student. Our hypothesis is that KAN can improve both the expressive power of GNN teachers and the effectiveness of the distilled student, especially when the teacher set is structurally diverse.

2 Main Contributions

- We propose three new architectures, KGAT, KSGC, and KAPPNP, which combine the nonlinear representation power of KAN [4] with the strengths of GAT [8], SGC [9], and APPNP [1], respectively, to improve GNN performance.
- We design a training framework based on multi-teacher knowledge amalgamation that transfers knowledge from multiple teacher models to a graph-independent KAN student model, improving inference efficiency.
- We validate our approach on multiple benchmark datasets, showing the superior performance of the proposed models. We also evaluate different KAN variants in knowledge distillation tasks and conduct ablation studies to analyze the contribution of each component.

3 Proposed Approach and Experimental Results

A KAN layer replaces conventional linear transformation plus fixed activation with learnable univariate spline functions [4]. We incorporate this idea into three representative GNNs.

KGAT. Starting from GAT [8], we study two KAN insertions. *KGAT_arch1* replaces the attention-scoring nonlinearity with a KAN layer, while *KGAT_arch2* replaces the linear feature projection with KAN. This allows attention coefficients to be computed from a more expressive nonlinear transformation.

Table 1: Accuracy of representative teachers and the best distilled KAN student.

Model	Cora	CiteSeer	AMZ-P
GAT	0.812	0.703	0.903
KGAT	0.819	0.726	0.915
SGC	0.814	0.718	0.900
KSGC	0.802	0.724	0.902
APPNP	0.811	0.724	0.906
KAPPNP	0.814	0.726	0.913
Best distilled KAN student	0.827	0.740	0.921

KSGC. Starting from SGC [9], we preserve the efficient k -step propagation $\hat{A}^k X$ and apply a KAN layer after propagation. This adds nonlinear modeling capacity while largely retaining the simplicity of SGC.

KAPPNP. Starting from APPNP [1], we replace the MLP predictor with a KAN layer before personalized PageRank propagation. The propagation mechanism remains unchanged, but the initial prediction function becomes more expressive.

For knowledge transfer, each teacher produces logits \mathbf{Z}^t , and similarity-based attention weights α_t are used to construct a super-teacher target:

$$\mathbf{z}_i = \text{softmax} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t \mathbf{Z}_{[i,:]}^t \right). \quad (1)$$

The graph-independent KAN student is trained by combining distillation and hard-label supervision:

$$\mathcal{L} = \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}} + (1 - \lambda) \mathcal{L}_{\text{hard}}. \quad (2)$$

This design allows the student to absorb complementary knowledge from heterogeneous teachers while avoiding graph dependency during inference.

We evaluate on three benchmark datasets: Cora and CiteSeer [6], and Amazon-Photo [7]. We follow the common semi-supervised setting with 20 labeled nodes per class for training, 30 per class for validation, and the remaining nodes for testing. Results are averaged over 10 runs.

Table 1 shows that KGAT is the strongest teacher among the proposed models and consistently outperforms vanilla GAT on all three datasets. KAPPNP also improves over APPNP across all datasets. KSGC performs competitively, improving over SGC on CiteSeer and Amazon-Photo but dropping on Cora, suggesting that the benefit of KAN insertion is architecture-dependent rather than uniform.

We next evaluate multi-teacher knowledge amalgamation using conventional GNNs, KAN-based GNNs, and their combinations. The strongest student models are obtained from *heterogeneous* teacher pairs that combine one KAN-based GNN with one conventional GNN. Specifically, the best student accuracy on Cora is 0.827 using **KSGC+GCN**; on CiteSeer it is 0.740 using **KSGC+GAT**; and on Amazon-Photo it is 0.921 using **KGAT+GCN**. In contrast, pairs composed of two conventional GNNs or two KAN-based GNNs are generally weaker. This indicates that teacher diversity matters more than simply pairing two individually strong models.

Finally, the distilled KAN student substantially reduces inference cost because it no longer depends on graph propagation. In our implementation, on Cora the KAN student requires 0.099 seconds versus 0.254 for GCN and 1.469 for GAT; on Amazon-Photo it requires 0.162 seconds versus 0.892 and 4.906, respectively. These results support the practical value of graph-free KAN students for efficient deployment.

4 Conclusion

We presented a two-stage framework for scalable graph learning: KAN-enhanced GNN teachers and a graph-independent KAN student trained by multi-teacher knowledge amalgamation. Experiments show that KAN can strengthen representative GNN backbones, with KGAT providing the most consistent gains, and that structurally heterogeneous teacher pairs produce the strongest students. The resulting KAN student achieves both strong accuracy and much faster inference, making it a promising alternative for efficient node classification and broader graph-learning applications.

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Hybrid Data-Driven Models for Hotel Demand Analysis and Forecasting: Evidence from Real-World Booking Data

Luis Nobre Pereira^{1,2}, Luciano Viverit^{3,4}, Cindy Yoonjoung Heo⁵, Daniele Contessi⁴, Piero Luchi^{3,4},
Lara Ferreira^{1,2}

¹ University of Algarve / School of Management, Hospitality and Tourism

² Research Centre for Tourism, Sustainability and Well-being

³ Hotelnet, srl

⁴ Travelbrain, srl

⁵ EHL Hospitality Business School, HES-SO/ University of Applied Sciences and Art Western

lmp@ualg.pt

Keywords

hybrid models, machine learning, hotel demand forecasting, conversion rate, hospitality analytics

1 Introduction

The increasing availability of granular reservation data has created new opportunities to improve demand modelling and forecasting in the hospitality industry. At the same time, the growing complexity of booking behaviour requires analytical approaches capable of combining domain knowledge with advanced data-driven techniques. Hybrid modelling frameworks integrating econometric methods and machine learning algorithms have emerged as promising tools to address these challenges in hospitality analytics. This study presents a unified hybrid modelling framework applied to real-world reservation data from European hotels to analyse booking behaviour, conversion dynamics, and demand forecasting.

2 Main contribution

The first component of the framework focuses on identifying the determinants of conversion rates in direct booking channels. Hotels increasingly invest in digital platforms and marketing campaigns to stimulate direct bookings and reduce commissions paid to online travel agencies (OTAs). However, the factors that transform booking requests into confirmed reservations remain insufficiently understood. Previous research highlights the role of digital engagement and artificial intelligence technologies in shaping customer behaviour and conversion processes in online environments. Using a panel dataset with monthly observations from 54 hotels located in three European seasonal destinations, regression models are estimated to identify the drivers of conversion rates. The results indicate that price-related variables and location characteristics play a significant role in explaining variations in conversion performance across hotels.

The second component addresses the seasonal dynamics of booking conversion. Although hotels receive a large volume of booking requests, only a small share is converted into confirmed reservations, introducing additional uncertainty into demand forecasting and revenue management decisions. To better understand this phenomenon, a hybrid data-mining framework is proposed. Machine learning algorithms are first employed to segment stay dates according to booking patterns. Subsequently, logistic regression models estimate the probability of conversion within each segment. This approach allows the identification of heterogeneous behavioural patterns across demand segments and provides actionable insights for conversion rate optimization. The framework builds on recent empirical evidence highlighting the importance of identifying key drivers of hotel booking conversion dynamics.

The third component focuses on hotel occupancy forecasting using interpretable machine learning methods. Accurate forecasts are crucial for revenue management strategies, pricing decisions, and capacity planning. While deep learning approaches have shown promising forecasting performance in hospitality demand prediction, their lack of interpretability may limit managerial adoption. To address this limitation, a two-step modelling strategy is proposed. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is first used

to reduce the dimensionality of booking curves and group them according to similar patterns. These components are then incorporated into pickup forecasting models to predict daily occupancy levels. This approach builds on previous studies applying machine learning techniques to cluster booking curves for hotel demand forecasting [0]. The framework is tested using booking data from three European hotels between 2018 and 2022 and compared with traditional additive pickup models and clustering-based approaches.

3 Conclusions

Taken together, these three studies illustrate how hybrid modelling strategies can improve the understanding of hotel demand formation and forecasting. By combining econometric models, machine learning techniques, and dimensionality reduction methods, the proposed framework provides a comprehensive approach to analysing booking behaviour and predicting demand. The results highlight the potential of integrating interpretable artificial intelligence tools into hospitality analytics systems, enabling more informed pricing, marketing, and distribution strategies.

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Imitation learning framework based on Fully Probabilistic Design

Siavash Fakhimi Derakhshan, Ladislav Jirsa, Tatiana Valentine Guy

Adaptive System Department, Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences

fakhimi@utia.cas.cz, jirsa@utia.cas.cz, guy@utia.cas.cz

Keywords

Fully probabilistic design, imitation learning, Kullback-Liebler divergence, learning from demonstration, optimal policy

1 Introduction

Imitation learning is an important branch of machine learning and control theory that aims to construct decision-making policies from observed demonstrations. Instead of learning through repeated trial-and-error interaction with the environment, the learner tries to extract useful behavioral patterns from expert trajectories. This paradigm is especially attractive in applications where online exploration is costly, risky, or impractical, such as robotics, autonomous systems, industrial control, and human-centered decision support. In such settings, demonstrations provide a valuable source of information about how a task can be performed successfully.

However, traditional imitation learning methods face several limitations. Behavior Cloning, one of the most common approaches, directly maps states to actions using supervised learning. Although simple and computationally convenient, it often suffers from compounding errors when the learner encounters states that are insufficiently represented in the training data. Inverse Reinforcement Learning addresses this issue by inferring a latent reward function that explains expert behavior, but this comes at the cost of increased computational complexity and reliance on strong assumptions regarding optimality and reward structure. More recent adversarial methods improve flexibility and empirical performance, yet they typically require complex optimization procedures and substantial data.

This study introduces an alternative framework for imitation learning by building on the theory of Fully Probabilistic Design (FPD). Instead of formulating the control objective in terms of a reward function, FPD describes desired behavior through an ideal probability distribution over future states and actions. The learner then searches for a stochastic policy whose induced closed-loop behavior is as close as possible to this ideal model. This perspective provides a principled probabilistic foundation for decision-making under uncertainty and opens a new direction for imitation learning in environments where demonstrations are available but explicit rewards are not.

The importance of this idea lies in the fact that it does not seek to reproduce demonstrations mechanically. Rather, it evaluates demonstrated behavior according to how well it aligns with the learner's own probabilistic objective. As a result, demonstrations become a source of structured evidence rather than fixed templates to be copied. This makes the framework particularly suitable when demonstrations come from different experts, contain exploratory actions, or are only partially optimal.

2 Main Contribution

The main contribution of this study is the development of a novel imitation learning method that integrates demonstration-based learning with the Fully Probabilistic Design framework. The method learns a stochastic policy directly from trajectories while explicitly incorporating the learner's desired probabilistic behavior. This is a meaningful contribution because it moves beyond the two dominant paradigms in imitation learning: direct action replication and reward inference. Instead of asking what action the expert chose in a given state, or what hidden reward the expert might have optimized, the proposed method asks which demonstrated behaviors are most compatible with the learner's ideal closed-loop objective.

A central strength of the method is its ability to work with heterogeneous and imperfect demonstrations. The dataset may include trajectories generated by multiple experts, each with different styles, preferences, or levels of quality. In many real-world scenarios, such variability is unavoidable. Standard imitation learning methods often struggle in this setting because they implicitly assume that all demonstrations are equally informative and equally aligned with the target objective. The proposed framework overcomes this difficulty by assigning importance weights to demonstrated trajectory fragments according to their compatibility with the ideal probability distribution. Fragments that better support the desired behavior receive more influence, while less useful or poorly aligned fragments are naturally down-weighted.

Another major contribution is the algorithmic mechanism through which the policy is learned. At each decision step, the learner observes the current state and searches the demonstration dataset for subsequences beginning in that state. For each candidate action, it extracts relevant future trajectory fragments and uses them to estimate the local closed-loop behavior that would follow from that choice. This estimated behavior is then compared with the ideal probabilistic model through the Kullback–Leibler divergence. Candidate actions that produce smaller divergence are given a higher probability in the learned policy. This construction yields a stochastic decision rule that is both data-driven and explicitly goal-oriented.

This research, therefore, contributes not only a conceptual framework but also a practical computational procedure. The learner does not need to solve a full reinforcement learning problem, infer a reward function, or assume that demonstrations are perfectly optimal. Instead, it uses available data in a selective and principled way. This makes the method computationally attractive and theoretically elegant. It also offers a bridge between probabilistic control and imitation learning by showing that demonstration data can be filtered through an explicit probabilistic objective rather than treated as unquestionable ground truth.

A further contribution is the reinterpretation of imitation learning itself. In this framework, imitation is not merely copying observed actions; it is the process of extracting useful behavioral structure from demonstrations under a user-defined objective. This makes the learner more autonomous and robust. The policy that emerges is informed by demonstrations, but it is ultimately shaped by the learner’s own model of desirable behavior. Such a viewpoint is especially valuable in uncertain environments where demonstrations may be informative yet incomplete, inconsistent, or only locally relevant.

3 Conclusion

In conclusion, *Policy Learning via Fully Probabilistic Design* makes an important contribution to imitation learning by introducing a probabilistic alternative to reward-based and purely supervised approaches. This study shows that it is possible to learn stochastic control policies directly from demonstrations while avoiding explicit reward engineering and while remaining robust to imperfect or heterogeneous data. By embedding imitation learning into the FPD framework, the authors provide a method that is theoretically grounded, practically meaningful, and well-suited to uncertain decision-making settings.

The key value of the proposed approach is its ability to combine two important ideas: learning from demonstrations and optimizing toward a desired probabilistic behavior. Demonstrations are not copied blindly; instead, they are evaluated and weighted according to their relevance to the learner’s ideal objective. This allows the method to exploit useful information even when the available data are diverse, noisy, or partially suboptimal. At the same time, the use of stochastic policies makes the framework naturally compatible with uncertainty and complex control tasks.

Overall, the proposed work presents a clear and original perspective on imitation learning. Its main significance lies in showing that demonstration-based policy learning can be formulated as probabilistic matching between actual and desired closed-loop behavior. This insight broadens the methodological toolbox of imitation learning and suggests promising opportunities for future work in adaptive control, robotics, autonomous systems, and data-driven sequential decision-making.

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Avoiding the Curse of Dimensionality in Structured Control Problems via Separable Neural Networks

Mario Sperl¹, Lars Grüne¹

¹ Mathematical Institute, University of Bayreuth

mario.sperl@uni-bayreuth.de, lars.gruene@uni-bayreuth.de

Keywords

Neural networks, Optimal control, Separable Approximation, Curse of Dimensionality, Lyapunov Functions

1 Introduction

High-dimensional control problems arise naturally in large-scale and interconnected dynamical systems, but their numerical solution is limited by the curse of dimensionality. In particular, the computation of optimal value functions becomes intractable when classical grid-based or basis-function approaches are used.

Deep neural networks have emerged as powerful function approximators for high-dimensional problems. Beyond their empirical success, theoretical results show that deep networks can efficiently represent compositional and in particular separable functions with a number of neurons that grows only polynomially in the state dimension rather than exponentially (see, e.g., [4], [5]). This raises the prospect that high-dimensional control problems exhibiting suitable structural properties may admit efficient neural network representations.

Motivated by these developments, we investigate high-dimensional stabilization and optimal control problems and provide structural conditions that allow for an efficient representation of control Lyapunov functions and optimal value functions with neural networks.

2 Main Contribution

We begin by recalling an approximation result for separable functions with neural networks. A function $F: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called *d-separable* if there exist functions $F_j: \mathbb{R}^{d_j} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $d_j \leq d$ for $j = 1, \dots, s$, such that

$$F(x) = \sum_{j=1}^s F_j(z_j),$$

where each z_j consists of a subset of at most d components of x . Thus, F can be written as a sum of low-dimensional contributions depending only on small subvectors of the state.

It has been shown in [2] that *d-separable* functions can be approximated by suitably structured neural networks with a number of neurons that scales only polynomially in the state dimension n (for fixed d), rather than exponentially. More precisely, for fixed d the required network size grows on the order of

$$\mathcal{O}_{n \rightarrow \infty}(nd + n^{d+1})\mathcal{O}_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0}(\varepsilon^{-d}).$$

We briefly review this result and present the corresponding neural network architecture, which explicitly reflects the separable structure. We then investigate how this representation result can be exploited in control-theoretic settings.

First, we consider stabilization problems for interconnected systems whose interactions are described by a graph structure. The dynamics take the form

$$\dot{x}_i = f_i(x_i, u_i, x_{\mathcal{N}_i}), \quad i = 1, \dots, s,$$

where $x_{\mathcal{N}_i}$ denotes the collection of states corresponding to the neighbors of subsystem i . Building on results from [1], we demonstrated how a small-gain conditions between the subsystems guarantees the

existence of a separable control Lyapunov function. In view of the representation theorem for separable functions, this implies that the Lyapunov functions can be stored efficiently by a neural network; see also [7]. We illustrate the theoretical findings with a numerical example of a 10-dimensional interconnected system.

We then turn to infinite-horizon optimal control problems with cost functional

$$J(x_0, u) = \int_0^\infty \ell(x(t), u(t)) dt,$$

subject to the same class of interconnected dynamics. Analogously to the system structure, we assume that the running cost reflects the underlying graph interconnections, i.e., we can write

$$\ell(x, u) = \sum_{i=1}^s \ell_i(x_i, u_i, x_{\mathcal{N}_i}).$$

In contrast to the stabilization setting, the optimal value function $V(x) := \inf_u J(x, u)$ is in general not exactly separable, since optimal performance typically requires accounting for subsystem interactions. Instead, we introduce a *decaying sensitivity property*, which formalizes the idea that the mutual influence of distant subsystems decreases with the graph distance. Under such a spatial decay condition, we show that the optimal value function can be approximated by a separable function with controlled accuracy; see [8, 9]. We also present a numerical example in which a high-dimensional optimal value function is approximated using a separable neural network architecture.

We further discuss control-theoretic conditions that ensure the decaying sensitivity property. For linear-quadratic optimal control problems, such results are well established [6]. Extensions to nonlinear systems are the subject of ongoing research, with first results available in [3].

3 Conclusion

We established structural conditions under which high-dimensional Lyapunov and optimal value functions admit efficient separable representations, and demonstrated how these structures can be realized by tailored neural network architectures.

The results raise several questions for future research. These include extensions to non-smooth settings, the incorporation of more general compositional structures beyond purely separable ones, and the development of convergence guarantees and generalization bounds for the corresponding neural network architectures and training procedures.

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Certifying Properties of Control Systems: Algorithms, Verification, and Theory

Stefan Ratschan¹

¹ Institute of Computer Science
Czech Academy of Sciences

`stefan.ratschan@cs.cas.cz`

Keywords

Lyapunov functions, barrier certificates, formal verification, machine learning

Abstract

The notion of a Lyapunov function has been a fundamental object in control theory since its very beginnings, mainly due to its ability to certify the stability of a given dynamic systems. The automated synthesis of Lyapunov functions is an important topic [5, 10] where machine learning techniques are highly promising [1, 12].

However, stability is not the only desirable property of control systems. For example, many control systems include dangerous states, that should be avoided at all costs. Here, barrier certificates [7, 8] play an analogous role to Lyapunov functions by certifying that a given dynamical system is safe in the sense of never reaching a dangerous state. Further properties include reach-while-avoid properties [6, 4] and, in general, properties expressed in temporal logics such as STL [3].

In control, one is usually not only interested in verifying that a given system satisfies certain properties, but in designing control laws that ensure that a system satisfies such properties. Objects such as control Lyapunov functions [11] and control barrier certificate [2] certify the existence of such control laws.

In the talk, I will review algorithmic techniques for the synthesis and formal verification of such certificates, discuss extensions of recent results [9] that provide theoretical conditions for the existence of such algorithms, and sketch a general research program on certifying properties of control systems.

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N-to-1 Knowledge Transfer in Reinforcement Learning via Adaptive *Q*-function Selection

Marko Ruman¹, Tatiana V. Guy¹

¹Department of Adaptive Systems, Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

ruman@utia.cas.cz

Keywords

Reinforcement Learning, Knowledge Transfer, Multi-source Transfer, Value Error, Continual Learning, Adaptive Control

1 Introduction

Deep reinforcement learning (RL) has demonstrated remarkable success in solving complex sequential decision-making problems. However, standard RL algorithms are notoriously data-inefficient, typically requiring millions of interactions to master a single task [1]. Furthermore, such agents often exhibit catastrophic forgetting and struggle to generalize across varying environments. Knowledge Transfer (KT) addresses this inefficiency by enabling agents to reuse experience from previously solved source tasks to accelerate learning in a new target task [2].

While 1-to-1 transfer settings have been extensively studied, practical deployment of autonomous agents necessitates multi-source (*N*-to-1) transfer. In this scenario, an agent possesses a library of skills from *N* diverse prior tasks and must dynamically adapt to a novel, unlabeled environment. Existing methods for multi-source transfer often rely on shared representations, complex feature alignment, or auxiliary task labels [3, 4], which can limit their autonomy and scalability in non-stationary settings. In this work, we propose a theoretically grounded, purely autonomous mechanism that allows an agent to dynamically select the most suitable policy from its pre-existing library by estimating the long-term value error of each candidate skill.

2 Problem Formulation and Limitations of Naive Selection

We model the environment as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) defined by the tuple $(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{A}, T, R, \gamma)$. The agent has access to a library of *N* previously learned skills, where each skill $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is encapsulated by a learned *Q*-function, $Q_i(s, a)$, and a corresponding predictive environment model, $H_i(s, a) \rightarrow (s', r)$. Upon encountering a novel target task, the agent concurrently initializes a new target *Q*-function, Q_0 , and target model, H_0 , which are learned from scratch. At each timestep t , the agent must select a policy $\hat{Q}^t \in \{Q_0, \dots, Q_N\}$ to dictate its behavior.

A naive approach to this selection problem is to evaluate candidates based on their immediate Temporal Difference (TD) error: $\delta(Q_i; s, a, r, s') = Q_i(s, a) - (r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q_i(s', a'))$. However, empirical evaluations demonstrate that instantaneous TD errors are highly noisy and myopic. A low TD error on a single transition does not guarantee optimal long-term behavior, often leading agents to select heavily suboptimal or random policies, causing "negative transfer."

3 Value-Error-Based Adaptive Selection Methodology

To overcome the limitations of short-term signals, our proposed method relies on estimating the true *Value Error*, defined as $\Delta(Q; s, a) = Q(s, a) - Q^*(s, a)$, where Q^* is the unknown optimal *Q*-function. Theoretical insights establish that the value error is equivalent to the expected Bellman error over the discounted state-action occupancy distribution induced by the optimal policy. Because evaluating this exact expectation is intractable in unknown environments, we introduce three core approximations:

1. **Finite Rollout Approximation:** We approximate the infinite-horizon expectation using a finite model-based rollout of length L .
2. **Policy Substitution:** Lacking π^* , we simulate trajectories using the greedy policy derived from the candidate Q -function itself: $a_t = \arg \max_a Q_i(s_t, a)$.
3. **Error Substitution:** We replace the theoretical Bellman error with the sample-based TD error computed along the simulated trajectory.

The resulting value error estimate for a candidate Q_i at state s_t is given by:

$$\hat{\Delta}(Q_i; s_t, a_t) \approx \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \sum_{j=0}^L \gamma^j \delta(Q_i; \bar{s}_j, \bar{a}_j, \bar{r}_j, \bar{s}_{j+1}) \quad (1)$$

where $(\bar{s}_j, \bar{a}_j, \bar{r}_j, \bar{s}_{j+1})$ denotes the trajectory simulated using the source model H_i .

Crucially, to prevent the agent from trusting "hallucinated" rollouts generated by an inaccurate source model applied to a mismatched target environment, we introduce a model error penalty: $\epsilon_M(H_i) = \|(s_{t+1}, r_t) - H_i(s_t, a_t)\|_2$. The final adaptive selection criterion minimizes the weighted sum of the estimated value error and the model error over a short historical batch of size M :

$$\hat{Q}^t = \arg \min_{i \in \{0, \dots, N\}} \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=t-M}^{t-1} \left(|\hat{\Delta}(Q_i; s_k, a_k)| + w_M \cdot \epsilon_M(H_i; s_k, a_k, r_k, s_{k+1}) \right) \quad (2)$$

4 Experimental Evaluation

The proposed methodology was rigorously evaluated in the Arcade Learning Environment (Atari 2600) across three distinct scenarios designed to test robust policy selection and dynamic adaptation.

1. Static Task Selection: The agent was placed in the target task *Pong* and tasked with selecting among four fixed Q -functions: the optimal policy, a partially trained distractor, a random policy, and an irrelevant policy from a different game (*Bowling*). Our method successfully rejected the distractors, continuously selecting the optimal policy, achieving a Jumpstart Improvement (JI) of 0.93 and reducing the required training steps by over 99% (Learning Speed Improvement, LSI ≈ 0.997).

2. Adaptation in Non-Stationary Environments: The environment was configured to dynamically, and without warning, cycle between the dynamics of three different games (*Pong*, *Space Invaders*, *Star GUNner*) every 30 episodes. While standard baseline agents suffered catastrophic performance drops due to the non-stationarity, our selection mechanism flawlessly tracked the underlying environmental shifts, matching the performance of an Oracle agent possessing perfect task knowledge.

3. Bootstrapping and Autonomous Transitioning: To test the trade-off between exploiting prior knowledge and committing to newly learned skills, the agent was provided a suboptimal "head-start" policy alongside its own randomly initialized target policy (Q_{Scratch}). Early in training, the mechanism correctly relied on the suboptimal source to gather high-quality interaction data. As Q_{Scratch} converged in the background, the mechanism autonomously detected the crossover point where the self-learned policy became superior, permanently shifting its selection to Q_{Scratch} and driving the agent to optimal asymptotic performance.

5 Conclusions

We introduced a highly adaptive, N -to-1 knowledge transfer mechanism for deep reinforcement learning that operates without explicit task labels or prior domain knowledge. By estimating the long-term value error through model-based rollouts and heavily penalizing inaccurate environment models, the proposed framework safely and efficiently navigates libraries of pre-learned skills. Our empirical results demonstrate superior sample efficiency, robustness to distractors, and the critical ability to autonomously bootstrap a self-learned policy. This approach represents a significant step toward developing scalable, lifelong learning agents capable of operating in complex, dynamic, and unlabeled environments.

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AI techniques for anomaly assessment in port structures

Akhil John¹, Ana Hipólito², Ana Rita Gaspar³, Alexandra Nunes³, Marko Ruman¹⁴,
Maria João Barros¹, Nuno Alexandre Cruz³, José Cascalho¹, Armando B. Mendes¹

¹ IS2E, LIACC, University of the Azores, Portugal

² Trisolaris, Portugal and CIBIO, University of the Azores, Portugal

³ CRAS, INESC-TEC, University of Porto, Portugal

⁴ Dept. of Adaptive Systems, UTIA, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic

armando.b.mendes@uac.pt

Keywords

Underwater Robotics, Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV), Anomaly Detection, Sensor Fusion

1 Introduction

Maritime infrastructures, such as the walls and piles of the quays, are constantly degraded by seawater corrosion, waves, and biofouling [2]. Maintaining these facilities is essential to prevent economic loss and safety hazards, yet traditional diver-led inspections are costly, risky, and produce subjective data. To modernize this workflow, the AI4Ports project introduces a semi-automated approach using a cost-effective robotic system augmented with specialized sensors. We detail a methodology for automated anomaly detection and metric size estimation of defects, such as holes in metal piles and gaps in concrete walls, using multimodal sensor fusion. This system was developed and successfully tested on port structures in Ponta Delgada, Portugal.

2 AI-Driven Anomaly Assessment

Hardware Setup: The AI4Ports project utilizes the BlueROV2 platform (shown in Fig 1a) [1], an 8-thruster underwater vehicle providing six degrees of freedom. This ensures stability against currents during vertical structural inspections. The integrated payload includes:

- **Acoustic Imaging:** A Sonoptix Echo multibeam sonar (400/700 kHz) for navigation in turbid water and detecting structural voids.
- **High-Resolution Optical Imaging:** A Panasonic Lumix BGH1 camera in a custom waterproof housing, providing the high-fidelity data that standard navigation cameras cannot resolve.

Software Setup: The project establishes a standardized End-to-End Inspection Data Flow, from field deployment to the web dashboard, as illustrated in Fig 1b.

- **Field Operations:** A custom-built **Inspection Console** serves as a unified hub, precisely time-synchronizing live feeds from sonar and dual-camera systems, while QGroundControl runs in the background to manage core piloting and vehicle commands. Automated metadata labeling ensures all recordings are organized by location for streamlined archival and stakeholder review.
- **Data Management:** Following the mission, all synchronized logs and video files are uploaded to a secure central database. Users can then remotely review the footage and mission logs through a browser-accessible web dashboard.

For anomaly assessment the AI4Ports project developed a semi-automated solution for the characterization of structural defects. The visual analysis involves a multi-stage pipeline:

- **Structure Isolation:** The system identifies the limits of the pile or wall in the image and crops the frame by an additional 5% margin to isolate the structure and reduce the number of pixels evaluated in subsequent steps.

- **Anomaly Detection:** A machine learning model classifies the cropped frames into "with_hole" or "without_hole" categories. To ensure precision, images classified as "without_hole" with a confidence score below 0.85 are still passed for further review.
- **Contour Filtering:** Traditional computer vision techniques increase contrast to draw contours around anomalies. False positives are filtered by verifying contour shapes, such as discarding results that do not match the expected oval shape of a structural hole.

To achieve accurate damage metrics, we perform **Information Fusion** by combining optical data with distance measurements from the multibeam sonar. By determining the precise distance between the ROV and the structure, the system computes a scale factor. This allows the AI to infer the actual size of a defect in metric units rather than just pixels. Preliminary tests successfully identified a hole (7 cm wide x 15 cm high) in an inspected pile (shown in Fig 1c).

Figure 1: **a:** View of BlueROV2 inspecting a pillar. **b:** Data acquisition and management workflow. **c:** Final result of anomaly detection after information fusion.

3 Conclusions

AI4Ports demonstrates that integrating AI with cost-effective ROVs transforms high-risk manual inspections into a standardized, quantitative workflow. By establishing a validated "End-to-End Inspection Data Flow," the system provides faster, more consistent assessments supporting preventive maintenance and port sustainability. Future directions include developing a Severity Indexing system to prioritize repairs and implementing autonomous ROV missions to further reduce manual piloting needs.

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